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By

Marie Sesay

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The Dissertation Committee for Marie Sesay certifies that this is the approved version of the following dissertation:

DEVELOPMENTAL STUDENTS' LEVELS OF ENGAGEMENT AND STUDENT SUCCESS IN TWO-YEAR INSTITUTIONS:

A STUDY OF A SUBURBAN COMMUNITY COLLEGE SYSTEM IN TEXAS

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developmental Students' levels of engagement and student success in two-year institutions:

A Study of a SUBUrban Community College system in Texas

by

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Dedication

This study is dedicated to my deceased paternal and maternal grandparents from Sierra Leone, West Africa whom I never met. Though never formally educated, you wrote memoirs of your journey through amazing stories shared by many who were blessed to know you. You also planted seeds of hope in your children that have blossomed into forests in your

grandchildren. I have inherited the valuable lessons and share them with anyone willing to listen. I will forever live the words in KrioSABI No GeTWo RI {West African Proverb means Knowledge has no worry.} To my first teachers (the strictest parents in the world) Yarta B. and Aminata T. J. Sesay, thank you for daring to raise an American baby like we were in "Sa Lone." Your tough love worked...thank you. The perspective I have on life is filled with lessons of perseverance, faith, and education. These are the gifts I will treasure the most.

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developmental Students' levels of engagement and student success in two-year institutions:

A Study of a SUBUrban Community College system in Texas

Marie Sesay, Ph.D.

The University of Texas at Austin, 2011

Supervisor: Walter Bumphus

The need for development education for first year community college students is a growing trend and has a variety of solutions. Engagement and retention of these students is vital to the success of the student and the college in which they attend. Taking developmental education courses should not be repetitive hurdles for a college student. This study is to

establish the level of engagement of community college students who are enrolled in developmental education compared to students not enrolled in developmental education and their levels of success. The study evaluates administrative practices that engage developmental students in 2-year institutions.

This study aims at increasing successful outcomes in developmental education students through research. The study of levels of engagement, retention, successful strategies and academic support may be the determining factor of success of developmental education students and the 2-year institution in which they are enrolled.

Quantitative analysis will determine if there are significant differences in the engagement levels among first year developmental education students versus first year non-developmental college students within 2-year institutions and what institutional practices or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in 2-year institutions.

The instrument used was the 2009 SENSE (Survey of Entering Student Engagement). This tool assists colleges to focus on the "front door" of the students' college experience. This study uses an independent sample t-test to analyze the responses of students currently enrolled in developmental education courses versus students enrolled in non-developmental courses. The SENSE Survey was administered to students at 120 member community colleges during the fourth and fifth week of the fall 2009 semester. Fall 2009 was the first national administration of the survey. A 20-year community college system in suburban Houston, TX was specifically examined.

This study determines the significance of implementation of successful programs and academic support procedures to enhance the college experiences and performance of students enrolled in developmental education, increases more efficient use of college resources, and assists students to complete developmental courses to persist into college level courses.

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Chapter One: Introduction

Furthering education is one of the most common ways for personal and career advancement. Adults enroll in community colleges all over the country with goals of completing degrees to advance their career and personal interests. "As is typical in a recession, many community colleges are experiencing a surge in enrollment, at precisely the same time that they must-like many enterprises, both public and private-contend with choking constraints on resources" (McClenney, 2009, p. 1). Community colleges are filling the need of their communities by producing graduates better prepared for successful workforce participation and better prepared for higher education program entry. Community colleges have assumed an increasingly central role in the nation's education and training system (Kane & Rouse, 1999).

The American spirit and dream are more alive in community colleges than anywhere. In responding to the forces in society that are reshaping the world and the immediacy with which workers will require retraining or updating of job skills to maintain a vital economy, community colleges must act quickly, effectively, and decisively.

They must reconsider operational strategies and become engineers of

innovation and transformation- applying equal and positive to the external forces that are driving change. (Roueche & Jones, 2005, p. ix)

“Changes in the world of higher education are occurring at a dizzying pace. As a college community turns to address a challenge in one direction, a new and unexpected challenge propels it in another” (Roueche & Jones, 2005, p. x). Today, more and more students are seeking their education in community colleges. “Community colleges enroll over half of all beginning public postsecondary students including disproportionate numbers of adult, first generation, low income, and other underrepresented subpopulations” (Schuetz & Barr, 2008, p. 17).

Community colleges are designed to meet the needs of their local constituents. In addition to costing less than other higher education options, community colleges frequently offer flexible schedules, part time programs, and other services that are important to students who are working and/or have families. (Fabes & Matoon, 2007, p. 1)

Accessibility, cost efficiency, and small teacher to student ratios are some of the factors attracting students to community colleges. In addition, geographic accessibility and flexible scheduling have been supplementary attractions to community colleges (Kane & Rouse, 1999).

The surge in enrollments within community colleges across the nation is the basis for the need to assess the skills of entering students early in their college careers. New college students typically start their college ventures in the fall semester. According to McCabe (2000), “a third of those who enter college are underprepared” (p. vii). “It is critically important to focus resources on the needs of students in that first term,” states Kay M. McClenney, a senior lecturer at the College of Education at The University of Texas at Austin, who directs an annual survey of community college students (Blum, 2007, p. 2).

Developmental education is defined as a variety of courses that teach material not typically offered in high school but frequently necessary for success in college (Boylan & Bonham, 2007, p. 2). “Studies show that students who enroll in and successfully complete remedial courses in their first term are more likely to graduate or stay on track to graduate than any other population of students, including those who were never in

remedial education” (Blum, 2007, p. 2). Community colleges are challenged with the duty of transitioning students through developmental education (or also known as remedial) courses.

Schuetz and Barr note that:

As demands for institutional accountability increase and growing proportions of underprepared community college students are arriving on campus, this volume addresses the important task of identifying promising new perspectives and practices that offer colleges more effective leverage over student outcomes. (2008, p. 106)

Successfully transitioning students through the required levels of developmental education courses to college level courses has become an issue. The idea is that colleges have not been successful in the area of retaining developmental students and they leave college. More students leave their college or university prior to degree completion than stay (Tinto, 1987). Colleges that offer placement exams assess the student and may deem placement in developmental education courses necessary.

Placement exams are administered to incoming college students to determine if developmental courses are required. Students can be placed in developmental mathematics, developmental reading, or developmental writing courses. For example, students that do not meet the requirements for college level mathematics are advised or mandatorily placed into developmental mathematics courses, which teach students the basic mathematical principles needed to meet the skill level of college level mathematics. According to Blum (2007):

Students are required to take such courses based on their scores on placement tests taken after admission. Remedial math, along with other developmental education programs in reading and writing, is considered a core offering at nearly every two-year college, meant to provide a bridge to college-level work for underprepared students. (p. 2)

Students do not earn college credit but develop the skills necessary for the next level of developmental education. The levels of developmental education per subject range between two and four courses that must be passed before the student can transition into college level courses. If the required phases of developmental education are not passed, the student

gains no college credit and must enroll in that course again until they have successfully passed it (with a "C" or better).

Statement of Problem

The community colleges across the nation value access, student success, and teaching and learning. According to a report from the Community College Survey of Student Engagement:

Community colleges have long distinguished themselves through their efforts to put students first and their emphasis on teaching and learning. Innovations in curriculum, teaching strategies, and support services for students are hallmarks of these institutions. Yet while community colleges often pioneer new strategies, they don't have sufficient access to tools that help them assess their initiatives and measure their progress toward key goals. (CCSSE, 2010, p. iii)

Colleges must meet a variety of their students' educational needs, thus leading to the pre-requisite of developmental education.

"The reality for community colleges is this: No matter how good our colleges are today-and they do contribute mightily to educational access, work-force development, and economic prosperity-they simply are not yet good enough" (McClenney, 2009, p. 1). According to McClenney (2009), the following are problem areas:

- Roughly 14% of students who begin studies in a community college do not complete a single credit in their first academic term.
- At least a quarter of entering fall-term students do not return for their subsequent spring term. Almost half, on average, are gone from our classrooms by the second fall term.
- Just under 30% have earned an associate degree after three years.
- Fewer than half of community-college students, who aspire to earn associate or bachelor's degrees or transfer to four-year institutions, achieve their goals within six years. (p. 1)

Community colleges that encompass developmental education programs must examine closely if their programs are meeting the educational needs of their students. McClenney (2009) suggests that colleges answer the following questions:

- Does the college have in place, and does it consistently apply, policies that require assessment and course placement; enrollment in

remedial education in the first term of college (starting with reading, if so indicated); elimination of late registration; college orientation; and enrollment of all entering remedial students in a student-success course?

- What percentage of remedial courses are taught by part-time faculty members? By faculty members who have been adequately prepared to teach those courses?
- What percentage of the instructional budget is allocated to support remedial education? How does that percentage compare with the proportion of revenue-tuition and public support-that is produced through remedial-education enrollments?
- Does the college routinely track the progress of entering students in remedial education, collecting data about the percentage of students who successfully complete remedial courses and sequences as well as their first related college-level courses? Are those data widely shared and discussed?
- Does the college rigorously evaluate its alternative strategies for serving remedial students? Does the college budget reflect a commitment to bring effective strategies to scale? (p. 2)

Developmental courses are required courses for students who have been determined through assessment to need additional remediation in a reading, writing, and/or mathematics. Remediation is a significant part of higher education with approximately one-third of students needing developmental education (Bettinger & Long, 2004). These courses develop the students' comprehension in that subject. The problem is that developmental education courses are courses that are taken by community college students but not successfully completed.

Achieving the Dream (AtD) colleges have also found that students who fail to complete their first developmental education courses usually do not return the following semester; nor do they complete their other requirements for continuing in college. Their frustration with their lack of progress and the financial burden of having to retake courses contribute to low rates of retention and completion. (Biswas, 2007, p. 1)

Tracking students for college readiness or providing academic support

programs may be the answers to the developmental education problems.

Purpose of the Study

Colleges across the country have observed an increase in the number of students enrolled in developmental education courses. Schuetz and Barr (2008) note the impact of underprepared students.

Underprepared students have been a significant presence in community colleges for decades. The growing size of this student population and the urgent reality of workforce accountability and other demands that did not exist forty years ago are pushing colleges to find more effective ways to support success for such students. (p. 113)

“Each year more than half a million people enroll in remedial programs and gain the skills to become positive contributors to society” (McCabe, 2000, p. viii). The reasons for this influx of students vary from being un-equipped with college ready skills from high school, to a gap in the amount of time since the student was enrolled in college. Regardless of the reason, community colleges are charged with transitioning these students from remedial courses to college level courses. “Estimates vary, but many community-college educators and experts say that, on average, between 40 percent and 70 percent of new students entering two year colleges around the country place into remedial math” (Blum, 2007, p. 1). This statistic is reflective of all developmental courses and illustrates the necessity for successful outcomes in developmental education.

Some colleges have not been successful at providing the resources needed so students can move through the sequence of developmental education courses even though they can financially afford to be successful. “At a cost of only 1% of the U.S. higher education expenditures, remedial education is the nation’s most cost-effective educational program (McCabe, 2000, p. viii). The purpose of this study is to research developmental (or remedial) education, engagement levels, and institutional practices in 2-year institutions.

Research Questions

1. Are there significant differences in the engagement levels among first year developmental education students versus first year non-developmental college students within 2-year institutions?
2. What institutional practices or academic support initiatives support

developmental students' engagement in 2-year institutions?

Methodology

A quantitative method design was employed to research engagement levels of first year developmental education students enrolled in 2-year institutions along with the educational programs or institutional practices that support their retention and persistence. The instrument used was the SENSE (Survey of Entering Student Engagement). This tool assists colleges' focus on the "front door" of the students' college experience. The survey is grounded in research about what works in retaining and supporting entering students. SENSE collects and analyzes data about institutional practices and student behavior in the earliest weeks of college (SENSE, 2010a). This study used t-tests to enable the researcher to analyze the significant experiences of students enrolled in developmental courses versus students not enrolled in developmental education courses.

Definition of Terms

College-ready- A student academically prepared to apply the skills and knowledge successfully in entry-level courses offered at the college or university.

Developmental education- A variety of courses that teach material not typically offered in high school but frequently necessary for success in college (Boylan & Bonham, 2007, p. 2).

Engagement- Engagement refers to the amount of time and energy that students invest in educationally meaningful activities (McClenney, 2006).

Retention- An estimate to "measure how much student growth takes place, how valued and respected students feel on campus, and how effectively the campus delivers what students expect, need and want" (Levitz, Noel, & Richter, 1999, pp. 31-32).

Remediation- A process of taking a course again to further develop a skill.

Gatekeeper Courses- Pre-requisite courses within general education taken at the college level that must be passed in order to move forward in a degree program.

Success –Completion of a developmental education course by passing the course with a letter grade of "C" or better.

Delimitation

Delimitations of this study include the following:

1. This study will focus on engagement levels of developmental education students within two-year colleges.
2. The colleges that will be part of this study utilized the Survey of Student Engagement (SENSE).
3. The study will not attempt to predict that one strategy or academic support program will assist developmental education students persist through developmental education courses.
4. The study will focus on the experiences of community college level students who are enrolled or have been enrolled in developmental education courses only.

Limitations

The limitations to this study will include the following:

1. This research requires knowledge of survey design, statistical techniques, and research familiarity.
2. Survey constraints include the number of questions and length of student response.
3. Planning, creating, and designing of the survey entails months of design and examination of the study.
4. The research performed for this study focuses on students enrolled in developmental education courses within community colleges.

Assumptions

For the purpose of this study the following assumptions are made:

1. Every student enrolled in a developmental education courses are enrolled in that course for the purpose of moving through the sequences of courses to advance to college level courses.
2. The student is not receiving any additional assistance outside of the college to pass the developmental education courses; and every student responded to the survey accurately.

Significance of the Study

Like gatekeeper courses, developmental education courses are significant in moving students forward toward the ultimate goal of obtaining a degree. Learning what specific strategies or academic support procedures assist students to succeed through these courses is vital for the college and the student. Successful strategies or academic support

programs implemented early may aid students to successfully pass the levels of developmental education courses. Thorough research may assist colleges develop techniques specific to the students within their college and may aid students in saving time, money, and might remove anxiety while increasing successful outcomes in developmental education. The study of levels of engagement, retention, successful strategies and academic support may be the determining factors of success of the student and the college.

Summary

The need for development education for first year community college students is a growing trend and has a variety of solutions. Engagement and retention of these students is vital to the success of the student and the college in which they attend. Taking developmental education courses should not be repetitive hurdles for a college student. According to Bonham, "There are students taking these courses three, four, five times before they can pass them, and many who drop out, give up before they do" (Blum, 2007, p. 2). It is vital that community colleges implement successful program and academic support procedures to enhance the college experiences and performance of students enrolled in developmental education.

Chapter Two: Review of Literature

Overview of the Community College

Since the early 1900s community colleges have provided academic enrichment to students across the nation. The growth of community colleges has been credited to access and affordability of the courses that it offers. It is well chronicled that the G.I. Bill created opportunities to afford an education for veterans of the United States. The 1947 Truman Commission Report also contributed to the expansion of colleges (Bailey & Smith, 2006). To date, community colleges are vital educational entities for adults within their communities.

The American Association of Community Colleges (AACC) shares the following regarding community colleges:

Community colleges are centers of educational opportunity. They are an American invention that put publicly funded higher education at close-to-home facilities, beginning nearly 100 years ago with Joliet Junior College. Since then, they have been inclusive institutions that

welcome all who desire to learn, regardless of wealth, heritage, or previous academic experience. The process of making higher education available to the maximum number of people continues to evolve at 1,173 public and independent community colleges. When the branch campuses of community colleges are included, the number totals about 1,600. (AACC, 2010a)

Community colleges provide access to education for adults with no prior experience in higher education (CCRC, 2006). One hundred years after community colleges opened their doors, they have creatively strived to meet the needs of the changing community, trends in employment, cultures, and developmental needs of students.

Despite the efforts community colleges have made to provide educational training to all students, some students have not arrived prepared for the rigor of the course work. Though community colleges provide access, “only about one third of all community college students receive any degree or certificate, even eight years after initial college enrollment. Twenty percent do not complete ten credits in that period of time” (Bailey et al., 2005, p. 10). Two thirds of community college students are not academically prepared for college and contain academic skills weak in at least one major subject area (CCRC, 2008). In other words, community college students need additional support to assist them to be successful in their basic skills.

Basic skills deficiencies jeopardize students’ capability to thrive in college-level courses. In fact, the barriers that college students who are deficient academically face are burdensome. The Community College Research Center (2008) found that “students who enroll in remediation are less likely to complete degrees or transfer than non-developmental students (p. 3). In addition, nationally “nearly 50% of entering students drop out before their second year. Other students stay in school, but struggle to complete developmental sequences” (SENSE, 2010b). Colleges must find successful practices, programs, and solutions for the growing numbers of students enrolled in developmental education not only to fulfill the mission of the college, but to better serve every student seeking higher education.

In the future, community colleges have several obstacles to overcome.

A report published by California Tomorrow (2007) further details the educational challenges that community colleges must face:

But community colleges are also facing tremendous challenges that threaten to undermine their capacity to maintain, improve, and expand their innovative workforce preparation and basic skills programs.

Among these challenges are the pressures of unprecedented enrollment demand for the accessible and affordable educational programs, the growth in under preparedness among students entering their doors, and the challenges of developing and sustaining high cost instructional approaches and support services that are essential to meet the needs of students who are learning English, working several jobs, raising children and helping to support extended families. (p. 3)

With challenges, come opportunities for community colleges. Colleges have the opportunity to learn from their mistakes, and polish their accomplishments. The Creative Community College: Leading Change Through Innovation (2008) noted some certainties for colleges:

- The lines between K-12, community college, and baccalaureate institutions will disappear. The community college educational mission will absorb the others, to propel these colleges into becoming the largest segment of higher education.
- Student enrollments will increase four-fold on some campuses in a span of 20 years.
- Changing demographics will require colleges to provide developmental education, orientation, and first-generation student services for the largest at-risk student body ever seen on our campuses.
- Community colleges should not expect the already-reduced federal and state funding to return but rather raise funds to become more self-sustaining.
- Managing community colleges is a big business; some already have more students and personnel than the largest of universities and corporations.
- Community will never have the same connotation it had when community colleges were first being built or that it has today.
- By 2010, the century's first decade will have seen three of

every four community college presidents retired and replaced.

New leadership styles will accompany new leaders to their posts.

- Technology will enable and significantly improve faculty/student engagement. Soon, teachers and learning objects will virtually appear in three dimensions wherever and whenever students need.

Education will continue to be increasingly mobile. (Roueche et al., p. 253)

Theories and Models

Astin's student development theory. Astin's (1999) Student Development Theory supports college persistence and describes the emotional and physical drive that students apply towards their education. The learners' learning is enhanced by the rigor dedicated to their academic career. The student's academic development is enhanced by academic support programs and interaction. Astin's theory supports the idea that students with high levels of involvement in studying, extracurricular activities, and constant interaction with faculty are prone to persist than students who do not participate in the same activities. Though Astin's research has been based on university level students, generalities can be made regarding the importance of student involvement that in turn leads to student success within community colleges.

Tinto's interactionist theory. Vincent Tinto's (1987)

Interactionist theory of student persistence and retention describes the community college student as a melting pot of diversity. The theory supports the idea that each student arrives to college with an array of academic, cultural, and social backgrounds. The theory explains the reasons that some students succeed scholastically where other students do not. The cultural differences between students can also be a strong factor that alters student persistence. Some cultures stress the importance of education where others do not. Tinto further documents that academic and social integration for the student with the institution occurs through educational and social communities on the campus.

Tinto's integration model. Tinto's Integration Model (1987) suggests that institutions of higher learning that incorporate the academic environment with extracurricular interests of its students have a better chance of retaining those students. This model says that students involved

in both entities increase their chances of staying in college, which in return increases the colleges overall retention rates. Tinto developed a model that incorporates the significance of engagement activities and academics. The model links the formal and informal aspects of college that are essential in success of college students.

Overview of Developmental Education

One of the purposes of developmental education is to provide and categorize remedial services offered to students. Developmental education—often called “remediation”—has become an integral part of the community college mission, offering instruction in basic reading, writing, and math skills to enable under-prepared students to master the college curriculum (CCRC, 2002). The series of courses and services are created and administered in an effort to assist and retain students and ensure that they complete their higher education goals. Developmental education is, therefore an umbrella under which a continuum of courses and services are provided (Boylan & Bonham, 2007).

Community colleges offer open access education. This allows for a variety of student proficiencies in developmental subjects such as mathematics, reading, and writing. The open access allows for an array of students to enter college with variations of range in their levels of comprehension. Boylan and Bonham (2007) further noted that developmental education efforts also included a variety of courses that teach material not typically offered in high school but frequently necessary for success in college (p. 2).

According to the National Center for Education Statistics (2003) 99% of community colleges and approximately 70% of universities offer developmental courses. This is a strong indication that developmental education has additional challenges that college leaders must face.

“Although colleges attempt to increase student preparedness in a variety of ways, developmental education courses are the most visible form of remediation in community colleges” (CCRC, 2002, p. 1).

Developmental education provides students with the basic skills needed to successfully meet the competence criteria for college level course work. When completed, it provides an introduction to the student of what to expect in the college course they will enroll in for credit.

To attend to the needs of developmental education, institutions of higher learning must make remediation a priority. Colleges that are successful at providing the fundamentals needed by students to move them into college level courses are accomplishing the goals of remedial education. Boylan states we should not be shocked when developmental education is flourishing at institutions where it is precedence (2002). It is imperative that developmental education be a priority within community colleges because of the large number of students who are enrolling in one or more developmental courses per year.

Previous research has shown that intervention may lead to prevention for future students. A majority of first-time freshmen are considerably older and have not been in a classroom in a long time; they don't have the skills they need to succeed at college-level work without intervention (Roueche & Roueche, 1999). "Community colleges have a particularly important role. They educate the most deficient students and prepare them for employment and personal advancement" (McCabe, 2000, p. 13). This validates the necessity for intercession in developmental education for all ages and skill levels of college students.

Programs that have the ability to meet the needs of a variety of students have a stronger opportunity in retaining them and providing for their remediation needs. McCabe (2000) notes the following techniques, models, or structures that will contribute to successful remediation:

- Implementation of mandatory assessment and placement.
- Establishment of clearly specified goals and objectives for developmental programs and courses.
- Use of mastery learning techniques in remedial courses.
- Provision of high degree of structure in remedial courses.
- Use of variety of approaches and methods in remedial instruction.
- Application of sound cognitive theory in the design and delivery of remedial courses.
- Provision of a centralized or highly coordinated remedial program.
- Use of a formative evaluation to guide program development and improvements.
- Establishment of a strong philosophy of learning to develop program goals and objectives and to deliver program services.

- Provision of a counseling component integrated into the structure of remedial education.
- Provision of tutoring performed by well-trained tutors.
- Integration of classroom and laboratory activities.
- Establishment of an institution wide commitment to remediation.
- Assurance of consistency between exit standards for remedial courses and entry standards for regular curriculum.
- Use of learning communities in remedial instruction.
- Use of supplemental instruction, particularly video based.
- Provision of supplemental instruction to support remedial courses.
- Provision courses or workshops on strategic thinking.
- Provision of staff training and professional development for those who work with underprepared students.
- Provision of ongoing student orientation courses.
- Integration of critical thinking into the remedial curriculum. (2000, p. 45)

Developmental Education: Past, Present, and Future

Community colleges strive to provide open access within the community they serve. "Community colleges have extended an invitation in the spirit and language of the "open door" and laid out the welcome mat to a highly diverse population; community colleges are obligated on principle and funded by law to map the abilities of under prepared students in their curriculum and instruction, and to give those students true access to higher education" (Roueche & Roueche, 1999, p. 8).

As communities became more diverse, so did the community colleges. Students from all races, ethnicities, and social classes took advantage of the opportunity to educate themselves. Higher education went through a transformation period that brought an assortment of diversity within the student that was scholastically unprepared (McCabe, 2000). The birth of remedial developmental education in the 1960s was needed for the students who were not college ready. As demographics transformed, community colleges maintained their ultimate goal of access for everyone. Community colleges symbolize the American values of meaningfulness and purpose of every person (McCabe, 2000). These same values lead to fundamental changes in higher education in North America.

The early 1960s brought positive changes within community college classrooms, but faced future challenges in attempting to provide the same education for every student. In the 1960s, the nation urgently strived for equality, and higher education responded by providing opportunities for people who previously had been excluded. As a result, remedial education programs became essential (McCabe, 2000). During this era, developmental education provided access to persons with disabilities, older adults, and women. Community colleges made the dream of education a reality for many. Roueche (1977) noted that historically remedial courses were non-credit courses. College students protested spending time in a course for which no credit was allowed. "To make matters worse, students often recoil when told that they need to take (and pay for) courses that 'don't count' towards graduation. These courses stretch out the time and money to complete the degree, and some students see them as conspiracies to separate them from their money. Combine shaky preparation with suspicious attitude, and the odds of success aren't high" (Dad, 2009, p. 2). The decision to allow credit for development education courses is still of interest to students to this day. The 1970s brought additional ideas for developmental education within community colleges.

Not only was there question of whether remedial courses should be counted for credit but the question of mandatory testing also surfaced. Many minority advocates, concerned that minority students would be driven from colleges, vehemently opposed these changes (McCabe, 2000). The advocates suggested that mandatory testing discriminated minority students from college admission. These ideas came from the influx of students less prepared than their classmates. Teaching became a challenge for many instructors and students moved through the system without the proper proficiency upon graduation.

The 1980s were prosperous years for developmental education. The 1980s brought the birth of the National Association for Developmental Education (NADE). This organization was previously called the National Association for Remedial/Developmental Education in Postsecondary Education (NAR/DSPE) (Boylan & Bonham, 2007). 1984 was also the year the U.S. Department of Education recognized developmental education as a subject that warranted additional research.

Boylan and Bonham (2007) further discuss the advance of developmental education by noting in 1985 the National Center for Developmental Education contributed to the research and literature of the field by conducting a national study of exemplary programs and practices in developmental education. This study resulted in the publication of a directory of exemplary developmental education programs. The study also afforded the sponsorship of a national conference on exemplary practices in developmental education held in Atlanta, Georgia in 1986. The field of study was further justified with the creation of the first doctoral program in developmental education at Grambling State University in Grambling, Louisiana. The 1980s presented recognition and opportunities for the growing study of developmental education.

The 1990s brought support from corporations to endorse research towards developmental education. The Exxon Education Foundation and the National Center for Developmental Education collaborated to conduct the first national study on developmental education. "Using transcript analysis, the study not only gathered descriptive information on the state of the art in the field of developmental education but also identified relationships between methods, courses, services, and organizational structures and student outcomes" (Boylan & Bonham, 2007, p. 1).

The American Council of Developmental Education Association also added to the body of knowledge in developmental education. Boylan and Bonham (2007) noted the organization recognized those who have made outstanding contributions to the field as Fellows of the American Council of Developmental Education Associations. This organization bestows the highest honor for professionals in the field.

In 2011, developmental education is continuously a major issue for community colleges. Today, almost all community colleges offer developmental education courses, most in multiple levels (McCabe, 2000). "Nationally, 62 percent of remedial education students are deficient in mathematics, compared with 37.7 percent in reading and 55.6 percent in writing" (McCabe, 2000, p. 41). These figures indicate developmental education is an issue that requires continuous research locally and nationally.

Purpose of developmental education. The purpose of developmental

education is to categorize the services offered to students under a broad range of courses. As a result of developmental education services were created and administered in an effort to assist and retain students and ensure they complete their higher education goals. Community colleges offer “open access” education which allows for a variety of student proficiencies in developmental subjects such as math. Boylan and Bonham (2007) further noted that developmental education efforts also included a variety of courses that teach material not typically offered in high school but frequently necessary for success in college (p. 2).

Services for underprepared students must fully use the knowledge gained from successful remedial education programs. McCabe (2000) refers to additional characteristics to look for:

- Research has provided substantial insight into how underprepared students learn.
- Exemplary remedial education programs should serve as models.
- Many community colleges ignore available knowledge and continue to deliver services in under supported, traditional arrangements.
- Doing less than our best is unacceptable (2000, p. 52)

To date, there is not one correct way to manage developmental education but data, research, and recommendations to assist along the way. Bailey (2009) makes the following recommendations regarding developmental education:

- Rethink assessment, focusing on understanding what students need in order to be successful in college rather than simply concentrating on placement within the sequence of a curriculum.
- Abandon the dichotomy between developmental and college-ready students for a wide range of students above and below current developmental cutoff scores by opening college-level courses to more students and by incorporating academic support assistance into college-level courses.
- For those students whose skills are so weak that they could not be successful even in augmented college-level courses, especially work to minimize the time necessary to prepare students for entry into those courses. (2009, p. 3)

Challenges facing developmental education. There are a variety of challenges that developmental education must face. There is a need to increase the conversations regarding developmental education within the

legislature. It is imperative that we influence those who make decisions for education within our states with the facts regarding education.

Educators must enforce the importance of developmental education within our community colleges with legislature. Instead of conversations on who is to address the needs of developmental students, the discussion should be about how developmental education is going to be funded and supported. "If legislators talked about developmental education they usually talked about eliminating remedial courses or relegating them to the community colleges" (Boylan & Bonham, 2007, p. 2). "Relegating," as Boylan and Bonham (2007) noted, should include financial support from the state to address the growing needs of developmental educators within the state.

A second challenge is the need for national organizations to support and promote the field of developmental education. Developmental education has been in existence for over 30 years, yet the organizations are fairly new. In fact, a majority of the trained professionals in the growing fields are newly trained professionals in the field as well. For example, at one time there was only one professional organization in the field to support ideas of developmental education, now there are more.

According to Hunter Boylan, Director of the National Center of Developmental Education at Appalachian State University, in the article "30 Years of Developmental Education: A Retrospective" (2007), an organization for developmental education was not created until the late 1970s. Until that period, an organization did not exist to support the professional development and teaching and learning needs of developmental education.

"The legitimacy of the field was not established until Grambling State University (La) started the nation's first doctoral degree in developmental education in 1985" (p. 3). The same journal discussed the creation of the Technology Institute for Developmental Educators (TIDE) at Texas State University in San Marcos, Texas to train participants in a range of developmental education technology applications.

National Challenges. Nationally, the concern is that students are not prepared for the workforce. There are few unskilled jobs left, and the majority of new jobs require a high school diploma and some postsecondary education (Roueche & Roueche, 1999). With these expectations increasing, students will return to college to increase their workforce skills.

Community colleges should prepare for a surge in enrollment and developmental education needs. Proper training and development is needed for our ever-changing demographics.

Major changes in U.S. demographics are occurring at the same time as our greatest need for an educated citizenry. If trends continue more young people than ever before will reach adulthood without the skills and knowledge they need to be gainfully employed. (Roueche & Roueche, 1999, p. 3)

The demographic changes that are occurring in our country are affecting community colleges. Roueche and Roueche (1999) stressed that the national population is aging, living longer, working longer, and threatening our soon to be unstable social security system. Nationwide, community colleges are vital in providing training, development, or remedial education to our changing population.

McCabe (2000) noted a national guide should be instituted to assist community colleges in developing appropriate and effective remedial education programs:

- It is essential for our nation's future that a higher percentage of young adults gain the skills necessary for employment. Too many people are being lost.
- Most programs for seriously deficient students are unsuccessful and need a full revision.
- Business and industry representatives should be involved in developing the guide. A high percentage of successful remedial education students go into occupational programs or into the workplace. Skills needed to begin standard college work and those needed for information-age job entry are similar.
- Mathematics is a major hurdle for remedial education students. Goals in this discipline require careful review (p. 54)

Texas Best Practices. Hunter Boylan (2002) conducted research based best practices in developmental education in the Lone Star State (Texas). His published findings noted that developmental education is a priority, although not yet a high priority, in most Texas public community colleges. The idea of developmental education, formerly remediation, has been in existence for over thirty years, yet it is still not a main concern to

every institution in Texas. The Coordinating Board (TCB) reports that The Texas Success Initiative has produced changes in developmental education, but the changes have not been dramatic. The Texas Coordinating Board also noted attempts within Texas to decrease developmental education. In 1987, the Texas Academic Skills Program (TASP) was created. That initiative created a statewide examination required of most new college students mandated continuous developmental education prior to beginning college-level course work, and included passing the exam as a condition of continued enrollment. In 2003, TASP was replaced by the Texas Success Initiative (TSI). The Texas Success Initiative moves much of the responsibility for ensuring that students are qualified to do college level work to the institutions. While an initial assessment examination is still required, institutions are given much greater flexibility in assessing the preparedness of their students, and students are given greater flexibility in addressing their academic deficiencies. (TCB, 2004, p. 1)

Examples of strategies to consider are to incorporate intrusive advising, mandate advising, strengthen assessment programs, provide learning communities, paired courses or supplemental instruction. A handful of colleges minimized mandatory advising and gave students flexibility in choosing when they will address scholastic needs. This may not be a suitable technique as some students may not be aware of the value in advising as first-year college students and will need that guidance from an advisor.

In most institutions, assessment programs are stronger than advising and placement programs and should be utilized to meet the needs of developmental education students. The literature reflects the developmental education movement in Texas appears to be sluggish to implement innovative teaching techniques such as learning communities, paired courses, supplemental instruction and others (Texas Coordinating Board, 2005).

Potential Strategies of Success

Community colleges that develop strategies to lead their developmental education students to successfully passing their courses are attacking the issue before it becomes a problem on their campus. An example of a strategy that is working at Montgomery County Community

College (PA) is the implementation of a learning-assistance lab. The institution's learning-assistance lab has long offered general tutoring sessions for students taking remedial mathematics. The new program, in contrast, has tutors behave more like teaching assistants—attending classes and holding weekly help sessions designed around that specific course. The tutors are students or former students who have recently passed developmental-mathematics courses, along with some higher level math as well. (Blum, 2007, p. 2) Cleveland State Community College (TN) created an “emporium model” popularized by the National Center for Academic Transformation. Instead of attending lectures in basic math, elementary algebra, and intermediate algebra, remedial students come to a large computer lab where they solve math problems and, when they need help, work with on-site faculty members and tutors. “Courses are arranged in weekly modules with accompanying quizzes that can be retaken until students are ready for the next step” (Carey, 2009, p. 2). A strategy like this is likely to reduce remediation and increase retention. Statistically the approach has been successful for Cleveland State Community College and may serve as a guide for other community colleges.

Carey (2009) also noted that the percentage of remedial students earning at least a C in the three math courses jumped from 55% to 72% (pg. 2). The program has been so successful that the college is considering revamping the mathematics department. Other colleges are now considering implementing this project within their developmental education programs while researching additional programs that may benefit the developmental needs of their college.

Orientation. Additional programs that may benefit colleges exploring opportunities to strengthen their developmental education programs are implementing mandatory orientation and assessment for all incoming students. There is extensive literature that agrees with the benefits of mandatory orientation, assessment, and placement. Shuetz (2008) notes the following with reference to orientation:

Arguably, orientation activities welcome students to campus, introduce them to the kinds of educational opportunities available, resolve basic uncertainties about how to get started, suggest how to negotiate

campus environments, and describe how to engage more fully in the college experience over time. Although some of this kind of information is procedural, other vital elements are not. (pp. 25-26)

Roueche and Roueche (1999) suggest that student orientation should be a requirement, pointing out that universities are far better at instilling this rule than community colleges. Research has demonstrated that those who participate in new student orientations are more likely to be retained in community college than those who do not receive orientation (Boylan & Saxon, 2002). Jenkins (2007) notes students are successful when student success services are synchronized with programs such as advising, orientation, or early alert programs throughout the campus.

Orientation would serve as an introduction to the college and would provide the student with an opportunity to be introduced to departments within the college that are vital to his or her success. Orientations to the college can vary in detail. Orientation for new students provides a formal greeting and welcome for students new to higher education. Roueche and Roueche (1999) suggest students can feel misplaced in the institution that is characterized as impersonal or not socially inviting. A well-planned orientation can familiarize the student with the culture and climate of the campus.

Some orientations last a few hours where others take place over a weekend or longer. Overall, the most important aspect of orientation includes a clear introduction to the resources that will aid the student such as a tutoring lab or the office to receive counseling or mentoring services. Roueche and Roueche (1999) suggest that students be matched with qualified mentors to assist in explaining results of assessment exams and the purpose of developmental courses. Regarding student services success, Roueche and Roueche (1997) also noted that:

During orientation, students are provided with mentors-teachers and experienced students-who stay in contact with the student and regularly discuss questions and problems. The students are required to participate in collaborative activities, both extracurricular and academic, that strengthen their relationships with peers, and they are required to visit college units that can help with such services as applying for financial aid and finding affordable childcare

facilities. Some colleges report that better student evaluations and improved GPAs are two outcomes of enrolling students in cohort groups (groups that take all classes together for the first semester or quarter, follow “study buddy” system, and participate in extracurricular activities that require spending time together in pursuit of an assignment or social event) and that these outcomes have made the time and complexity of the effort required during the registration process worthwhile. (p. 2)

For the students attending college for the first time, orientation and proper advising can be the catalyst to a successful college career. “Many community college students face serious barriers to success in college, such as family and work responsibilities and deficient academic preparation. Indeed, it is precisely students such as these, who may not have access to baccalaureate institutions, whom community colleges seek to serve” (Bettinger & Long, 2004, p. 10).

Assessment. Compulsory assessment and placement is cited as best-practice recommendations for exemplary programs (Roueche & Roueche, 1999).

The authors noted the following regarding assessment and placement:

Information from colleges that make assessment and placement mandatory, together with data reporting the performance of all students taking remedial work, suggests that remediation correlates with improved performance over the rest of the college experience.

(1999, p. 47)

Developmental course success rates were positively linked with mandatory placement in both 2- and 4-year schools. These writers construe these findings as positive support for both mandatory assessment and placement. They contend that, under voluntary placement, the academically weakest students may not take the remedial courses at all and will not obtain the assistance that they need.

The Community College Research Center (2007) documented mandatory course placement after initial assessment has been somewhat more controversial with respect to outcome data. “Many students whose test scores suggest that they need some academic help to prepare them for college-level work do not end up enrolling in developmental education classes” (CCRC, 2008, p. 2). Not every state mandates assessment tests as

a tool to predict college placement. "California being the most prominent, students can enroll in college-level courses even if their scores on an assessment test suggest that they are not adequately prepared, so that enrollment in remediation effectively becomes voluntary" (CCRC, 2008, p. 2).

To contest the impact on student retention that may accompany mandatory course placement, McCabe (2000) informs colleges of the importance to encourage students and increase motivation for college into placement in remedial coursework. McCabe notes that many students convey that they do not comprehend why they are required to complete remedial coursework. A thorough explanation of the benefits of assessment and strategic follow up will assist students see the value in enrolling in developmental courses.

The Community College Research Center (2008) has further researched the impact of educational assessments for students taking into consideration the financial costs and stigmas associated with developmental education courses. The center (2008) notes:

Developmental education assessments are in reality "high stakes" tests. Failing such tests often leads to enrollment in remediation with attendant costs and delayed progress for students. Yet those services have dubious benefits, at least in the way that developmental education is currently carried out. But despite the importance of the test outcomes, there is no national consensus about what level of skills is needed to be "college ready" or how to assess that level.

(p. 2)

McCabe (2000) made the following recommendations for assessment and evaluation:

- If the college does not know a student is deficient, it cannot provide an appropriate program.
- It is unfair to students and undermines program quality if students are allowed to enroll in courses for which they are underprepared and have little prospect of success.
- Few students who are academically deficient and fail to enroll in remedial education are academically successful. (p. 50)

The Developmental Student

Students today are more diverse and involved in more non-academic pursuits than students were when developmental education began over 30 years ago. "We know that many community college students confront work and family challenges that complicate their education" (Bailey, et al, 2005, p. 10). Additionally, Bailey et al, (2005) added that, "community college students face severe obstruction to their academic achievements in college, such as family and work responsibilities and deficient academic preparation. Indeed, it is precisely students such as these, who may not have access to baccalaureate institutions, whom community colleges seek to serve" (p. 14).

Today's developmental education students come from all races, genders, socioeconomic statuses, and ages. Robert McCabe's (2000) research found:

54% of remedial education students are under 24 years of age, 24% are between the ages of 25 and 34, and 17% are over 35 years of age. Female enrollment slightly exceeds male enrollment [see figure 1]. 60% are white non-Hispanic, 23 % are African American, and 12% are Hispanic. 54% have an annual family income of less than \$20,000. (Bailey, 2005, p. 5)

[pic]

Figure 1. Enrollment by Gender, Source: (AACC, 2010b)

Today, developmental education students juggle the challenges of higher education, employment, family issues, and families of their own. Developmental education students brave the obstacles within their homes, their professions, and the hurdle of acquiring the necessary skills to advance to college level courses, meaning that in the classroom they will need more consideration. Courses offered to developmental education students should fit their social and academic needs as well. As educators we should provide and create an environment conducive to success.

Engaging and Retaining the Developmental Education Student
Engagement. Student engagement within community colleges can be effective for developmental education students as well as non-developmental students enrolled in college for the first time. The college experience is heightened by the connection students feel to the institution.

The first days and weeks of the college experience are foundational:

expectations meet campus realities, attitudes fostering or hindering academic success are reinforced or newly created, and choices are made about whether and how to engage in the college experience.

Students are more open to change when they first arrive on campus, yet most institutions squander this fleeting opportunity to truly engage beginning students. (Schuetz & Barr, 2008, p. 110)

Schuetz and Barr (2008) shared the following regarding engagement of underprepared students:

Underprepared students have been a significant presence in community colleges for decades. The growing size of this student population and the urgent reality of workforce accountability and other demands that did not exist forty years ago are pushing colleges to find more effective ways to support success for such students. (p. 113)

Retention of Developmental Education Students. Retention of developmental education students is vital to the success of the student and the college that they attend. Community colleges, like glue, have to pull two entities together. We have to create ways to draw on the things learned or not learned while the student was in the K-12 system.

Developmental education, although a hurdle for some, can be the answer to the problem of remediation. "There are students taking these courses three, four, five times before they can pass them, and many who drop out, give up before they do," says Barbara S. Bonham, consultant to colleges on remedial education (Blum, 2007, p. 2). Initiatives such as Achieving the Dream (AtD) diligently attempt to increase degree completion and transfer rates for students.

Retention of developmental education students, minority students, and the like are the key interests of AtD. For a variety of reasons, developmental students have low completion rates.

Achieving the Dream colleges have also found that students who fail to complete their first developmental education courses usually do not return the following semester; nor do they complete their other requirements for continuing in college. Their frustration with their lack of progress and the financial burden of having to retake courses contribute to low rates of retention and completion. (Biswas, 2007, p.

Departmental Practices: Hiring Faculty and Maintaining Departments

Developmental education is charged with the challenge of hiring appropriate staff to teach their students. "In practice, however, discipline-area instructors may decline developmental teaching assignments, and the instruction of remedial courses may be left to part-time, adjunct faculty who may not also be teaching college-level courses" (CCRC, 2002, p. 2).

More recently, colleges have hired part-time instructors or adjuncts to teach over half of their courses. The reason for this is that part-time faculty save the college money whereas hiring full-time faculty to teach those classes would cost the college more money. Some colleges and universities depend on part-time instructors as a source of low-cost labor but also recognize that they provide a valuable service because many of them have advanced degrees and life experiences that can enhance the institutions' offerings (Eney & Davidson, 2006).

"Considering the historical background of the use of part-time faculty in developmental education, it is essential to begin to make changes in the way colleges and universities select part-time instructors and how they treat them once they are hired" (Eney & Davidson, 2006, p. 3). If a college depends heavily on adjunct faculty they should make sure they have and can retain the best part-time instructors. Eney and Davidson also made the following suggestions regarding part-time faculty:

- Employ individuals with appropriate credentials, personalities, and beliefs.
- Provide adequate compensation.
- Provide part-time instructors with necessary services.
- Involve part-time instructors in institutional processes.
- Establish practical professional development activities and resources.
- Establish a faculty-to-faculty mentoring program for new hires.
- Develop a goal-setting and evaluation plan.

Developmental students require lectures from instructors that can contribute more to them in the classroom than life experiences. They require academically experienced, patient full time instructors. Despite the financial costs, 2-year institutions should invest in full time faculty to teach their developmental students especially if their classrooms are

larger due to soaring enrollments.

Developmental courses provide students with the academic enrichment that they lack. "Developmental courses are resource-intensive. They have to be kept small, since these students need personal attention" (Dad, 2009, p. 1). To fully take advantage of the opportunity for remediation in a particular subject developmental education courses should limit their class sizes. Students that place in developmental courses may be reluctant to speak up or thrive in large classrooms. Perhaps keeping developmental education classrooms small will provide students with the opportunities to develop the skills needed to advance to academic courses.

The Community College Research Center (2002) agrees with revamping classroom strategies to better suit the needs of their students in the classroom. They stated that

Since the main purpose of remedial education is to prepare students for college level academic demands, the skills and content taught in developmental classrooms should be related to those that students would later encounter in their subject matter classrooms. (p. 1)

McCabe (2000) notes majority of institutions fall short to utilizing existing studies concerning developmental education. "In recent years, some exciting and effective remedial programs have been developed.

"Nevertheless, the information concerning effective practices has been largely ignored" (p. 44). Two-year institutions would benefit from utilizing any previous research on developmental education to strengthen their programs.

Centralized departments. Centralized departments may disentangle the issues that arise from the discussion regarding the type of subject matter and content that is taught in the classroom. A centralized department has the potential to minimize the number of adjuncts used while properly training the ones that are being utilized. Ms. Anne Arboreli, Dean of Developmental Education at Lone Star College CyFair (Texas), shared that her department is centralized to only manage the needs of developmental students. As the Dean, the department is committed to hiring instructors "only focused in the developmental needs of their students" (personal communication, March 8, 2010). She also noted the key advantage for a centralized department is the one-on-one training that they can provide

their instructors which results in an increased quality of teaching for the students. Administrators that revamp their departments to include centralized departments will provide developmental students with the most qualified instructors with specialized training.

The Community College Research Center (2002) made the following suggestions regarding centralized developmental education departments:

1. Developmental curricula should be aligned with content and skills found in college-level courses.
2. Individualized attention and supplementary tutoring are important sources of support for academically under-prepared students. Colleges that mainstream developmental education should ensure that appropriate support services are available. This may require setting up the early-warning system.
3. Professional development, with appropriate incentives for participation, would help improve teaching ability and motivation in centralized developmental education.
4. Allow students to participate in college activities that are related to their majors and professions to which they aspire.
5. Efforts should be made by academic department and college administrators to integrate developmental education with the rest of the college program. (p. 3)

McCabe (2000) documented the priority community colleges should make towards developmental education:

Institutional commitment to underprepared students is of greatest importance. Successful remediation occurs in direct proportion to priority given to the program by the college. Most importantly is caring staff who believe in the student in the importance of their work. Presidential leadership, in word and deed, is critical to success. (p. 49)

Organizational Membership

Community colleges across the nation are the leading catalyst for educational access, student development, and success. Colleges that maintain a strong network of resources and best practices can provide their students with leading research to fit their student success needs.

Colleges that strive to improve their developmental education programs

would benefit from partnering through affiliation and membership in organizations such as Achieving the Dream (AtD), National Institute of Staff and Organizational Development (NISOD), Community College Survey of Student Engagement (CCSSE), Entering Student Success Institute (ESSI) and the Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE).

Achieving the dream (AtD). Achieving the Dream: Community Colleges Count (AtD) is a national initiative to help more community college students succeed (earn degrees, earn certificates, or transfer to other institutions to continue their studies). The initiative is particularly concerned about student groups that have faced the most significant barriers to success, including low-income students and students of color.

Achieving the Dream focuses colleges and others on understanding and making better use of data. It acts on multiple fronts, including efforts at community colleges, research, public engagement, and public policy.

Achieving the Dream is funded by the Lumina Foundation for Education and 18 other partner foundations (Biswas, September 2007, p. ii). Community colleges can benefit by participating in this initiative as it focuses on students facing barriers that may have a significant impact on their success as students at their institution.

National institute of staff and organizational development (NISOD).

The National Institute of Staff and Organizational Development (NISOD) is an organization founded to support the professional and academic needs of administrators, faculty and staff in higher education. Founded by Drs. John and Suanne Roueche, the organization set out to be the change agent in community college leadership.

NISOD provides academic and research based best practices in leadership across the country and internationally. The membership-based association provides an annual conference in Austin, Texas, frequent abstracts filled with student success testimonies, webinars, and educational updates through social media. NISOD, supported by the educational practice from the nationally recognized Community College Leadership Program at The University of Texas at Austin, is a vehicle for administrative leadership in higher education. Through membership colleges can profit from innovative techniques and share their own best practices and successful outcomes in developmental education nationally and

internationally.

Community college survey of student engagement(CCSSE). The Community College Survey of Student Engagement (CCSSE) was founded in 2001 at The University of Texas at Austin as a project for the Community College Leadership Doctoral Program and provides evaluation and enhancement of student learning, retention, and performance.

To respond effectively to these challenges, community and technical colleges need assessment tools appropriate to their unique missions and the characteristics of their diverse student populations. The Community College Survey of Student Engagement (CCSSE) is meeting that need. (CCSSE, 2010a)

Colleges that submit their institutions to the assessment process and survey provided by this organization will benefit by accurate assessment of the needs of the students and possible organizational quandaries that may need to be modified.

CCSSE produced a survey instrument called The Community College Student Report, which provides student engagement data, a gauge at learning by students and a better understanding of organizational interaction with students. The Community College Student Report is a versatile, research-based tool appropriate for multiple uses. This tool can be used as the following:

1. Benchmarking instrument — establishing national norms on educational practice and performance by community and technical colleges.
2. Diagnostic tool — identifying areas in which a college can enhance students' educational experiences.
3. Monitoring device — documenting and improving institutional effectiveness over time (CCSSE, 2010b).

Entering student success institute (ESSI). The Center for Community College Student Engagement with collaboration from Achieving the Dream, and the Community College Leadership Program will host the fourth institute of ESSI in New Mexico in 2011(ESSI, 2010a). The institute can train community college administrative staff to learn about student record, related statistical review, or goals for achievement. For full effectiveness of the institute, ESSI recommends the following persons attend:

- President
- Chief Academic Officer
- Chief Student Services Officer
- Faculty Leader
- Developmental Education Faculty Leader
- First Year Experience/Entering Student Experience Leader
- Director of Institutional Research
- Achieving the Dream Core Team or Data Team Leader, if applicable (ESSI, 2010b).

Survey of entering student engagement (SENSE). The Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE) helps community and technical colleges focus on the “front door” of the college experience (SENSE, 2010). SENSE assembles statistical facts to support the student success needs of entering students into the college and aims at improving their experiences. Colleges that align themselves with this organization obtain key input on the experiences of their students when they begin college, their engagement levels while they are enrolled there.

Overall, retaining and engaging developmental education students will take a team effort. Two-year institutions can no longer afford to not budget annually for organizational memberships. Organizational memberships benefit everyone. The community college, its faculty and staff, and sharing of best practices will be key areas of focus to develop strong developmental education programs locally, nationally and internationally.

Chapter Three: Methodology and Procedures

Introduction

Community colleges are the gateway to higher education for many students who would otherwise have limited access to college (Bailey et al., 2005). Transitioning students through the essential levels of developmental education courses to college level courses has become an issue.

Administering placement exams to incoming college students assist community colleges determine if developmental courses are needed. Students can be placed in developmental mathematics, developmental reading, or developmental writing courses.

It is imperative that community colleges create better methods to retain incoming students who place into developmental courses. Colleges

that identify and measure the levels of engagement of their students can better preserve those students. If students are not retained they are more likely to delay college enrollment, attend college part-time, or have gaps in college enrollment.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this chapter is to use quantitative techniques to identify levels of engagement of developmental students versus non-developmental students within 2-year institutions. The researcher also wants to identify institutional strategies or academic support initiatives that assist students enrolled in developmental education courses within community colleges. In addition, the researcher will examine the educational experiences of developmental students in 2-year institutions. The Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE) was the source of data for this study. This chapter describes the research methodology that was used to carry out this study. The chapter includes the purpose of the study, research questions, methodology, research design, description of sample, procedures and data collection, instrument development, instrument validity, procedure for obtaining informed consent for agenda, SENSE research protocol, data analysis, and summary.

Research Design

Results from this quantitative study will add knowledge to the field of developmental education by preparing administrators and faculty with research to support their efforts to educate students within their college. For the quantitative analysis, sample surveys were utilized from the Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE), which was conducted during the fall 2009 semester at a suburban community college system in Texas. For purposes of this study, the following two questions were addressed:

Research Questions

1. Are there significant differences in the engagement levels among first year developmental education students versus first year non-developmental college students within 2-year institutions?
2. What institutional practices or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in 2-year institutions?

Methodology

Survey research was used to collect and identify the strategies that

assisted students persist through developmental education courses.

The purpose of this chapter is to use quantitative techniques to identify strategies that assist students enrolled in developmental education courses. "A quantitative approach is one in which the investigator primarily used postpositivist claims for developing knowledge, employs strategies of inquiry such as experiments and surveys, and collects data on predetermined instruments that yield statistical data" (Creswell, 2003, p. 18). This used a research design to determine if there are significant differences in the engagement levels of entering community college students enrolled in developmental courses. Sydenstricker (2007) notes that statistical tests (regressions, t-tests, chi square, etc) are "strong in internal validity and can parallel other non-equivalent designs in terms of validity threats, interpretation of results might be difficult" (para. 17). With that in mind, the use of t-tests will enable the researcher to analyze the significant experiences of students enrolled in developmental courses versus students not enrolled in developmental education courses.

The data collected is from the Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE). The primary independent variable, students, is categorical. The dependent variable, student engagement, is continuous. The researcher studied variables that included the level of engagement, and passing or failing developmental courses.

Description of the sample. The Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE) was administered to students at 120 member community colleges during the fourth and fifth week of the fall 2009 semester. This survey yielded over 50,327 surveys from entering students. Fall 2009 was the first national administration of the survey. The survey was administered in classes randomly selected from the population of all first college-level English, first college-level math, and developmental education courses (excluding ESL courses). Colleges chose to include zero, one, or two of the four 2009 special-focus modules in their surveys. The 2009 special-focus modules were commitment and support, Engagement through Technology, Financial Assistance, and Student success Courses. In all, 75 colleges administered special-focus modules (SENSE, 2010).

SENSE sampling procedures are at the classroom level. Full-time

students are more likely to be sampled. SENSE results are weighted based on the most recent publically available IPEDS data (Sense, 2010).

Procedures and data collection. The 2009 Survey of Entering Student Engagement was collected through the use of paper surveys administered in-class during the 4th and 5th weeks of the fall academic term by survey administrators. Students respond to the survey in class, and member colleges receive survey reports including data and analysis they can use to improve their programs and services for entering students (SENSE, 2010). Instrument development. Researchers from The Community College Survey of Student Engagement (CCSSE) produced the SENSE instrument. Consultations with national experts in the field community and technical colleges assisted with creation of this instrument (SENSE, 2010). The instrument contains 38 questions regarding barriers that some entering college students may face. There is particular focus on questions regarding student success, development courses, and entering student engagement concerns.

Instrument validity. The SENSE instrument has been previously validated through CCSSE's large-scale validation research study (McClenney & Marti, 2006) and by the National Survey of Student Engagement (NSSE) administered to 4-year colleges and universities in the United States (Kuh, 2003). Questions on the survey associate with issues revealed in retention literature that is significant when assessing persistence, engagement, and retention. These questions assessed areas such as:

1. Student effort
2. Student-faculty interaction
3. Services – support for learners
4. Active and collaborative learning (SENSE, 2010).

Procedure for Obtaining Informed Consent for SENSE

Presidents from the colleges participating in the SENSE survey signed membership and agreement forms when they registered their college online. Students in randomly selected classes were afforded with an oral description of the study given by the survey administrator. Students were assured that participation was voluntary, were provided with explanations regarding student identification numbers, and any additional questions they had were addressed (SENSE, 2010).

SENSE research protocol. Registration for colleges to participate in the SENSE survey occurred online. The SENSE survey requires that signatures of the colleges President or CEO and completion of the Institutional Membership and Agreement Form. Each college was sent a procedure guide to their delegated contact person. Each college submitted an inventory of every credit course that met the sampling limitation. Analysts for SENSE completed random sampling, survey packets and all necessary materials that were mailed directly to the college contact. With approval of the random sample consent from the instructor to administer the SENSE survey during class is obtained. The survey time lasts between 30 and 45 minutes. The survey administrator then thoroughly reads the script and notifies all partakers that their participation is voluntary. Once each survey is completed, the administrator collected the surveys, placed them in the envelope provided by SENSE and mailed to SENSE for analysis (SENSE, 2010).

Data Analysis

This study used an independent sample t-test to analyze the responses of students currently enrolled in developmental education courses versus students enrolled in non-developmental courses. Sample t-test assisted the researcher to answer questions one and two. The following questions will answer question two regarding institutional practices and academic support initiatives from the 2009 SENSE Survey:

Question 11

The following statements are about this college's orientation for new students (mark all that apply).

- I took part in an online orientation prior to the beginning of classes.
- I attended an on-campus orientation prior to the beginning of classes.
- I enrolled in an orientation course as part of my course schedule during my first semester/quarter at this college.
- I was not aware of a college orientation.
- I was unable to participate in orientation due to scheduling or other issues.

Question 12

This set of items asks you about your earliest experiences at this college.

To respond, please think about your experiences from the time of your decision to attend this college through the end of the first three weeks of your first semester/quarter (yes or no).

- Before I could register for classes I was required to take a placement exam (COMPASS, ASSET, ACCUPLACER, SAT, ACT, etc.) to assess my skills in reading, writing and/ or math.
- I was exempt from taking a placement test from this college.

Question 14

This college required me to enroll in classes indicated by my placement test during my first semester/quarter (yes or no).

Question 20

This section asks three questions about a variety of college services. Answer three questions for each service indicating (1) whether you knew about it, (2) how often you used it, and (3) how satisfied you were. To respond, please think about your experiences from the time of your decision to attend this college through the end of the first three weeks of your first semester/quarter.

- Academic advising/planning
- Career counseling
- Job placement assistance
- Face to face tutoring
- Online tutoring
- Writing, math, or other skill lab
- Financial assistance lab
- Computer lab
- Student organizations
- Transfer credit assistance
- Services to students with disabilities

Question 22

Thinking about your experiences from the time of your decision to attend this college through the end of the first three weeks of your first semester what has been your MAIN source of academic advising (help with academic goal-setting, planning, course recommendations, graduation requirements, etc.)? (Mark only one)

- Friends, family, or other students

- Computerized degree advisor system
- Instructors
- College staff (not instructors)
- College Web site
- Other college materials

Question 23

Was a specific person assigned to you so you could see him/her each time you needed information or assistance? (yes or no) (SENSE, 2010)

In this study, the researcher was interested in determining the levels of engagement and educational experiences of first year college students within 2-year institutions. The researcher used SPSS to analyze the data.

Chapter Summary

Results from the study of the levels of engagement and all academic support programs for first year college students will benefit 2-year colleges around the world. Administrators within 2-year institutions will have data to support the student success programs offered at their institutions. The quantitative method approach was suitable for this study because the available data was the result of a sound survey instrument and provided a good framework to answer each research question.

Chapter Four: Data Analysis and Findings

Introduction

The purpose of this study was to investigate the dissimilarities in engagement levels between developmental students and non-developmental students by employing the Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE). The Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE) was administered to students at 120 member community colleges during the fourth and fifth week of the fall 2009 semester. This survey yielded over 50,327 surveys from entering students. Fall 2009 was the first national administration of the survey. The survey was administered in classes randomly selected from the population of all first college-level English, first college-level math, and developmental education courses (excluding ESL courses). In all, 75 colleges administered special-focus modules (SENSE, 2010). For the purpose of this study survey results from Lone Star College System in Houston, Texas were analyzed.

The 2009 Survey of Entering Student Engagement was collected through the use of paper surveys administered in-class during the fourth and fifth weeks of the fall academic term by survey administrators. Students respond to the survey in class, and member colleges receive survey reports including data and analysis they can use to improve their programs and services for entering students (SENSE, 2010) at their college.

SENSE identifies six benchmarks of valuable procedures with entering students. Early Connections identifies a specific person the entering student connects with as a source of support at the college. This connection can prove vital to the persistence of the student. High Expectations and Aspirations notes nearly all students arrive at their community colleges intending to succeed and believing they have the motivation to do so. When entering students perceive clear, high expectations from college staff and faculty, they are more likely to understand what it takes to be successful and adopt behaviors that lead to achievement. Clear Academic Plan and Pathway says that students are more likely to persevere when they are advised on the courses to take and are assisted with their academic goals and plans to achieve them. Effective Track to College Readiness focuses on improvements in student success and academic procedures administratively. Engaged Learning fosters strong instructional approaches that engage students academically. Academic and Social Support Network is geared toward providing the student information on college services and social support to lead to student success. This practice strives to be intentional (SENSE, 2010).

Chapter four describes in detail the statistical methods described in chapter three and the findings from the statistical analysis for the two research questions. These findings will assist in framing the conclusions and recommendations for chapter five.

Analysis

As framework for the analysis of first time in college students the researcher used question six, "How many semesters/quarters have you been enrolled at this college." If the student answered A, this is my first semester/quarter, then the student is considered a first time in college student. An additional question used to screen developmental versus non-developmental students was question 17 on the SENSE survey. If the student

responded to any of the items (developmental reading, writing, or math) that student was determined to be a developmental student. For the purposes of this research 2,345 students were analyzed. Any statistical significances have been labeled, divided by benchmark, and cross-campus compared by college.

Research question #1. Are there significant differences in the engagement levels among first year developmental education students versus first year non-developmental college students within 2-year institutions?

To answer question number one the independent variables, developmental students versus non-developmental students were identified using the screener questions listed above. SPSS was used to divide all students by college. College one equals Lone Star College Cyfair, college two equals Lone Star College Kingwood, college three equals Lone Star College Montgomery, college four equals Lone Star College North Harris, and college five equals Lone Star College Tomball. Frequency distributions were run for all students who identified themselves as developmental or non-developmental. Independent sample t-tests were run for 2,231 students who identified themselves as developmental.

Engagement. To determine significant differences between developmental and non-developmental students independent sample t-tests were run for engagement variables under the SENSE benchmarks Early Connections, High Expectations and Aspirations, Clear Academic Plan and Pathway, Effective Track to College Readiness and Engaged Learning. From SPSS main menu choose ANALYZE, COMPARE MEANS, and INDEPENDENT SAMPLES T-TEST. For dependent variables all variables listed in the SENSE Codebook (see Appendix B) were used.

The final step was to determine if there was an actual difference that existed between the two independent variables. The findings were used to perform a cross-campus comparison for deeper analysis of the independent variables within the 2-year college system that comprises of five colleges.

Research question #2. What institutional practices or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in two-year institutions?

To determine if any institutional practices or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in 2-year

institutions the researcher focused on the student answers to questions that asked specifically regarding practices performed within the two year institution. The researcher used SPSS software and analyzed the data using independent samples t-test. As dependent variables the following variables were used:

- Regclass When did you register for your courses for your first semester/quarter at this college?
- Onlorien I took part in an online orientation program prior to the beginning of classes.
- Oncorien I attended an on-campus orientation program prior to the beginning of classes.
- Csorien I enrolled in an orientation course as part of my course schedule during my first semester/quarter at this college.
- Reqptest Before I could register for classes I was required to take a placement test (COMPASS, ASSET, ACCUPLACER, SAT, ACT, etc.) to assess my skills in reading, writing, and/or math.
- Reqclass This college required me to enroll in classes indicated by my placement test scores during my first semester/quarter.
- Aaselmaj An advisor helped me to select a course of study, program, or major.
- Acadgoal An advisor helped me to set academic goals and to create a plan for achieving them.
- Crsadv An advisor helped me identify the courses I needed to take during my first semester/quarter.
- Osgomm A college staff member talked with me about my commitments outside of school (work, children, dependents, etc.) to help me figure out the number of courses to take.
- Actintro All instructors had activities to introduce students to one another.
- Resource All instructors clearly explained academic and student support services available at this college.
- Gradedpol All instructors clearly explained course grading policies.
- Syllabi Instructors clearly explained course syllabi (syllabuses).
- Cstafnam At least one college staff member (other than an instructor) learned my name.

- Ostudnam At least one other student whom I did not previously know learned my name.
- Facnam At least one instructor learned my name.
- Stunam I learned the name of at least one other student in most of my classes.
- Supinstr Participate in supplemental instruction (extra class sessions with an instructor tutor, or experienced student).
- Facassn Discuss an assignment or grade with an instructor.
- Feedback Receive prompt written or oral feedback from instructors on your performance.
- Acadplng Academic advising/planning
- AcadpuseFrequency: Academic advising/planning
- CareerCareer Counseling
- Jobplace Job placement assistance
- Fftutor Face-to-face tutoring
- Oltutor Online tutoring
- Oltsat Satisfaction: Online tutoring

Tables

Table 1.

LSC Cyfair Statistics Early Connection

|Group Statistics |

||

||t|Df|Sig|Mean|

|||(2-tailed)|Diff`|

|||d)||

|Early Connections|1.57|471|.11|3.49|

|(benchmark)|||||

|Felt welcomed 1st|.78|483|.43|.06|

|visit|||||

|College gave info|-.51|481|.60|-.06|

|about financial|||||

|assistance|||||

|Staff helped|-.28|479|.77|-.03|

|determine|||||

|qualifications for|||||

|financial aid | | | | |

|Staff learned my |1.11 |482 |.26 |.15 |

|name | | | | |

|Assigned specific |-2. |473 |.00* |-.09 |

|person | | | | |

At Lone Star College Cyfair non-developmental students are more likely to be assigned a specific person.

Table 3.

LSC Kingwood Statistics Early Connections

|Group Statistics |

| |

| |t |Df |Sig |Mean |

| | | |(2-tailed) |Diff` |

| | | |d) | |

|Early Connections |2.81 |497 |.00* |7.27 |

|Felt welcomed 1st |.23 |510 |.81 |.02 |

|visit | | | | |

|College gave |1.67 |507 |.09 |.21 |

|information about | | | | |

|financial | | | | |

|assistance | | | | |

|Staff helped |2.11 |502 |.03* |.26 |

|determine | | | | |

|qualifications for| | | | |

|financial aid | | | | |

|Staff learned my |.81 |510 |.41 |.11 |

|name | | | | |

|Assigned specific |-4.14 |496 |.00* |-.19 |

|person | | | | |

At Lone Star College Kingwood developmental students are more likely to report Early Connections and staff helped determine qualifications for financial aid. Non-developmental students are more likely to be assigned a specific person.

Table 5.

LSC Montgomery Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics				
	T	Df	Sig	Mean
			(2-tailed)	Diff.
		d		
Early Connections	1.57	633	.11	3.08
Welcomed 1st Visit	1.75	659	.08	1.12
College gave information about financial assistance	1.25	657	.21	1.12
Staff helped determine qualifications for financial aid	.37	658	.70	.03
Staff learned my name	1.21	658	.22	-.13
Assigned specific person	-.46	642	.64	-.01

At Lone Star College Montgomery there was no significance in the Early Connections benchmark.

Table 7.

LSC North Harris Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics				
	T	Df	Sig	Mean
			(2-tailed)	Diff.
		d		
Early Connections	1.74	649	.08	4.57
Welcomed 1st Visit	.04	665	.96	1.00
College gave information about financial assistance	1.47	660	.14	1.18
Staff helped	1.23	659	.21	1.15

determine				
qualifications for				
financial aid				
Staff learned my	-.73	663	.46	-.10
name				
Assigned specific	-1.35	640	.17	-.06
person				

At Lone Star College North Harris there was no significance in the Early Connections benchmark.

Table 9.

LSC Tomball Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics	t	Df	Sig	Mean	(2-tailed)	Diff`	d
Early Connections	3.80	578	.00*	8.72			
Welcomed 1st Visit	2.97	582	.00*	.21			
College gave information about financial assistance	.60	582	.54	.06			
Staff helped determine qualifications for financial aid	.97	576	.33	.10			
Staff learned my name	2.15	583	.03*	.26			
Assigned specific person	-3.40	561	.00*	-.11			

At Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report Early Connections, the very first time they came to this college they felt welcome and at least one college staff member (other than an instructor) learned their name. Non-developmental students are more likely to report they were assigned a specific person than developmental students.

Table 11.

LSC Cyfair Statistics High Expectations and Aspirations

Group Statistics				
	t	Df	Sig.	Mean
			(2-tailed)	Diff.
				d
High Expectations	1.32	471	.18	3.18
and Aspirations				
Instructors want	1.78	482	.07	.12
me to succeed				
Motivation for	2.20	482	.02*	.15
success				
Prepared	1.56	482	.11	.12
academically to				
succeed				
Turn in	2.07	483	.03*	.12
assignments late				
Not turn in an	.77	480	.44	.05
assignment				
Come to class	-3.30	484	.00*	-.25
incomplete				
readings and				
assignments				
	-.16	485	.87	-.01
Skip class				

At Lone Star College Cyfair developmental students are more likely to report having the motivation to do what it takes to succeed in college, turn in assignments late, and they come to class without completing readings or assignments.

Table 13.

LSC Kingwood Statistics High Expectations and Aspirations

Group Statistics				
	t	Df	Sig.	Mean

	t	Df	Sig	Mean
High Expectations and Aspirations	-.89	497	.37	-2.02
Instructors want me to succeed	.72	510	.47	.05
Motivation for success	.41	508	.67	.03
Prepared academically to succeed	-.90	510	.36	-.07
Turn in assignments late	3.26	510	.00*	.19
Not turn in an assignment	1.92	508	.05	.12
Come to class incomplete readings and assignments	-1.75	510	.07	-.13
Skip class	1.45	510	.14	.09

At Lone Star College Kingwood developmental students are more likely to report that they turn in assignments late.

Table 15.

LSC Montgomery High Expectations and Aspirations

	t	Df	Sig	Mean
High Expectations and Aspirations	-.05	633	.96	-.11
Instructors want me to succeed	1.36	657	.17	.08
Motivation for success	.87	657	.38	.05
Prepared academically to succeed	-.74	655	.45	-.04
Turn in assignments late	2.13	660	.03*	.12
Not turn in an assignment	.66	654	.50	.03
Come to class incomplete readings and assignments	-1.75	657	.07	-.12
Skip class	-.77	660	.43	-.04

At Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students are more likely to report that they turn in assignments late.

Table 17.

LSC North Harris High Expectations and Aspirations

Group Statistics					
	t	Df	Sig.	Mean	
			(2-tailed)	Diff.	
				d	
High Expectations	1.93	578	.05	3.93	
and Aspirations					
Instructors want	2.92	584	.00*	.18	
me to succeed					
Motivation for	.96	584	.33	.06	
success					
Prepared	-.95	579	.33	-.06	
academically to					
succeed					
Turn in	1.96	586	.05	.09	
assignments late					
Not turn in an	-.11	584	.91	-.06	
assignment					
Come to class	-3.48	586	.00*	-2.50	
incomplete					
readings and					
assignments					
Skip class	-2.07	581	.03*	-.11	

At Lone Star College North Harris developmental students are more likely to report their instructors want them to succeed. Non-developmental students are more likely to report they come to class with incomplete readings/assignments and they skip class.

Table 19.

LSC Tomball Statistics High Expectations and Aspirations

Group Statistics

	t	Df	Sig	Mean
			(2-tailed)	Diff
				d
High Expectations and Aspirations	1.93	578	.05	3.93
Instructors want me to succeed	2.92	584	.00*	.18
Motivation for success	.96	584	.33	.06
Prepared academically to succeed	-.95	579	.33	-.06
Turn in assignments late	1.96	586	.05	.097
Not turn in an assignment	-.11	584	.91	-.06
Come to class incomplete readings and assignments	-3.48	586	.00*	-.25
Skip class	-2.07	581	.03*	-.11

At Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report their instructors wanted to see them succeed. Non-developmental students are more likely to report they come to class with incomplete readings/assignments and skip class.

Table 21.

LSC Cyfair Statistics Academic Plan

Group	Statistics
Developmental	Student
N	Mean
Std. Deviation	Std. Error
328	41.96
25.68	1.41
140	37.51
26.19	2.21
338	3.45
1.10	.06

	NonDev	139	3.33	1.03	.08	
	Advisor helped	Developmental	340	3.28	1.25	.06
	select course					
	of					
	study/prg/major					
	NonDev	142	3.20	1.21	.10	
	Advisor helped	Developmental	337	2.82	1.17	.06
	set acad goals					
	and plan to					
	achieve					
	NonDev	141	2.65	1.16	.09	
	Advisor helped	Developmental	339	3.55	1.22	.06
	identify					
	courses needed					
	first semester					
	NonDev	142	3.20	1.24	.10	
	Staff discussed	Developmental	340	2.43	1.12	.06
	commitments					
	outside of					
	school					
	NonDev	142	2.39	1.03	.08	

Table 22.

LSC Cyfair Independent Samples Academic Plan

	Independent Samples Test	Development vs.			
	Non-Developmental				
	t	Df	Sig	Mean	
		(2-tailed)	Diff`		
		d)			
	Academic Plan	1.70	466	.08	4.54
	Met with advisor at	1.08	475	.27	.11
	convenient times				
	Advisor helped	.66	480	.50	.082
	select course of				
	study/prg/major				
	Advisor helped set	1.52	476	.12	.18

acad goals and plan				
to achieve				
Advisor helped	2.80	479	.00*	.34
identify courses				
needed first				
semester				
Staff discussed	.31	480	.75	.03
commitments outside				
of school				

At Lone Star College Cyfair developmental students are more likely to report an advisor helped identify the courses needed the first semester.

Table 23.

LSC Kingwood Statistics Academic Plan

Group	Statistics		
Developmental	Non-Developmental		
N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
379	52.31	24.21	1.24
118	49.03	22.47	2.06
390	3.58	1.06	.054
118	3.63	1.06	.098
390	3.75	1.09	.055
119	3.66	1.07	.099
389	3.22	1.13	.058
120	3.09	1.09	.100
391	3.99	1.03	.053

identify	
courses needed	
first semester	
NonDev	120 3.76 1.06 .097
Staff discussed	Developmental 387 2.77 1.16 .059
commitments	
outside of	
school	
NonDev	120 2.67 1.11 .101

Table 24.

LSC Kingwood Independent Samples Academic Plan

|Independent Samples Test Development vs. |

|Non-Developmental |

|t |Df |Sig |Mean |

|| |(2-tailed) |Diff` |

|| |d) ||

|Academic Plan |1.30 |495 |.19 |3.27 |

|Met with advisor at|-.42 |506 |.67 |-.048 |

|convenient times ||||||

|Advisor helped |.84 |507 |.40 |.09 |

|select course of ||||||

|study/prg/major ||||||

|Advisor helped set |1.05 |507 |.29 |.12 |

|academic goals and ||||||

|plan to achieve ||||||

|Advisor helped |2.10 |509 |.03* |.22 |

|identify courses ||||||

|needed first ||||||

|semester ||||||

|Staff discussed |.85 |505 |.39 |.10 |

|commitments outside| |||||

|of school ||||||

At Lone Star College Kingwood developmental students are more likely to report an advisor helped identify the courses needed the first semester.

Table 25.

LSC Montgomery Statistics Academic Plan

|Group Statistics |

| |Developmental |N |Mean |Std. |Std. |

| |Student | | |Deviation|Error |

| | | | |Mean |

|Academic Plan |Developmental |2102 |50.44 |24.97 |.54 |

| |NonDev |717 |47.06 |24.65 |.92 |

|Met with |Developmental |2159 |3.69 |1.01 |.02 |

|advisor at | | | | | |

|convenient | | | | | |

|times | | | | | |

| |NonDev |724 |3.66 |.99 |.03 |

|Advisor helped |Developmental |2166 |3.61 |1.17 |.02 |

|select course | | | | | |

|of | | | | | |

|study/prg/major| | | | | |

| |NonDev |728 |3.53 |1.18 |.04 |

|Advisor helped |Developmental |2160 |3.09 |1.16 |.02 |

|set acad goals | | | | | |

|and plan to | | | | | |

|achieve | | | | | |

| |NonDev |730 |2.96 |1.15 |.04 |

|Advisor helped |Developmental |2166 |3.87 |1.06 |.02 |

|identify | | | | | |

|courses needed | | | | | |

|first semester | | | | | |

| |NonDev |731 |3.64 |1.14 |.04 |

|Staff discussed|Developmental |2164 |2.72 |1.21 |.02 |

|commitments | | | | | |

|outside of | | | | | |

|school | | | | | |

| |NonDev |729 |2.64 |1.12 |.04 |

Table 26.

LSC Montgomery Independent Samples Academic Plan

|Independent Samples Test Development vs. |

Non-Developmental	t	Df	Sig	Mean	(2-tailed)	Diff	d
Academic Plan	3.13	2817	.00*	3.37			
Met with advisor at convenient times	.65	2881	.51	.02			
Advisor helped select course of study/prg/major	1.60	2892	.10	.08			
Advisor helped set acad goals and plan to achieve	2.78	2888	.00*	.13			
Advisor helped id courses needed first semester	4.99	2895	.00*	.23			
Staff discussed commitments outside of school	1.44	2891	.14	.07			

At Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students are more likely to report statistical significance in Academic Plan, an advisor helped set academic goals and plan to achieve them and an advisor helped identify courses needed the first semester.

Table 27.

North Harris Statistics Academic Plan

Group Statistics	Developmental	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Academic Plan	Developmental	523	55.37	23.78	1.04
	NonDev	124	56.27	23.08	2.07
Met with advisor at convenient times	Developmental	532	3.82	.94	.04

NonDev	126	3.84	.93	.08	
Advisor helped	Developmental	537	3.83	1.13	.04
select course					
of					
study/prg/major					
NonDev	126	3.96	1.09	.09	
Advisor helped	Developmental	536	3.22	1.20	.05
set acad goals					
and plan to					
achieve					
NonDev	126	3.34	1.26	.11	
Advisor helped	Developmental	538	4.09	.96	.04
id courses					
needed first					
semester					
NonDev	126	4.06	.96	.08	
Staff discussed	Developmental	537	2.89	1.31	.05
commitments					
outside of					
school					
NonDev	124	2.89	1.30	.11	

Table 28.

LSC North Harris Independent Samples Academic Plan

|Independent Samples Test Development vs. |

|Non-Developmental |

| |t |Df |Sig |Mean |

| | | |(2-tailed) |Diff` |

| | | |d) | |

|Academic Plan |-.38 |645 |.70 |-.90 |

|Met with advisor at |-.19 |656 |.84 |-.01 |

|convenient times | | | |

|Advisor helped select |-1.16 |661 |.24 |-.13 |

|course of | | | |

|study/prg/major | | | |

|Advisor helped set |-1.05 |660 |.31 |-.12 |

|academic goals and | | | | |

|plan to achieve | | | | |

|Advisor helped |.23 |662 |.81 |.02 |

|identify courses | | | | |

|needed first semester | | | | |

|Staff discussed |.00 |659 |.99 |.00 |

|commitments outside of| | | | |

|school | | | | |

At Lone Star College North Harris there was no significance in the Academic Plan benchmark for developmental or non-developmental students.

Table 29.

LSC Tomball Statistics Academic Plan

|Group Statistics |

| |Developmental |N |Mean |Std. |Std. |

| |Student | | |Deviation|Error |

| | | | |Mean |

|Academic Plan |Developmental |418 |51.30 |24.60 |1.20 |

| |NonDev |157 |46.84 |22.24 |1.77 |

|Met with |Developmental |426 |3.76 |.97 |.04 |

|advisor at | | | | |

|convenient | | | | |

|times | | | | |

| |NonDev |159 |3.81 |.910 |.072 |

|Advisor helped |Developmental |425 |3.64 |1.12 |.05 |

|select course | | | | |

|of | | | | |

|study/prg/major| | | | |

| |NonDev |158 |3.54 |1.16 |.09 |

|Advisor helped |Developmental |424 |3.18 |1.12 |.05 |

|set acad goals | | | | |

|and plan to | | | | |

|achieve | | | | |

| |NonDev |160 |2.84 |.99 |.07 |

|Advisor helped |Developmental |425 |3.87 |1.02 |.05 |

|identified | | | | |

courses needed	
first semester	
NonDev	160 3.59 1.11 .08
Staff discussed	Developmental 425 2.69 1.20 .05
commitments	
outside of	
school	
NonDev	160 2.56 1.05 .08

Table 30.

LSC Tomball Independent Samples Academic Plan

Independent Samples Test Development vs. |

Non-Developmental |

t	Df	Sig	Mean
		(2-tailed)	Diff`
			d)
Academic Plan	1.98 573 .04*	4.45	
Met with advisor at	-.52 583 .59	-.04	
convenient times			
Advisor helped	.98 581 .32 .10		
select course of			
study/prg/major			
Advisor helped set	3.30 582 .00*	.33	
academic goals and			
plan to achieve			
Advisor helped	2.86 583 .00*	.27	
identified courses			
needed first			
semester			
Staff discussed	1.28 583 .20 .13		
commitments outside			
of school			

At Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report they have an Academic Plan and an advisor helped set academic goals and a plan to achieve them. Non- developmental students are more likely to report an advisor helped identify courses needed the first semester.

Table 31.

LSC Cyfair Statistics Effective Track to College Readiness

|Group Statistics |

| |Developmental |N |Mean |Std. |Std. |

| |Student | | |Deviation|Error |

| | | | |Mean |

|Effective track|Developmental |330 |56.58 |19.43 |1.06 |

|to college | | | | |

|readiness | | | | |

| |NonDev |143 |34.41 |25.97 |2.17 |

|Before register|Developmental |343 |1.05 |.21 |.01 |

|required | | | | |

|placement test | | | | |

| |NonDev |142 |1.25 |.43 |.03 |

|I took a |Developmental |337 |1.04 |.19 |.01 |

|placement test | | | | |

| |NonDev |140 |1.14 |.35 |.03 |

|This college |Developmental |341 |1.09 |.288 |.016 |

|required me to | | | | |

|enroll in | | | | |

|classes | | | | |

|indicated by my| | | | |

|placement test | | | | |

|scores during | | | | |

|my 1st | | | | |

|semester. | | | | |

| |NonDev |141 |1.62 |.486 |.041 |

|Within class or|Developmental |341 |3.97 |.974 |.053 |

|another | | | | |

|experience at | | | | |

|college I | | | | |

|learned to | | | | |

|improve study | | | | |

|skills | | | | |

| |NonDev |143 |3.75 |.876 |.073 |

Within class or	Developmental	341	3.86	.931	.050
another					
experience I					
learned to					
understand my					
academic					
strengths					
/weakness					

	NonDev	143	3.64	.859	.072
Within class or	Developmental	341	3.63	1.036	.056
another					
experience I					
learned skills					
and strategies					
to improve test					
taking ability					
	NonDev	142	3.37	.978	.082

Table 32.
LSC Cyfair Independent Samples Effective Track to College Readiness

Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental					
	t	Df	Sig	Mean	
			(2-tailed)	Diff`	
				d)	
Effective track to	10.24	471	.00*	22.17	
college readiness					
Before register	-6.65	483	.00*	-.19	
required placement					
test					
Took placement test	-4.15	475	.00*	-.10	
This college	-14.90	480	.00*	-.53	
required me to					
enroll in classes					
indicated by my					
placement test					
scores during my					

1st semester.	
Within class or	2.32 482 .02* .21
another experience	
at this college	
learned to improve	
study skills	
Within class or	2.41 482 .01* .21
another experience	
at this college	
learned to	
understand my	
academic strengths	
/weakness	
Within class or	2.62 481 .00* .26
another experience	
at this college	
learned skills and	
strategies to	
improve test taking	
ability	

Lone Star College Cyfair developmental students are more likely to report Effective Track to College Readiness, within a class or another experience at this college they learned skills and strategies to improve study skills, within a class or another experience at this college they learned to understand their academic strengths and weaknesses, within a class or another experience at this college they learned skills to improve test taking ability. Non-developmental students are more likely to report before registering for classes they were required to take a placement test, took a placement test, and the college required them to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester.

Table 33.

LSC Kingwood Statistics Effective Track to College Readiness

Group Statistics	
Developmental	N Mean Std. Std.
Student	Deviation Error

				Mean		
Effective track	Developmental	379	55.13	19.37	.99	
to college						
readiness						
	NonDev	120	32.75	26.23	2.39	
Before register	Developmental	388	1.07	.26	.01	
required						
placement test						
	NonDev	120	1.23	.42	.03	
Took placement	Developmental	387	1.04	.19	.01	
test						
	NonDev	119	1.14	.35	.03	
This college	Developmental	389	1.07	.25	.01	
required me to						
enroll in						
classes						
indicated by my						
placement test						
scores during						
my 1st						
semester.						
	NonDev	118	1.67	.47	.04	
Within class or	Developmental	390	3.89	.92	.04	
another						
experience at						
college I						
learned to						
improve study						
skills						
	NonDev	122	3.66	.95	.08	
Within class or	Developmental	390	3.81	.93	.04	
another						
experience at						
the college I						
learned to						

understand my	
academic	
strengths	
/weakness	
NonDev	122 3.63 .929 .084
Within class or	Developmental 390 3.52 1.03 .05
another	
experience at	
the college I	
learned skills	
and strategies	
to improve test	
taking ability	
NonDev	122 3.40 .97 .08

Table 34.

LSC Kingwood Independent Samples Effective Track to College Readiness

| Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

t	Df	Sig	Mean
		(2-tailed)	Diff`
		d)	
Effective track to	10.06	497	.00* 22.3
college readiness			
Before register	-4.91	506	.00* -.15
required placement			
test			
Took placement test	-3.97	504	.00* -.10
This college required	-17.70	505	.00* -.59
me to enroll in			
classes indicated by			
my placement test			
scores during my 1st			
semester.			
Within class or	2.38	510	.01* .23
another experience at			
this college I			

learned to improve				
study skills				
Within class or	1.87	510	.06	.18
another experience at				
this college				
learned to understand				
my academic strengths				
/weakness				
Within class or	1.09	510	.27	.11
another experience at				
this college				
learned skills and				
strategies to improve				
test taking ability				

Lone Star College Kingwood developmental students are more likely to report Effective Track to College Readiness and within class or another experience at this college they learned to improve their study skills. Non-developmental students are more likely to report before they registered they were required to take a placement test, took placement test and the college required them to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester.

Table 35.

LSC Montgomery Statistics Effective Track to College Readiness

Group	Statistics	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Developmental	Effective track to college readiness	56.52	20.05	.43
	Before register required placement test	1.07	.25	.00
NonDev	Effective track to college readiness	32.54	28.46	1.05
	Before register required placement test	1.29	.45	.01

Took placement	Developmental	2141	1.04	.20	.00
test					
	NonDev	717	1.17	.37	.01
This college	Developmental	2158	1.09	.28	.00
required me to					
enroll in					
classes					
indicated by my					
placement test					
scores during					
my 1st					
semester.					
	NonDev	719	1.63	.48	.01
Within class or	Developmental	2157	4.00	.91	.02
another					
experience at					
the college I					
learned to					
improve study					
skills					
	NonDev	739	3.76	.948	.0
Within class or	Developmental	2158	3.90	.89	.01
another					
experience at					
the college I					
learned to					
understand my					
academic					
strengths					
/weakness					
	NonDev	739	3.65	.92	.03
Within class or	Developmental	2155	3.62	1.03	.02
another					
experience at					
the college I					

learned skills					
and strategies					
to improve test					
taking ability					
	NonDev	738	3.37	1.00	.03

Table 36.

LSC Montgomery Independent Samples Effective Track to College Readiness

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

| |t |Df |Sig |Mean |

| | | |(2-taile|Diff` |

| | | |d) | |

|Effective track to |24.80 |2837 |.00* |23.97 |

|college readiness | | | | |

|Before register |-16.09 |2899 |.00* |-.22 |

|required placement | | | | |

|test | | | | |

|Took placement test|-10.92 |2856 |.00* |-.12 |

|This college |-36.51 |2875 |.00* |-.54 |

|required me to | | | | |

|enroll in classes | | | | |

|indicated by my | | | | |

|placement test | | | | |

|scores during my | | | | |

|1st semester. | | | | |

|Within class or |6.12 |2894 |.00* |.24 |

|another experience | | | | |

|at this college | | | | |

|learned to improve | | | | |

|study skills | | | | |

|Within class or |6.48 |2895 |.00* |.24 |

|another experience | | | | |

|at this college | | | | |

|learned to | | | | |

|understand my | | | | |

|academic strengths | | | | |

/weakness | | | | |
Within class or	5.72	2891	.00*	.25
another experience				
at this college				
learned skills and				
strategies to				
improve test taking				
ability				

Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students are more likely to report Effective Track to College Readiness, within class or another experience at this college they learned to improve their study skills, within class or another experience at this college they learned to understand their academic strengths and weaknesses and within class or another experience at this college they learned skills and strategies to improve test taking ability. Non- developmental students are more likely to report before they registered they were required to take a placement test, took placement test and the college required them to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester.

Table 37.

LSC North Harris Effective Track to College Readiness

Group Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	
Effective track to college readiness					
Developmental	524	58.26	20.64	.90	
NonDev	127	42.41	27.44	2.43	
Before register required placement test					
Developmental	537	1.09	.28	.01	
NonDev	126	1.21	.40	.03	
Took placement test					
Developmental	527	1.05	.21	.00	
NonDev	123	1.18	.385	.035	

This college	Developmental	534	1.07	.25	.01
required me to					
enroll in					
classes					
indicated by my					
placement test					
scores during					
my 1st					
semester.					
	NonDev	124	1.56	.49	.04
Within class or	Developmental	536	4.14	.86	.03
another					
experience at					
the college I					
learned to					
improve study					
skills					
	NonDev	128	4.14	.87	.07
Within class or	Developmental	535	3.99	.85	.03
another					
experience at					
the college I					
learned to					
understand my					
academic					
strengths					
/weakness					
	NonDev	128	4.00	.86	.07
Within class or	Developmental	535	3.74	1.03	.04
another					
experience at					
the college I					
learned skills					
and strategies					
to improve test					

|taking ability | | | | |
| |NonDev |128 |3.73 |1.008 |.08 |

Table 38.

LSC North Harris Independent Samples Effective Track to College Readiness

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

| |t |Df |Sig |Mean |

| | | |(2-tailed)|Diff` |

| | | |d) | |

|Effective track to |7.2 |649 |.00* |15.85 |

|college readiness | | | | |

|Before register |-3.95 |661 |.00* |-.12 |

|required placement | | | | |

|test | | | | |

|Took placement test |-5.03 |648 |.00* |-.13 |

|This college required |-15.36 |656 |.00* |-.48 |

|me to enroll in | | | | |

|classes indicated by | | | | |

|my placement test | | | | |

|scores during my 1st | | | | |

|semester. | | | | |

|Within class or |-0.03 |662 |.97 |-.03 |

|another experience at | | | | |

|this college I learned | | | | |

|to improve study | | | | |

|skills | | | | |

|Within class or |-.15 |661 |.87 |-.01 |

|another experience at | | | | |

|this college I learned | | | | |

|to understand my | | | | |

|academic strengths | | | | |

|/weakness | | | | |

|Within class or |.07 |661 |.94 |.00 |

|another experience at | | | | |

|this college I learned | | | | |

|skills and strategies | | | | |

|to improve test taking| | | | |

|ability | | | | |

Lone Star College North Harris developmental students are more likely to report Effective Track to College Readiness. Non-developmental students are more likely to report before they registered they were required to take a placement test, took placement test and the college required them to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester.

Table 39.

LSC Tomball Statistics Effective Track to College Readiness

|Group Statistics |

| |Developmental |N |Mean |Std. |Std. |

| |Student | | |Deviation|Error |

| | | | | |Mean |

|Effective track|Developmental |418 |57.15 |19.57 |.95 |

|to college | | | | | |

|readiness | | | | | |

| |NonDev |162 |32.30 |28.95 |2.27 |

|Before register|Developmental |426 |1.07 |.24 |.01 |

|required | | | | | |

|placement test | | | | | |

| |NonDev |159 |1.28 |.45 |.03 |

|Took placement |Developmental |419 |1.04 |.19 |.01 |

|test | | | | | |

| |NonDev |154 |1.13 |.33 |.02 |

|This college |Developmental |423 |1.09 |.28 |.01 |

|required me to | | | | | |

|enroll in | | | | | |

|classes | | | | | |

|indicated by my| | | | | |

|placement test | | | | | |

|scores during | | | | | |

|my 1st | | | | | |

|semester. | | | | | |

| |NonDev |158 |1.55 |.49 |.04 |

Within class or	Developmental	415	4.01	.87	.04
another					
experience at					
this college					
learned to					
improve study					
skills					
	NonDev	163	3.65	.90	.07

Within class or	Developmental	416	3.87	.86	.04
another					
experience at					
this college					
learned to					
understand my					
academic					
strengths					
weakness					
	NonDev	163	3.52	.94	.07

Within class or	Developmental	415	3.66	.98	.04
another					
experience at					
this college					
learned skills					
and strategies					
to improve test					
taking ability					
	NonDev	163	3.20	.99	.07

Table 40.
LSC Tomball Independent Samples Effective Track to College Readiness

Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental	t	Df	Sig	Mean
Effective track to college readiness	11.88	578	.00*	24.84

Before register	-7.38	583	.00*	-.21
required placement				
test				
Took placement test	-3.90	571	.00*	-.08
This college	-13.85	579	.00*	-.46
required me to				
enroll in classes				
indicated by my				
placement test				
scores during my				
1st semester.				
Within class or	4.45	576	.00*	.36
another experience				
at this college				
learned to improve				
study skills				
Within class or	4.21	577	.00*	.34
another experience				
at this college				
learned to				
understand my				
academic strengths				
/weakness				
Within class or	4.98	576	.00*	.45
another experience				
at this college				
learned skills and				
strategies to				
improve test taking				
ability				

Lone Star College Tomball developmental students reported Effective Track to College Readiness, within class or another experience at this college they learned to improve their study skills, within class or another experience at this college they learned to understand their academic

strengths and weaknesses and within class or another experience at this college they learned skills and strategies to improve test taking ability. Non-developmental students are more likely to report before they registered they were required to take a placement test, took placement test and the college required them to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester.

Table 41.

LSC Tomball Statistics Engaged Learning

Group Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	
Student		Mean			
Engaged Learning	Developmen	2107	56.52	20.05	.43
	NonDev	732	32.54	28.46	1.05
Ask questions in	Developmen	2173	2.82	.85	.01
class/ contribute					
to class					
discussions					
	NonDev	741	2.77	.901	.033
Prepare two drafts	Developmen	2164	2.16	.88	.01
of a					
paper/assignment					
before turning it					
in					
	NonDev	740	1.91	.86	.03
Participates in	Developmen	2166	1.50	.84	.01
supplemental					
instruction					
	NonDev	744	1.39	.78	.02
Works with other	Developmen	2168	2.36	.98	.02
students on					
project/assignment					
in class					
	NonDev	743	2.37	1.01	.03

Works with student	Developmen	2162	1.54	.86	.01	
outside class on	tal					
projects/assignment						
s						
	NonDev	741	1.51	.83	.03	
Participates in	Developmen	2164	1.25	.64	.01	
required study	tal					
group outside of						
class						
	NonDev	742	1.19	.58	.02	
Participates in	Developmen	2168	1.27	.66	.01	
student initiated	tal					
study group out of						
class (not						
required)						
	NonDev	744	1.26	.64	.02	
Uses electronic	Developmen	2166	2.03	1.11	.02	
tools to	tal					
communicate with						
students about						
coursework						
	NonDev	743	2.03	1.09	.04	
Uses electronic	Developmen	2159	1.96	1.02	.02	
tool to communicate	tal					
w/ instructors						
about coursework						
	NonDev	743	1.91	1.00	.03	
Discussed a	Developmen	2162	2.00	.90	.01	
grade/assignment	tal					
with instructor						
	NonDev	745	1.78	.84	.03	
Prompt feedback	Developmen	2165	2.25	.98	.02	
	tal					
	NonDev	745	2.12	.99	.03	
Discuss ideas from	Developmen	2163	1.51	.84	.01	

readings/class with	tal	
instructor out of		
class		
NonDev	743	1.37 .72 .02
Frequency: Developmen	2068	1.25 .63 .01
Face-to-face	tal	
tutoring		
NonDev	718	1.24 .66 .02
Freq: Use Writing, Developmen	2040	1.93 1.14 .02
math, or other	tal	
skill lab		
NonDev	705	1.45 .93 .03
Use computer lab Developmen	2072	2.17 1.18 .02
tal		
NonDev	716	1.80 1.07 .04
Ask for help from Developmen	2162	2.34 .94 .02
an instructor	tal	
regarding		
questions/problems		
related to class		
NonDev	743	2.17 .95 .03

Table 42.

LSC Tomball Independent Samples Engaged Learning

| Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

	t	Df	Sig	Mean
			(2-tailed)	Diff`
			d)	
Engaged Learning	24.80	2837	.00*	23.97
Ask questions in class/	1.42	2912	.15	.05
contribute to class				
discussions				
Prepare two drafts of a	6.59	2902	.00*	.24
paper/assignment before				
turning it in				
Participates in	3.0	2908	.02*	.10

supplemental instruction				
Works with other	-.05	2908	.95	-.00
students on				
project/assignment in				
class				
Works with student	.84		.39	.03
outside class on		2909		
projects/assignments				
Participates in required	2.31			.06
study group outside of		2901	.02*	
class				
Participates in student	.08	2904	.93	.00
initiated study group				
out of class (not				
required)				
Uses electronic tools to	.11	2910	.90	.00
communicate with				
students about				
coursework				
Uses electronic tool to	1.31	2900	.18	.05
communicate w/				
instructors about				
coursework				
Discussed a	5.80	2905	.00*	.22
grade/assignment with				
instructor				
Prompt feedback	2.95	2908	.00*	.12
Discuss ideas from	3.87	2904	.58	.13
readings/class with				
instructor out of class				
Frequency: Face-to-face	.54	2784	.00*	.01
tutoring				
Freq: Use Writing,	9.83	2743	.00*	.47
math, or other skill lab				
Use computer lab	7.22	2786	.00*	.36

Ask for help from an	4.07	2903	.00*	.16
instructor regarding				
questions/problems				
related to class				

Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report Engaged Learning, they prepare two drafts of a paper or assignment before turning it in, they participate in supplemental instruction, they participate in required study group outside of class, discussed a grade or assignment with an instructor, received prompt feedback, participated in face to face tutoring, use the writing, math, or other skill lab, use the computer lab, and ask for help from an instructor regarding questions or problems related to class.

Table 43.

LSC Cyfair Statistics Engaged Learning

Group Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Engaged Learning	330	56.58	19.43	1.06
Non-Engaged Learning	143	34.41	25.97	2.17
Ask questions in class/ contribute to class discussions	343	2.77	.88	.04
Prepare two drafts of a paper/assignment before turning it in	342	2.23	.88	.04
Participates in supplemental instruction	341	1.45	.79	.04

	NonDev	145	1.28	.67	.05
Works with other	Developmen	342	2.47	.91	.04
students on	tal				
project/assignment					
in class					
	NonDev	144	2.36	.97	.08
Works w/std outside	Developmen	340	1.55	.88	.04
class on	tal				
projects/assignment					
s					
	NonDev	143	1.52	.82	.06
Participates in	Developmen	342	1.23	.62	.03
required study	tal				
group outside of					
class					
	NonDev	143	1.15	.52	.04
Participates in	Developmen	343	1.27	.68	.03
student initiated	tal				
study group out of					
class (not					
required)					
	NonDev	145	1.26	.59	.05
Uses electronic	Developmen	340	2.15	1.11	.06
tools to	tal				
communicate with					
students about					
coursework					
	NonDev	145	2.09	1.08	.09
Uses electronic	Developmen	342	2.03	1.05	.05
tool to communicate	tal				
w/ instructors					
about coursework					
	NonDev	145	1.97	1.03	.08
Discussed a	Developmen	343	2.03	.88	.04
grade/assignment	tal				

with instructor					
NonDev	145	1.79	.79	.06	
Prompt feedback	Developmen	342	2.14	.969	.052
tal					
NonDev	144	2.03	.919	.077	
Discuss ideas from	Developmen	341	1.51	.828	.045
readings/class with	tal				
instructor out of					
class					
NonDev	144	1.40	.741	.062	
Frequency:	Developmen	335	1.22	.595	.033
Face-to-face	tal				
tutoring					
NonDev	135	1.15	.540	.046	
Freq: Writing,	Developmen	332	1.91	1.202	.066
math, or other	tal				
skill lab					
NonDev	132	1.45	.935	.081	
Use computer lab	Developmen	337	2.49	1.256	.068
tal					
NonDev	138	2.03	1.133	.096	
Ask for help from	Developmen	341	2.29	.942	.051
an instructor	tal				
regarding					
questions/problems					
related to class					
NonDev	144	2.09	.884	.074	

Table 44.

LSC Cyfair Independent Samples Engaged Learning

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

| |t |Df |Sig |Mean |

| | | |(2-tailed) |Diff` |

| | | |d) | |

|Engaged Learning |10.24 |471 |.00* |22.17 |

|Ask questions in class/ |.81 |486 |.41 |.07 |

contribute to class				
discussions				
Prepare two drafts of a	2.36	485	.01*	.20
paper/assignment before				
turning it in				
Participates in	2.24	484	.02*	.16
supplemental instruction				
Works with other students	1.15	484	.25	.10
on project/assignment in				
class				
Works with student outside	.29	481	.76	.02
class on				
projects/assignments				
Participates in required	1.29	483	.19	.07
study group outside of				
class				
Participates in student	.15	486	.87	.01
initiated study group out				
of class (not required)				
Uses electronic tools to	.52	483	.60	.05
communicate with students				
about coursework				
Uses electronic tool to	.61	485	.54	.06
communicate w/ instructors				
about coursework				
Discussed a	2.92	486	.00*	.24
grade/assignment with				
instructor				
Prompt feedback	1.14	484	.25	.10
Discuss ideas from	1.39	483	.16	.11
readings/class with				
instructor out of class				
Frequency: Face-to-face	1.28	468	.20	.07
tutoring				
Freq: Use Writing, math,				

or other skill lab	3.94	462	.00*	.46	
Use computer lab	3.70	473	.00*	.45	
Ask for help from an	2.14	483	.03*	.19	
instructor					
regarding questions/problem					
s related to class					

Lone Star College Cyfair developmental students are more likely to report Engaged Learning, prepare two drafts of a paper or assignment before turning it in, participates in supplemental instruction, discussed a grade or assignment with an instructor, frequency in use of writing, math, or other skill lab, use computer lab, and asked for help from an instructor regarding questions or problems related to the class.

Table 45.

LSC Kingwood Statistics Engaged Learning

Group Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	
Engaged Learning	379	55.13	19.37	.99	
NonDev	120	32.75	26.23	2.39	
Ask questions in class/	390	2.85	.87	.04	
contribute to class					
discussions	122	2.81	.80	.07	
Prepare two drafts of a	385	2.00	.87	.04	
paper/assignment before					
turning it in	121	1.98	.95	.08	
Participates in	391	1.53	.87	.04	
supplemental instruction					
NonDev	121	1.39	.81	.07	
Works with other	392	2.35	1.01	.05	
students on					

project/assignment in					
class					
	NonDev	121	2.31	1.09	.09
Works w/std outside	Developmen	387	1.57	.88	.04
class on	tal				
projects/assignments					
	NonDev	121	1.57	.93	.08
Participates in required	Developmen	389	1.25	.57	.02
study group outside of	tal				
class					
	NonDev	121	1.17	.52	.04
Participates in student	Developmen	391	1.24	.60	.03
initiated study group	tal				
out of class (not					
required)					
	NonDev	122	1.36	.80	.07
Uses electronic tools to	Developmen	391	2.03	1.11	.05
communicate with	tal				
students about					
coursework					
	NonDev	121	2.14	1.12	.10
Uses electronic tool to	Developmen	385	1.98	1.04	.05
communicate with	tal				
instructors about					
coursework					
	NonDev	121	1.89	1.00	.09
Discussed a	Developmen	390	1.90	.89	.04
grade/assignment with	tal				
instructors					
	NonDev	122	1.70	.86	.07
Prompt feedback	Developmen	391	2.14	.95	.04
	tal				
	NonDev	122	2.05	1.01	.09
Discuss ideas from	Developmen	389	1.47	.81	.04

readings/class with	tal				
instructor out of class					
NonDev	121	1.31	.68	.06	
Frequency: Face-to-face	Developmen	375	1.25	.63	.03
tutoring	tal				
NonDev	119	1.24	.64	.05	
Freq: Writing, math, or	Developmen	364	1.36	.77	.04
other skill lab	tal				
NonDev	113	1.23	.69	.06	
Use computer lab	Developmen	374	1.69	.99	.05
	tal				
NonDev	117	1.50	.82	.07	
Ask for help from an	Developmen	389	2.27	.94	.04
instructor regarding	tal				
questions/problems					
related to class					
NonDev	122	2.14	.95	.08	

Table 46.

LSC Kingwood Independent Samples Engaged Learning

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

t	Df	Sig	Mean
	(2-taile	Diff`	
	d)		
Engaged Learning	10.06 497	.00*	22.37
Ask questions in class/	.44 510	.65	.04
contribute to class			
discussions			
Prepare two drafts of a	.23 504	.81	.22
paper/assignment before			
turning it in			
Participates in supplemental	.38 511	.70	.00
instruction			
Works with other students on	.00 506	.99	.00
project/assignment in class			
Works with student outside	1.28 508	.19	.07

class on projects/assignments	
Participates in required study	-1.76 511 .07 -.12
group outside of class	
Participates in student	-.92 510 .35 -.10
initiated study group out of	
class (not required)	
Uses electronic tools to	.82 504 .40 .08
communicate with students	
about coursework	
Uses electronic tool to	2.09 510 .03* .19
communicate w/ instructors	
about coursework	
Discussed a grade/assignment	.91 511 .36 .09
with instructor	
Prompt feedback	1.85 508 .06 .15
Discuss ideas from	.15 492 .88 .01
readings/class with instructor	
out of class	
Frequency: Face-to-face	.15 492 .88 .01
tutoring	
Freq: Use Writing, math, or	1.8 475 .10 .13
other skill lab	
Use computer lab	1.8 489 .07 .18
Ask for help from an	1.3 509 .17 .13
instructor regarding	
questions/problems related to	
class	

Lone Star College Kingwood developmental students are more likely to report significance in Engaged Learning and use of electronic tools to communicate with instructors about school work.

Table 47.

LSC Montgomery Statistics Engaged Learning

Group Statistics

Developmental	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Engaged Learning	100	2.09	.03	.19
Use of Electronic Tools	100	.82	.40	.08
Communication with Instructors	100	1.85	.06	.15
Coursework	100	1.8	.10	.13
Computer Lab	100	1.8	.07	.18
Help from Instructor	100	1.3	.17	.13
Questions/Problems	100	.91	.36	.09
Class	100	.15	.88	.01

Developmental	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Engaged Learning	100	2.09	.03	.19
Use of Electronic Tools	100	.82	.40	.08
Communication with Instructors	100	1.85	.06	.15
Coursework	100	1.8	.10	.13
Computer Lab	100	1.8	.07	.18
Help from Instructor	100	1.3	.17	.13
Questions/Problems	100	.91	.36	.09
Class	100	.15	.88	.01

	Student	Mean			
Engaged Learning	456	55.03	20.68	.96	
NonDev	180	24.19	29.82	2.22	
Ask questions in	478	2.83	.82	.03	
class/ contribute					
to class					
discussions					
NonDev	182	2.87	.88	.06	
Prepare two drafts	475	2.12	.89	.04	
of a					
paper/assignment					
before turning it					
in					
NonDev	184	1.91	.86	.06	
Participates in	476	1.42	.82	.03	
supplemental					
instruction					
NonDev	185	1.49	.83	.06	
Works with other	478	2.32	.97	.04	
students on					
project/assignment					
in class					
NonDev	185	2.52	.97	.07	
Works w/std outside	476	1.45	.82	.03	
class on					
projects/assignment					
s					
NonDev	185	1.50	.79	.05	
Participates in	477	1.22	.63	.02	
required study					
group outside of					
class					
NonDev	185	1.25	.67	.04	
Participates in	477	1.21	.59	.02	

student initiated	tal				
study group out of					
class (not					
required)					
	NonDev	185	1.26	.58	.04
Uses electronic	Developmen	477	1.93	1.06	.04
tools to	tal				
communicate with					
students about					
coursework					
	NonDev	185	2.08	1.10	.08
Uses electronic	Developmen	476	1.99	1.05	.04
tool to communicate	tal				
with instructors					
about coursework					
	NonDev	184	2.10	1.06	.07
Discussed a	Developmen	476	2.02	.88	.04
grade/assignment	tal				
with instructors					
	NonDev	184	1.89	.85	.06
Prompt feedback	Developmen	474	2.35	1.00	.04
	tal				
	NonDev	185	2.31	1.05	.07
Discuss ideas from	Developmen	476	1.47	.83	.03
readings/class with	tal				
instructor out of					
class					
	NonDev	184	1.37	.70	.05
Frequency:	Developmen	460	1.26	.62	.02
Face-to-face	tal				
tutoring					
	NonDev	178	1.33	.76	.05
Freq: Writing,	Developmen	452	2.18	1.18	.05
math, or other	tal				
skill lab					

NonDev	175	1.53	.99	.07
Use computer lab	458	1.83	1.05	.04
tal				
NonDev	177	1.53	.96	.07
Ask for help from	475	2.33	.94	.04
an instructor tal				
regarding				
questions/problems				
related to class				
NonDev	184	2.28	.99	.07

Table 48.

LSC Montgomery Independent Samples Engaged Learning
 |Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

	t	Df	Sig	Mean
			(2-tailed)	Diff`
				d)
Engaged Learning	14.82	634	.00*	30.84
Ask questions in class/	-.51	658	.60	-.03
contribute to class				
discussions				
Prepare two drafts of a	2.73	657	.00*	.21
paper/assignment before				
turning it in				
Participates in supplemental	-.94	659	.34	-.06
instruction				
Works with other students on	-2.39	661	.01*	-.20
project/assignment in class				
Works with student outside	-.67	659	.50	-.04
class on				
projects/assignments				
Participates in required	-.68	660	.49	-.03
study group outside of class				
Participates in student	-.68	660	.49	-.03
initiated study group out of				
class (not required)				

Uses electronic tools to	-.1.15	660	.24	-.05
communicate with students				
about coursework				
Uses electronic tool to	-1.6	660	.10	-.14
communicate w/ instructors				
about coursework				
Discussed a grade/assignment	-1.13	658	.25	-.10
with instructor				
Prompt feedback	1.76	658	.07	.13
Discuss ideas from	.39	657	.69	.03
readings/class with				
instructor out of class				
Frequency: Face-to-face	1.51	658	.12	.10
tutoring				
Freq: Use Writing, math, or	-1.27	636	.20	-.07
other skill lab				
Use computer lab	6.39	625	.00*	.64
Ask for help from an	3.32	633	.00*	.30
instructor regarding				
questions/problems related				
to class				

Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students are more likely to report they participate in Engaged Learning, prepares two drafts of a paper or assignment before turning it in, use computer lab and asks for help from an instructor regarding questions or problems related to a class. Non-developmental students are more likely to work with other students on project or assignment in class.

Table 49.

LSC North Harris Statistics Engaged Learning

Group Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Student				
Engaged Learning	524	58.26	20.64	.90
Total				

	NonDev	127	42.41	27.44	2.43
Ask questions in	Developmen	539	2.84	.86	.03
class/ contribute	tal				
to class					
discussions					
	NonDev	128	2.72	.93	.08
Prepare two drafts	Developmen	537	2.29	.84	.03
of a	tal				
paper/assignment					
before turning it					
in					
	NonDev	128	1.90	.81	.07
Participates in	Developmen	532	1.56	.89	.03
supplemental	tal				
instruction					
	NonDev	129	1.52	.90	.07
Works with other	Developmen	533	2.31	1.01	.04
students on	tal				
project/assignment					
in class					
	NonDev	128	2.33	1.12	.09
Works with student	Developmen	535	1.60	.89	.03
outside class on	tal				
projects/assignment					
s					
	NonDev	128	1.64	.89	.07
Participates in	Developmen	536	1.31	.71	.03
required study	tal				
group outside of					
class					
	NonDev	129	1.21	.59	.05
Participates in	Developmen	535	1.32	.74	.03
student initiated	tal				
study group out of					
class (not					

required)					
	NonDev	128	1.30	.73	.06
Uses electronic	Developmen	538	2.03	1.11	.04
tools to	tal				
communicate with					
students about					
coursework					
	NonDev	128	1.95	1.06	.09
Uses electronic	Developmen	535	1.90	.98	.04
tool to communicate	tal				
with instructors					
about coursework					
	NonDev	128	1.90	.97	.08
Discussed a	Developmen	535	2.03	.94	.04
grade/assignment	tal				
with instructors					
	NonDev	130	1.86	.90	.07
Prompt feedback	Developmen	536	2.39	.99	.04
	tal				
	NonDev	129	2.21	.99	.08
Discuss ideas from	Developmen	538	1.55	.89	.03
readings/class with	tal				
instructor out of					
class					
	NonDev	129	1.46	.82	.07
Frequency:	Developmen	508	1.27	.65	.02
Face-to-face	tal				
tutoring					
	NonDev	127	1.31	.77	.06
Freq: Writing,	Developmen	506	1.94	1.08	.04
math, or other	tal				
skill lab					
	NonDev	128	1.57	.94	.08
Use computer lab	Developmen	509	2.41	1.16	.05
	tal				

	NonDev	127	2.06	1.19	.10
Ask for help from	Development	537	2.41	.96	.04
an instructor					
regarding					
questions/problems					
related to class					
	NonDev	128	2.26	.99	.08

Table 50.

LSC North Harris Independent Samples Engaged Learning
 Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental

t	Df	Sig	Mean		
		(2-tailed)	Diff`		
		d)			
Engaged Learning	7.24	.00*	15.85		
	649				
Ask questions in class/	1.43	.665	.15	.12	
contribute to class					
discussions					
Prepare two drafts of a	4.70	.663	.00*	.38	
paper/assignment before					
turning it in					
Participates in	.50	.659	.61	.04	
supplemental instruction					
Works with other students	.659	.85	-.01		
on project/assignment in	-.18				
class					
Works with student outside	-.41	.661	.67	-.03	
class on					
projects/assignments					
Participates in required	1.43	.663	.15	.09	
study group outside of					
class					
Participates in student	.17	.661	.85	.01	
initiated study group out					
of class (not required)					

Uses electronic tools to communicate with students about coursework	.81	664	.41	.08
Uses electronic tool to communicate w/ instructors about coursework	.00	661	.99	.00
Discussed a grade/assignment with instructor	1.81	663	.07	.16
Prompt feedback	1.85	663	.06	.18
Discuss ideas from readings/class with instructor out of class	1.03	665	.30	.08
Frequency: Face-to-face tutoring	-.55	633	.57	-.03
Freq: Use Writing, math, or other skill lab	3.57	632	.00*	.37
Use computer lab	3.02	634	.00*	.35
Ask for help from an instructor regarding questions/problems related to class	1.55	663	.12	.14

Lone Star College North Harris' developmental students are more likely to report Engaged Learning, prepare two drafts of a paper or assignment before turning it in, use the writing, math, or other skill lab, and use the computer lab.

Table 51.

LSC Cyfair Statistics Academic and Social Support Network

Group Statistics	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Student Academic and social support network	330	52.83	23.49	1.29
NonDev	140	45.64	24.70	2.08

Instructors	Development	342	3.89	.95	.05
explained academic					
and student					
support services					
	NonDev	142	3.54	1.10	.09
Instructors	Development	341	4.27	.77	.04
explained grade					
policies					
	NonDev	141	4.17	.81	.06
Instructors	Development	340	4.49	.63	.03
explained syllabi					
	NonDev	140	4.31	.75	.06
Knew how to get in	Development	342	4.28	.82	.04
touch with					
instructor outside					
of class					
	NonDev	142	4.23	.75	.06
1 other student	Development	342	4.14	.94	.05
learned my name					
	NonDev	142	4.04	.84	.07
1 Instructor	Development	341	4.33	.74	.04
learned my name					
	NonDev	142	4.04	.99	.08
I learned 1	Development	343	4.24	.92	.05
students name in					
most of my classes					
	NonDev	142	4.06	.94	.07

Table 52.

LSC Cyfair Independent Samples Academic and Social Support Network

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

| t | Df | Sig | Mean |

| | | (2-tailed) | Diff` |

| | | d) | |

|Academic and social support|2.90 |468 |.00* |7.19 |

|network | | | | |

Instructors explained	3.57	482	.00*	.35
academic and student				
support services				
Instructors explained grade	1.30	480	.19	.10
policies				
Instructors explained	2.65	478	.49	.05
syllabi				
Knew how to get in touch	.69	482	.49	.05
with instructor outside of				
class				
1 other student learned my	1.07	482	.28	.09
name				
1 Instructor learned my	3.44	481	.00*	.28
name				
I learned 1 students name	2.00	483	.04*	.18
in most of my classes				

Lone Star College Cyfair developmental students are more likely to report Academic and Social Support, an instructor explained academic and student support services, one instructor learned their name and they learned one students name in most of their classes.

Table 53.

LSC Kingwood Statistics Academic and Social Support Network

Group Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Student		Mean		
Academic and social support network	379	50.28	23.67	1.21
NonDev	118	47.30	26.32	2.42
Instructors explained academic and student support services	391	3.74	1.02	.05
NonDev	120	3.60	1.03	.09
Instructors explained academic and student support services	390	4.25	.78	.04

explained grade	tal	
policies		
NonDev	119	4.15 .88 .08
Instructors	Developmen	390 4.40 .65 .03
explained syllabi	tal	
NonDev	120	4.33 .70 .06
Knew how to get in	Developmen	391 4.23 .80 .04
touch with	tal	
instructor outside		
of class		
NonDev	120	4.18 .78 .07
1 other student	Developmen	392 4.12 .94 .04
learned my name	tal	
NonDev	120	4.08 .94 .08
1 Instructor	Developmen	392 4.29 .78 .04
learned my name	tal	
NonDev	120	4.18 .90 .08
I learned 1	Developmen	392 4.21 .90 .04
students name in	tal	
most of my classes		
NonDev	119	4.21 .91 .08

Table 54.

LSC Kingwood Independent Samples Academic and Social Support Network

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

|t|Df|Sig|Mean|

|||(2-tailed)|Diff`|

|||d)|

|Academic and social support|1.16|495|.24|2.98|

|network|||||

|Instructors explained|1.27|509|.20|.13|

|academic and student|||||

|support services|||||

|Instructors explained grade|1.15|507|.24|.09|

|policies|||||

|Instructors explained|1.08|508|.28|.07|

syllabi				
Knew how to get in touch	.59	509	.55	.05
with instructor outside of				
class				
1 other student learned my	.39	510	.69	.03
name				
1 Instructor learned my	1.38	510	.16	.11
name				
I learned 1 students name	- .00	509	.99	- .00
in most of my classes				

Lone Star College Kingwood had no statistical significance in the Academic and Social Support Network benchmark.

Table 55.

LSC Montgomery Statistics Academic and Social Support Network

Group	Statistics
	N Mean Std. Deviation Error
Student	Mean
Academic and social support network	Developmental 454 51.51 23.85 1.11
	NonDevelopmental 178 50.25 24.79 1.85
Instructors explained academic and student support services	Developmental 478 3.82 .96 .04
	NonDevelopmental 182 3.66 1.05 .07
Instructors explained grade policies	Developmental 475 4.24 .76 .03
	NonDevelopmental 182 4.29 .67 .05
Instructors explained syllabi	Developmental 476 4.43 .66 .03
	NonDevelopmental 183 4.33 .67 .05
Knew how to get in touch with	Developmental 476 4.34 .71 .03
	NonDevelopmental 183 4.33 .67 .05

instructor outside	
of class	
NonDev	183 4.28 .76 .05
1 other student	Development 475 4.10 .97 .04
learned my name	tal
NonDev	182 4.16 .85 .06
1 Instructor	Development 474 4.24 .88 .04
learned my name	tal
NonDev	183 4.13 .92 .06
I learned	1 Development 476 4.21 .92 .04
students name in	tal
most of my classes	
NonDev	183 4.25 .77 .05

Table 56.

LSC Montgomery Independent Samples Academic and Social Support Network

Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental

t	Df	Sig	Mean
		(2-tailed)	Diff`
		d)	
Academic and social support	.58	630	.55 1.25
network			
Instructors explained	1.82	658	.06 .15
academic and student			
support services			
Instructors explained grade	-.72	655	.46 -.04
policies			
Instructors explained	1.72	657	.08 .09
syllabi			
Knew how to get in touch	.92	657	.35 .05
with instructor outside of			
class			
1 other student learned my	-.75	655	.45 -.06
name			
1 Instructor learned my	1.45	655	.14 .11
name			

|I learned 1 students name |-.59 |657|.55|-.04|

|in most of my classes |||||

Lone Star College Montgomery had no statistical significance in the Academic Support and Social Network benchmark.

Table 57.

LSC North Harris Statistics Academic and Social Support Network

|Group Statistics |

| |Developmen|N |Mean |Std. |Std. |

| |tal || |Deviation|Error |

| |Student || |Mean |

|Academic and social|Developmen|524 |49.87 |24.17 |1.05 |

|support network |tal || || |

| |NonDev |124 |51.66 |21.63 |1.943 |

|Instructors |Developmen|538 |3.79|.99|.04|

|explained academic |tal || || |

|and student || || || |

|support services || || || |

| |NonDev |126 |3.57 |1.08|.09|

|Instructors |Developmen|535 |4.24|.80|.03|

|explained grade |tal || || |

|policies || || || |

| |NonDev |125 |4.34|.80|.07|

|Instructors |Developmen|537 |4.36|.71|.03|

|explained syllabi |tal || || |

| |NonDev |126 |4.48|.65|.05|

|Knew how to get in |Developmen|538 |4.34|.70|.03|

|touch with |tal || || |

|instructor outside || || || |

|of class || || || |

| |NonDev |127 |4.31|.70|.06|

|1 other student |Developmen|538 |4.07|.98|.04|

|learned my name |tal || || |

| |NonDev |127 |4.10|.99|.08|

|1 Instructor |Developmen|537 |4.20|.91|.04|

|learned my name |tal || || |

NonDev	127	4.38	.70	.06	
I learned 1	Development	538	4.16	.92	.04
students name in	tal				
most of my classes					
NonDev	127	4.25	.86	.07	

Table 58.

LSC North Harris Independent Samples Academic and Social Support Network

Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental

t	Df	Sig	Mean
		(2-tailed)	Diff`
		d)	
Academic and social support	-1.75	.044	-1.79
network			
Instructors explained academic	2.18	.02*	.21
and student support services			
Instructors explained grade	-1.2	.22	-.09
policies			
Instructors explained syllabi	-1.60	.10	-.11
Knew how to get in touch with	.30	.75	.02
instructor outside of class			
1 other student learned my name	-.30	.75	-.03
1 instructor learned my name	-2.03	.04*	-.17
I learned 1 students name in	-1.06	.29	-.09
most of my classes			

Lone Star College North Harris developmental students are more likely to report instructors explained academic and social support services. Non-developmental students are more likely to report one instructor learned their name.

Table 59.

LSC Tomball Statistics Academic and Social Support Network

Group	Statistics				
Developmental	N	Mean	Std.	Std.	
tal		Deviation	Error		
Student		Mean			
Academic and social	Developmental	418	48.71	23.63	1.15

support network	tal					
	NonDev	157	45.89	22.45	1.79	
Instructors	Development	424	3.71	.99	.04	
explained academic	tal					
and student						
support services						
	NonDev	159	3.53	.98	.07	
Instructors	Development	425	4.19	.77	.03	
explained grade	tal					
policies						
	NonDev	160	4.19	.78	.06	
Instructors	Development	424	4.34	.69	.03	
explained syllabi	tal					
	NonDev	159	4.38	.66	.05	
Knew how to get in	Development	424	4.26	.73	.03	
touch with	tal					
instructor outside						
of class						
	NonDev	160	4.13	.76	.06	
Students learned my	Development	424	4.05	.95	.04	
name	tal					
	NonDev	159	4.00	1.01	.08	
1 other student	Development	427	4.17	.86	.04	
learned my name	tal					
	NonDev	160	4.13	.84	.06	
I learned 1	Development	426	4.21	.84	.04	
students name in	tal					
most of my classes						
	NonDev	160	4.08	.97	.07	

Table 60.

Tomball Independent Samples Academic and Social Support Network

|Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

|t |Df |Sig |Mean |

|| |(2-tailed) |Diff` |

|| |d) |

Academic and social support	1.29	573	.19	2.82
network				
Instructors explained	1.9	581	.05	.18
academic and student				
support services				
Instructors explained grade	- .10	583	.91	-.00
policies				
Instructors explained	- .51	581	.60	-.03
syllabi				
Knew how to get in touch	1.83	582	.06	.12
with instructor outside of				
class				
1 other student learned my	.60	581	.54	.05
name				
1 Instructor learned my	.43	585	.66	.03
name				
I learned 1 students name	1.55	584	.12	.12
in most of my classes				

Lone Star College Tomball had no statistical significance in the Academic and Social Support Network benchmark.

Table 61 LSC Cyfair Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics				
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Student		Mean		
Felt Welcomed 1st visit	342	3.92	.860	.046
NonDev	142	3.86	.740	.062
Instructor wants me to succeed	342	4.29	.677	.037
NonDev	142	4.17	.673	.057
Met with an advisor at convenient times	338	3.45	1.10	.060
NonDev	139	3.33	1.03	.088
An advisor helped me	340	3.28	1.25	.068

to select a course of	tal				
study, program, or					
major					
	NonDev	142	3.20	1.21	.102
Advisor helped set	Developmen	337	2.82	1.17	.064
academic goals	tal				
	NonDev	141	2.65	1.16	.098
Advisor helped	Developmen	339	3.55	1.22	.066
identify courses	tal				
needed					
	NonDev	142	3.20	1.24	.104
Staff discussed	Developmen	340	2.43	1.12	.061
commitments outside	tal				
of school					
	NonDev	142	2.39	1.03	.087
All Instructors had	Developmen	340	3.50	1.16	.063
activities to	tal				
introduce students to					
one another					
	NonDev	140	3.07	1.17	.100
Instructors explained	Developmen	342	3.89	.952	.051
academic & student	tal				
support services					
	NonDev	142	3.54	1.10	.093
Staff Learned my name	Developmen	342	2.88	1.39	.075
	tal				
	NonDev	142	2.73	1.28	.108
Students learned my	Developmen	342	4.14	.940	.051
name	tal				
	NonDev	142	4.04	.849	.071
1 Instructor learned	Developmen	341	4.33	.741	.040
my name	tal				
	NonDev	142	4.04	.996	.084
Participates in	Developmen	341	1.45	.794	.043
supplemental	tal				

instruction					
NonDev	145	1.28	.674	.056	
Discussed a	Developmen	343	2.03	.885	.048
grade/assignment with	tal				
instructor					
NonDev	145	1.79	.792	.066	
Receive prompt	Developmen	342	2.14	.969	.052
written or oral	tal				
feedback from					
instructors on					
performance					
NonDev	144	2.03	.919	.077	

Table 62.

LSC Cyfair Independent Samples Early Connections

| Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental |

| t | Df | Sig | Mean |

| | | (2-tailed) | Diff` |

| | | d) | |

| Felt welcomed first | .78 | 482 | .43 | .06 |

| visit | | | |

| Instructor wanted me | 1.78 | 482 | .07 | .12 |

| to succeed | | | |

| Met with an advisor | 1.08 | 475 | .27 | .11 |

| convenient times | | | |

| An advisor helped me | .66 | 480 | .50 | .08 |

| to select a course | | | |

| of study, program, | | | |

| or major | | | |

| An advisor helped | 1.52 | 476 | .12 | .18 |

| set academic goals | | | |

| Advisor helped | 2.80 | 479 | .00* | .34 |

| identify courses | | | |

| needed | | | |

| Staff discussed | .31 | 480 | .75 | .03 |

| commitments out of | | | |

school	
All instructors had	3.68 478 .00* .43
activities	
Instructors	3.5 482 .00* .35
explained academic &	
student support	
services	
Staff learned my	1.11 482 .26 .15
name	
Students learned my	1.07 482 .28 .09
name	
1 instructor learned	3.4 481 .00* .28
my name	
Participates in	2.2 484 .02* .16
supplemental	
instruction	
Discussed a	2.9 486 .00* .249
grade/assignment	
with an instructor	
Receive prompt	1.1 484 .25 .10
written or oral	
feedback from	
instructor on	
performance	

To answer research question two data analysis was run to obtain frequency in developmental and non-developmental students' answers. At Lone Star College Cyfair developmental students are more likely to report advisor helped identify courses needed, all instructors had activities to introduce students to one another, participates in supplemental instruction, and discussed a grade/assignment with an instructor.

Table 63.

LSC Kingwood Group Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics	
t Df Sig Mean	

		(2-taile	Diff`	
		d)		
Felt welcomed first	.23	510	.81	.02
visit				
Instructor wanted me	.72	510	.47	.05
to succeed				
Met with an advisor	-.42	506	.67	-.04
convenient times				
An advisor helped me	.84	507	.40	.09
to select a course of				
study, program, or				
major				
An advisor helped set	1.05	507	.29	.12
academic goals				
Advisor helped	2.1	509	.03*	.22
identify courses				
needed				
Staff discussed	.85	505	.39	.10
commitments out of				
school				
All instructors had	2.2	508	.02*	.28
activities to				
introduce students to				
one another				
Instructors explained	1.2	509	.20	.13
academic & student				
support services				
Staff learned my name	.81	510	.41	.11
Student learned my	.39	510	.69	.03
name				
1 instructor learned	1.3	510	.16	.11
my name				
Participates in	1.5	510	.11	.14
supplemental				

instruction				
Discussed a	2.0	510	.03*	.19
grade/assignment with				
an instructor				
Receive prompt written	.91	511	.36	.09
or oral feedback from				
instructor on				
performance				

Lone Star College Kingwood developmental students are more likely to report advisor helped identify courses needed, all instructors had activities to introduce students to one another and discussed a grade/assignment with an instructor.

Table 65.

LSC Montgomery Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	
Student		Mean			
Felt Welcomed 1st visit	478	3.89	.808	.037	
NonDev	183	3.77	.800	.059	
Instructor wants me to succeed	476	4.18	.706	.032	
NonDev	183	4.10	.656	.048	
Met w/advisor convenient times	473	3.74	.964	.044	
NonDev	182	3.69	.995	.074	
An advisor helped me to select a course of study, program, or major	474	3.47	1.21	.056	
NonDev	183	3.42	1.21	.090	
Advisor helped set academic goals	474	2.97	1.13	.052	
NonDev	183	2.94	1.15	.085	

Advisor helped	Developmen	473	3.78	1.06	.049
identify courses	tal				
needed					
	NonDev	183	3.66	1.15	.085
Staff discussed	Developmen	475	2.71	1.18	.054
commitments outside	tal				
of school					
	NonDev	183	2.73	1.09	.081
All Instructors had	Developmen	476	3.00	1.14	.052
activities	tal				
	NonDev	183	2.96	1.12	.083
Instructors explained	Developmen	478	3.82	.962	.044
academic and student	tal				
support services					
	NonDev	182	3.66	1.05	.078
Staff Learned my name	Developmen	477	2.81	1.32	.061
	tal				
	NonDev	183	2.67	1.31	.097
Students learned my	Developmen	475	4.10	.972	.045
name	tal				
	NonDev	182	4.16	.851	.063
1 Instructor learned	Developmen	474	4.24	.882	.040
my name	tal				
	NonDev	183	4.13	.928	.069
Participates in	Developmen	476	1.42	.821	.038
supplemental	tal				
instruction					
	NonDev	185	1.49	.835	.061
Discussed a	Developmen	476	2.02	.889	.041
grade/assignment with	tal				
instructor					
	NonDev	184	1.89	.858	.063
Receive prompt	Developmen	474	2.35	1.00	.046
written/ oral	tal				
feedback from					

	t	Df	Sig	Mean	Diff	(2-tailed)	id
Instructor on performance	1.85	2.31	1.05	.077			
Felt welcomed first visit	1.7	659	.08	.12			
Instructor wanted me to succeed	1.3	657	.17	.08			
Met with an advisor at convenient times	.65	653	.51	.05			
An advisor helped me to select a course of study, program, or major	.52	655	.60	.05			
An advisor helped set academic goals	1.2	654	.20	.12			
Advisor helped identify courses needed	-.24	656	.80	-.02			
Staff discussed commitments out of school	.42	657	.66	.04			
All instructors had activities	1.8	658	.06	.15			
Instructors explained academic & student support services	1.2	658	.22	.13			
Staff learned my name	-.75	655	.45	.06			
Student learned my name	1.4	655	.14	.11			
1 instructor learned my name							

Participates in |-.94 |659|.34|-.06|
 supplemental | | | | |
 instruction | | | | |
 Discussed a |1.7 |658|.07|.13|
 grade/assignment with | | | | |
 an instructor | | | | |
 Receive prompt written |.39 |657|.69|.03|
 or oral feedback from | | | | |
 instructor on | | | | |
 performance | | | | |

Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students had no statistical significance.

Table 67.

LSC North Harris Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics	t	Df	Sig	Mean	(2-tailed)	Diff`	d
Felt welcomed first visit	.04	665	.96	.00			
Instructor wanted me to succeed	1.7	664	.07	.12			
Met with an advisor at convenient times	-.19	656	.84	-.01			
An advisor helped me to select a course of study, program, or major	-.1.16	661	.24	-.13			
An advisor helped set academic goals	-.1.00	660	.31	-.12			
Advisor helped identify courses needed	.23	662	.81	.02			
Staff discussed commitments out of	.00	659	.81	.02			

school	
All instructors had activities to introduce students to one another	3.78 658 .00* .45
Instructors explained academic & student support services	2.18 662 .02* .21
Staff learned my name	-.73 663 .46 -.10
Student learned my name	-.30 663 .75 -.03
1 instructor learned my name	-2.03 662 .04* -.17
Participates in supplemental instruction	.50 659 .61 .04
Discussed a grade/assignment with an instructor	1.81 663 .07 .16
Receive prompt written or oral feedback from instructor on performance	1.85 663 .06 .18

Lone Star College North Harris developmental students are more likely to say all instructors had activities to introduce students to one another and instructors explained academic and student support services. Non-developmental students are more likely to report one instructor learned my name.

Table 69.

LSC Tomball Statistics Early Connections

Group Statistics			
Developmental	Non-Developmental		
N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Error
Student	Mean		
Felt Welcomed 1st visit	Developmental	424	3.92 .769 .037
	Non Dev	160	3.71 .757 .060

Instructor wants me to	Developmen	426	4.31	.653	.032
succeed	tal				
	Non Dev	160	4.13	.701	.055
Met with advisor	Developmen	426	3.76	.973	.047
convenient times	tal				
	Non Dev	159	3.81	.910	.072
An advisor helped me to	Developmen	425	3.64	1.12	.054
select a course of	tal				
study, program, or					
major					
	Non Dev	158	3.54	1.16	.092
Advisor helped set	Developmen	424	3.18	1.12	.054
academic goals	tal				
	Non Dev	160	2.84	.994	.079
Advisor helped identify	Developmen	425	3.87	1.02	.050
courses needed	tal				
	Non Dev	160	3.59	1.11	.088
Staff discussed	Developmen	425	2.69	1.20	.058
commitments outside of	tal				
school					
	Non Dev	160	2.56	1.05	.083
All Instructors had	Developmen	425	3.31	1.19	.058
activities	tal				
to introduce students					
to one another					
	Non Dev	158	2.89	1.06	.085
Instructors explained	Developmen	424	3.71	.999	.049
academic &std; support	tal				
services					
	Non Dev	159	3.53	.986	.078
Staff learned my name	Developmen	425	2.94	1.35	.066
	tal				
	Non Dev	160	2.67	1.29	.103
Students learned my	Developmen	424	4.05	.952	.046
name	tal				

Non Dev	159	4.00	1.01	.081	
Instructor learned my	427	4.17	.868	.042	
name					
Non Dev	160	4.13	.848	.067	
Participates in	426	1.50	.830	.040	
supplemental					
instruction					
Non Dev	164	1.26	.652	.051	
Discussed a	418	2.00	.903	.044	
grade/assignment with					
instructor					
NonDev	164	1.65	.797	.062	
Receive prompt written/	422	2.14	.963	.047	
oral feedback from					
instructor on					
performance					
NonDev	165	1.98	.947	.074	

Table 70.

LSC Tomball Independent Samples Early Connections

Independent Samples Development vs. Non-Developmental

t	Df	Sig	Mean	
		(2-tailed)	Diff`	
			d)	
Felt welcomed first	2.97	.00*	.21	
visit				
Instructor wanted me to	2.92	.00*	.18	
succeed				
Met with an advisor	-.52	.59	-.04	
convenient times				
An advisor helped me to	.98	.32	.10	
select a course of				
study, program, or major				
An advisor helped set	3.30	.00*	.33	
academic goals				
Advisor helped identify	2.86	.00*	.27	

courses needed	
Staff discussed	1.28 583 .20 .13
commitments out of	
school	
All instructors had	3.88 581 .00* .42
activities to introduce	
students to one another	
Instructors explained	1.94 581 .05 .18
academic & student	
support services	
Staff learned my name	2.15 583 .03* .26
Student learned my name	.60 581 .54 .05
1 instructor learned my	.43 585 .66 .03
name	
Participates in	3.35 588 .00* .24
supplemental instruction	
Discussed a	4.44 580 .00* .35
grade/assignment with an	
instructor	
Receive prompt written	1.85 585 .06 .16
or oral feedback from	
instructor on	
performance	

Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report they felt welcomed on their first visit to the campus, instructors want them to succeed, advisor helped them set academic goals, an advisor helped identify courses needed, all instructors had activities to introduce student to one another, staff learned my name, participates in supplemental instruction, and discussed a grade/assignment with an instructor.

Table 71.

Categorical Data-Research Question #2 Institutional Practices

Crosstab		
Campus	Developmental Student	Total
	Developmental	NonDevelopmental
	Count	Count

|Cy Fair |Online Orient |No |Count |325 |140 |

| |prior to classes|response | | |

| | % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

| | |Developmen| | % |

| | |tal | | | |

| | |Student | | | |

|Kingwood|Online Orient |No |Count |377 |119 |

| |prior to classes|response | | |

| | % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

| | |Developmen| | % |

| | |tal | | | |

| | |Student | | | |

|Montgome|Online Orient |No |Count |466 |178 |

|ry |prior to classes|response | | |

| | % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

| | |Developmen| | % |

| | |tal | | | |

| | |Student | | | |

|North |Online Orient |No |Count |514 |121 |

|Harris |prior to classes|response | | |

| | % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

| | |Developmen| | % |

| | |tal | | | |

| | |Student | | | |

|Tomball |Online Orient |No |Count |409 |160 |

| |prior to classes|response | | |

| | % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

| | |Developmen| | % |

| | |tal | | | |

| | |Student | | | |

Table 72.

Categorical Data -Research Question #2 Institutional Practices

|Chi-Square Tests |

|Campus |Value |df |Asymp. |Exact |Exact |

| | |Sig. |Sig. |Sig. |

	(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)
Cy Fair			
Campus	Developmental	Total	
Student			
Developmental	NonDevelopmental		
Developmental	Developmental		
Cy Fair	On campus	No response	Count 237 94
orientation			
% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Developmental			0%
Student			
Kingwood	On campus	No response	Count 336 99
orientation			
% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Developmental			0%
Student			
Montgomery	On campus	No response	Count 228 98
orientation			
% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Developmental			0%
Student			
North	On campus	No response	Count 437 97
Harris	orientation		
% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Developmental			0%
Student			
Tomball	On campus	No response	Count 346 141
orientation			
% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
Developmental			0%
Student			

Table 74.

Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests

Campus	Value	df	Asymp.	Exact	Exact
			Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
			(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)
Cy Fair					
Campus	Developmental	Total			
	Student				
	Developmental	NonDevelopmental			
	total	total			
Cy Fair	Before register	Yes	Count	326	107
	required				
	placement test				
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.	
	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
Kingwood	Before register	Yes	Count	359	92
	required				
	placement test				
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.	
	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
Montgomery	Before register	Yes	Count	441	104
	required				
	placement test				
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.	
	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
North Harris	Before register	Yes	Count	491	100
	required				
	placement test				
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.	
	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
Tomball	Before register	Yes	Count	398	114
	required				
	placement test				

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| |Developmental| | |0% |

|| |Student| | | |

Table 76.

Chi-Square Tests

|Chi-Square Tests |

|Campus |Value |Df |Asymp. |Exact |Exact |

|| |Sig. |Sig. |Sig. |

|| | |(2-sided)| |(2-sided)| |(1-sided)|

|Cy Fair |

|Campus |Developmental |Total|

| |Student | |

| |Developme|NonDevelopm| |

| |ntal |ental | |

|Cy Fair|Took placement |Yes |Count |324 |120 |

| |test | | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| |Developmental| | |% |

|| |Student| | | |

|Kingwool|Took placement |Yes |Count |371 |102 |

|d |test | | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| |Developmental| | |% |

|| |Student| | | |

|Montgom|Took placement |Yes |Count |448 |141 |

|ery |test | | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| |Developmental| | |% |

|| |Student| | | |

|North |Took placement |Yes |Count |501 |101 |

|Harris |test | | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| |Developmental| | |% |

|| |Student| | | |

|Tomball|Took placement |Yes |Count |402 |134 |

	test					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0		
		Developmental		%		
		Student				

Table 78.

Chi-Square Tests

|Chi-Square Tests |
Campus	Value	df	Asymp.	Exact	Exact
			Sig.	Sig.	Sig.
			(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)
Cy Fair					

Campus	Developmental Student	Total	
	Developmental	NonDevelopm	
		ental	

Cy Fair	exptest	1	Count	43	45	
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0		
		Developmental		%		
		Student				

Kingwool	exptest	1	Count	36	41	
d						
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0		
		Developmental		%		
		Student				

Montgom	exptest	1	Count	63	87	
ery						
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0		
		Developmental		%		
		Student				

North	exptest	1	Count	63	33	
Harris						
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0		
		Developmental		%		
		Student				

|Tomball|exptest |1 |Count |49 |50 |
 || % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| Developmental || % |

|| Student || |

Table 80.

Chi-Square Tests

| Chi-Square Tests |

| Campus |

| Campus | Developmental | Total |

| Student | |

| Developme | Non Developm | |

| n | tal | ental | |

| Cy Fair | Required Dev | Yes | Count | 310 | 53 |

| Ed | | | | |

|| % within | 100.0% | 100.0% | 100.0 |

|| Developmental || % |

|| Student || |

| Kingwool | Required Dev | Yes | Count | 361 | 39 |

| d | Ed | | | | |

|| % within | 100.0% | 100.0% | 100.0 |

|| Developmental || % |

|| Student || |

| Montgom | Required Dev | Yes | Count | 414 | 47 |

| ery | Ed | | | | |

|| % within | 100.0% | 100.0% | 100.0 |

|| Developmental || % |

|| Student || |

| North | Required Dev | Yes | Count | 496 | 55 |

| Harris | Ed | | | | |

|| % within | 100.0% | 100.0% | 100.0 |

|| Developmental || % |

|| Student || |

| Tomball | Required Dev | Yes | Count | 385 | 71 |

| Ed | | | | |

|| % within | 100.0% | 100.0% | 100.0 |

|| Developmental || % |

|| Student || |

Table 82.

Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests	Value	df	Asymp.	Exact	Exact
	Sig.	Sig.	Sig.		
	(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)		
Cy Fair					
Campus	Developmental Student	Total			
	Developme	NonDevelopm			
	ntal	ental			
Cy Fair	enrlssdc	1	Count	25	3
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				
Kingwood	enrlssdc	1	Count	39	1
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				
Montgome	enrlssdc	1	Count	40	1
ry					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				
North	enrlssdc	1	Count	41	3
Harris					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				
Tomball	enrlssdc	1	Count	43	3
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				

Table 84.

Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests

|Campus |Value |df |Asymp. |Exact |Exact |

| | | |Sig. |Sig. |Sig. |

| | | |(2-sided)|(2-sided)|(1-sided)|

|Cy Fair |

|Campus |Developmental |Tota|

| |Student | | |

| |Developme|NonDevelopm| |

| |ntal |ental | |

|Cy Fair|Enrolled 1st |Enrolled |Count |6 |1 |

| |semester learning | | | | |

| |commu | | | | |

| | |% within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

| | |Developmenta| | |0% |

| | | |Student | | | |

|Kingwoo|Enrolled 1st |Enrolled |Count |7 |3 |

|d |semester learning | | | | |

| |commu | | | | |

| | |% within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

| | |Developmenta| | |0% |

| | | |Student | | | |

|Montgom|Enrolled 1st |Enrolled |Count |5 |2 |

|ery |semester learning | | | | |

| |commu | | | | |

| | |% within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

| | |Developmenta| | |0% |

| | | |Student | | | |

|North |Enrolled 1st |Enrolled |Count |25 |3 |

|Harris |semester learning | | | | |

| |commu | | | | |

| | |% within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

| | |Developmenta| | |0% |

| | | |Student | | | |

|Tomball|Enrolled 1st |Enrolled |Count |7 |0 |

| |semester learning | | | | |

| |commu | | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| Developmental | |0% |

|| Student | | | |

Table 86.

Chi-Square Tests

|Chi-Square Tests |

|Campus |

|Campus |Developmental |Total|

| |Student | | |

| |Developmental|NonDevelopmental| |

| |ntal |ental | |

|Cy Fair |

|Campus |

|Campus |Developmental |Student|Total|

| |Developmental|NonDevelopmental| |

| |ntal |ental | |

|Cy Fair|Career |Yes |Count |165 |67 |

| |Counseling | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| Developmental | | % |

|| Student | | | |

|Kingwood|Career |Yes |Count |189 |53 |

|d |Counseling | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| Developmental | | % |

|| Student | | | |

|Montgomery|Career |Yes |Count |315 |115 |

|ery |Counseling | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| Developmental | | % |

|| Student | | | |

|North |Career |Yes |Count |237 |72 |

|Harris |Counseling | | | |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.0|

|| Developmental | | % |

	Student			
Tomball	Career	Yes	Count	177 63
	Counseling			
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	Developmental		%	
	Student			

Table 90.

Chi-Square Tests

Chi-Square Tests				
Campus	Value	df	Asymp. Sig.	Exact Sig.
			(2-sided)	(2-sided) (1-sided)
Cy Fair				
Campus	Developmental	Total		
	Student			
	Developmental	NonDevelopmental		
	Total			

Cy Fair	Job placement	Yes	Count	80 24
	assistance			
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	Developmental		0%	
	Student			

Kingwood	Job placement	Yes	Count	92 25
	assistance			
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	Developmental		0%	
	Student			

Montgomery	Job placement	Yes	Count	161 67
	assistance			
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	Developmental		0%	
	Student			

North Harris	Job placement	Yes	Count	150 37
	assistance			
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
Tomball	Job placement	Yes	Count	115	31
assistance					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental		0%		
	Student				

Table 92.

Chi-Square Tests

| Chi-Square Tests |
Campus	Value	df	Asymp. Sig.	Exact Sig.	Exact Sig.
		Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	
		(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)	
Cy Fair					
Campus	Developmental	Total			
Student					
Developme	NonDevelopm				
n	tal	ental			
Cy Fair	Face to face	Yes	Count	259	102
tutoring					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental		%		
	Student				
Kingwoo	Face to face	Yes	Count	307	95
d	tutoring				
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental		%		
	Student				
Montgom	Face to face	Yes	Count	395	164
lery	tutoring				
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental		%		
	Student				
North	Face to face	Yes	Count	404	101
Harris	tutoring				

	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0	
	Developmental		%		
	Student				
Tomball	Face to face	Yes	Count	313	132
tutoring					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0	
	Developmental		%		
	Student				

Table 94.

Chi-Square Tests

|Chi-Square Tests |
Campus	Value	df	Asymp.	Exact	Exact
		Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	
		(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)	

|Cy Fair |
Campus	Developmental Student	Total	
	Developme	NonDevelopm	
	ntal	ental	

Cy Fair	Online tutor	Yes	Count	92	35
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				

Kingwood	Online tutor	Yes	Count	73	32
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Developmental				
	Student				

Montgome	Online tutor	Yes	Count	137	60	
ry						
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
	Developmental					
	Student					

North	Online tutor	Yes	Count	123	35	
Harris						
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%		
	Developmental					

	Student				
Tomball	Online tutor	Yes	Count	105	36
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

|| Developmental ||| |

|| Student ||| |

Table 96.

Chi-Square Tests

|Chi-Square Tests |

|Campus |Value |df |Asymp. |Exact |Exact |

||| |Sig. |Sig. |Sig. |

||| |(2-sided)|(2-sided)|(1-sided|

||| |)|

|Cy Fair |

|Campus |Developmental |Tota|

| |Student || |

| |Developme|NonDevelopm| |

| |ntal |ental | |

|Cy Fair|Assigned person |Yes |Count |52 |8 |

| |for needed info ||| |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

|| |Developmental| | |0% |

|| |Student ||| |

|Kingwoo|Assigned person |Yes |Count |128 |17 |

|d |for needed info ||| |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

|| |Developmental| | |0% |

|| |Student ||| |

|Montgom|Assigned person |Yes |Count |55 |19 |

|ery |for needed info ||| |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

|| |Developmental| | |0% |

|| |Student ||| |

|North |Assigned person |Yes |Count |181 |35 |

|Harris |for needed info ||| |

|| % within |100.0% |100.0% |100.|

	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
Tomball	Assigned person	Yes	Count	82	14
for needed info					
	% within	100.0%	100.0%	100.	
	Developmental		0%		
	Student				
Table 98.					
Chi-Square Tests					
Chi-Square Tests					
Campus	Value	df	Asymp.	Exact	Exact
		Sig.	Sig.	Sig.	
		(2-sided)	(2-sided)	(1-sided)	
Cy Fair					
	Cyfair	Kingwood		Montgome	NHarris
			ry		
Effective	Developme	56.58	55.13	56.52	58.26
track to	ntal	34.41	32.75	32.54	42.41
college	Non Dev				
readiness					
Before	Developme	1.05	1.07	1.07	1.09
register	ntal	1.25	1.23	1.29	1.21
required	Non Dev				
placement					
test					
Took	Developme	1.04	1.04	1.04	1.05
placement	ntal	1.14	1.14	1.17	1.18
test	Non Dev				
This college	Developme	1.09	1.07	1.09	1.07
required me	ntal	1.62	1.67	1.63	1.56
to enroll in	Non Dev				
classes					
indicated by					

my placement								
test scores								
during my								
first								
semester/qua								
rter.								
Within class	Developme	3.97	3.89	4.0	NS	4.01		
or another	ntal	3.75	3.66	3.76	NS	3.65		
experience	Non Dev							
at this								
college I								
learned to								
improve my								
study skills								
Within class	Developme	3.86	NS	3.90	NS	3.87		
or another	ntal	3.64	NS	3.65	NS	3.52		
experience	Non Dev							
at this								
college I								
learned to								
understand								
my academic								
strengths/we								
akness								
Within class	Developme	3.63	NS	3.62	NS	3.66		
or another	ntal	3.37	NS	3.37	NS	3.20		
experience	Non Dev							
at this								
college I								
learned								
skills and								
strategies								
to improve								
test taking								
ability								

Cross-campus comparison for Effective Track to College Readiness is more likely to be reported by developmental students at all five colleges within Lone Star College System. Non-developmental students at all five colleges within Lone Star College System are likely to report before registration they were required to take a placement test and took a placement test. Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair, Lone Star College Kingwood, Lone Star College Montgomery, and Lone Star Tomball are more likely to report within class or another experience at this college they learned to improve their study skills.

Lone Star College Cyfair, Lone Star College Montgomery, and Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report within class or another experience at their college they learned to understand their academic strengths/weakness. Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair, Lone Star College Montgomery and Lone Star Tomball are more likely to report within class or another experience at their college they learned skills and strategies to improve test-taking ability.

Effective Track to College Readiness appears to be the most significant for developmental students within this system. This benchmark is significant as it uses system wide institutional practices that influence academic success for developmental students. Enforcing the practice of taking placement tests prior to enrolling classes reveals the appropriateness or inappropriateness of college level courses for first time in college students.

Implications For Practice

The significance in the benchmark Effective Track to College Readiness implies developmental students are more likely to report their success was influenced by the mandated institutional practices prior to enrollment in college level classes. First time in college students may or may not be aware of their academic deficiencies. The eagerness of taking college level classes may override their aptitude in that course. Students who take placement tests prior to enrollment in college classes have the opportunity to test their knowledge in the material prior to taking the course. Review of the outcomes of the placement exam with a college representative allows for the one on one advisement that developmental students deem as an institutional practice that leads to their success. This benchmark implies

that it is a necessary practice within 2-year institutions for developmental students.

The benchmark Effective Track to College Readiness indicates that students enrolled in classes indicated by the placement test during their first semester/quarter provides an opportunity for students to converge over the skills in which they are deficient. Developmental students were statistically significant when reporting that within class or another experience at the college they learned to improve their study skills. This verifies that first time in college developmental students are not prepared for college level courses and have not mastered study skills that will lead them to success in college. Developmental students significantly indicated that they learned skills and strategies to improve test-taking ability. For administrators, this indicates that first time in college developmental students have not developed strong skills or strategies to improve test taking ability. Administrators at 2-year institutions should continue to require developmental students to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester/quarter. This institutional practice will lead to success of developmental students.

Table 103.

Cross-Campus Comparison Engaged Learning

	Cyfair	Kingwood	Montgomer	NHarris	Tomball
Engaged Learning	56.58	55.13	55.03	58.26	56.52
Non Dev	34.41	32.75	24.19	42.41	32.54
Ask questions in class/contribute to class/discussions	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
Prepare two drafts of a paper/assignment before	2.23	NS	2.12	2.29	2.16
	2.02	NS	1.91	1.90	1.91
	Non Dev				

turning it in							
Participates	Developmen	1.45	NS	NS	NS	NS	
in	tal	1.28	NS	NS	NS	NS	
supplemental	Non Dev						
instruction							
Works with	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
other students	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
on	Non Dev						
projects/assign							
nment in class							
Works with	Developmen	NS	NS	2.32	NS	NS	
students	tal	NS	NS	2.52	NS	NS	
outside class	Non Dev						
on							
projects/assign							
nments							
Participates	Developmen	NS	NS	1.22	NS	1.25	
in required	tal	NS	NS	1.25	NS	1.19	
study group	Non Dev						
outside of							
class							
Participates	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
in student	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
initiated	Non Dev						
study group							
out of class							
(not required)							
Uses	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
electronic	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
tools to	Non Dev						
communicate							
with students							
about							
coursework							
Uses	Developmen	NS	2.03	NS	NS	NS	

electronic	tal	NS	2.14	NS	NS	NS
tools to	Non Dev					
communicate						
with						
instructors						
about						
coursework						
Discussed a	Developmen	2.03	NS	NS	NS	2.00
grade/assignme	tal	1.79	NS	NS	NS	1.78
nt with	Non Dev					
instructor						
Receive prompt	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	2.25
or written	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	2.12
feedback from	Non Dev					
instructors on						
your						
performance.						
Discussed	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
ideas from	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
readings/class	Non Dev					
with						
instructor out						
of class						
Frequency:	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	1.25
Face-to-face	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	1.24
tutoring	Non Dev					
Frequency:	Developmen	1.91	NS	NS	1.94	1.93
Use writing,	tal	1.45	NS	NS	1.57	1.45
math, or other	Non Dev					
skill						
Use computer	Developmen	2.49	NS	1.05	2.41	2.17
lab	tal	2.03	NS	.96	2.06	1.80
	Non Dev					
Ask for help	Developmen	2.29	NS	2.33	NS	2.34
from an	tal	2.09	NS	2.28	NS	2.17

|instructor |Non Dev | | | | |

|regarding | | | | | |

|questions/prob| | | | | |

|lems related | | | | | |

|to class | | | | | |

Cross-comparison for engaged learning is more likely to be reported by developmental students at the five colleges within the Lone Star College System. Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair, Lone Star College Montgomery, Lone Star College North Harris, and Lone Star College Tomball are more likely to report they prepare two drafts of a paper/assignment before turning it in. Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair are more likely to report participation in supplemental instruction.

Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students are more likely to report they work with students on projects/assignments in class. Lone Star College Montgomery developmental students and Lone Star College Tomball non-developmental students are more likely to report they participate in required study groups outside of class.

Lone Star College Kingwood's non-developmental students are more likely to report they use electronic tools to communicate with instructors about coursework. Lone Star College Cyfair and Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to report they discussed a grade/assignment with an instructor.

Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to receive prompt or written feedback from instructors on their performance.

At Lone Star College Cyfair, Lone Star College North Harris, and Lone Star College Tomball developmental students are more likely to use writing, math, or other skills. Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair, Lone Star College Montgomery, Lone Star College North Harris, and Lone Star College Tomball are more likely to report that they use the computer lab.

At Lone Star Colleges' Cyfair, Montgomery, and Tomball, developmental students are more likely to report they ask for help from an instructor regarding questions/problems related to the class.

Implications For Practice

The benchmark Engaged Learning was statistically significant for

				y		
Felt	Development	NS	NS	NS	NS	3.92
welcomed	al	NS	NS	NS	NS	3.71
1st visit	Non Dev					
Instructor	Development	NS	NS	NS	NS	4.31
wants me	al	NS	NS	NS	NS	4.13
to succeed	Non Dev					
Met with	Development	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
an advisor	al	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
at	Non Dev					
convenient						
times						
An advisor	Development	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
helped me	al	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
to select	Non Dev					
a course						
of study,						
program,						
or major						
Advisor	Development	NS	NS	NS	NS	3.18
helped set	al	NS	NS	NS	NS	2.84
academic	Non Dev					
goals						
Advisor	Development	3.55	3.99	NS	NS	3.87
helped	al	3.20	3.76	NS	NS	3.59
identify	Non Dev					
courses						
needed						
Staff	Development	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
discussed	al	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
commitment	Non Dev					
s outside						
of school						
All	Development	3.50	3.22	NS	3.26	3.31
instructor	al	3.07	2.94	NS	2.81	2.89

s had	Non Dev						
activities							
to							
introduce							
students							
to one							
another							
Instructor	Development	3.89	NS	NS	NS	NS	
s	al	3.54	NS	NS	NS	NS	
explained	Non Dev						
academic/s							
tudent							
support							
services							

In research question two, the institutional practices that were most statistically significant to developmental students cross-campus are all instructors had activities to introduce students to one another (except LSC Montgomery) and advisors helped identify courses needed (except LSC North Harris and LSC Montgomery).

There was not statistical significance at any of the five colleges within Lone Star College System in the following areas: Met with an advisor at convenient time, an advisor helped me to select a course of study, program or major, and staff discussed commitments outside of school.

Table 107

Cross-Campus Comparison For Institutional Practices

| |
		Cyfair	Kingwood	Montgomer	NHarris	Tomball	
				y			
Staff learned	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	2.94	
my name	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	2.67	
	Non Dev						
Students	Developmen	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
learned my	tal	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
name	Non Dev						
1 instructor	Developmen	4.33	NS	NS	4.20	NS	

learned my name	4.04	NS	NS	4.38	NS
Participates in supplemental instruction	1.45	NS	NS	1.50	
Discussed a grade/assignment with instructor	2.03	1.90	NS	NS	2.0
Received prompt written/oral feedback from instructor on performance	1.79	1.70	NS	NS	1.65

Cross-campus developmental students within Lone Star College System are more likely to report that they discussed a grade/assignment with an instructor, participated in supplemental instruction and one instructor learned my name. Non-developmental students at Lone Star College North Harris are more likely to report that one student learned their name. Lone Star College Cyfair and Lone Star College Tomball developmental students reported that they are more likely to participate in supplemental instruction. Lone Star College developmental students indicated significance in discussed a grade or assignment with an instructor. There was no statistical significance for developmental or non-developmental students in students learned my name and received prompt written, oral feedback from instructors on performance.

Table 108.

Cross-Campus Comparison of Institutional Practices within Lone Star College System (categorical)

Institutional Practice/	Cyfair	Kingwood	Montgomery	North	Tomball
				Harris	

Academic					
Support					
Initiative					
Online	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
orientation					
prior to					
class					
On campus	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
orientation					
Before	S	S	S	S	S
registration					
required					
placement					
test					
Took	S	S	S	S	S
placement					
test					
Exempt from	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
placement					
test					
During 1st	S	S	S	S	S
semester/qua					
rter					
enrolled					
into a					
specific					
course:					
College					
Success					
Enrolled 1st	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
semester in					
learning					
community					
Academic	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
advising/					

Planning					
Career	NS	NS	NS	S	NS
counseling					
Job	NS	NS	NS	NS	S
placement					
Face to face	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
tutoring					
Online	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
tutoring					
Assigned	S	S	NS	NS	S
person for					
needed					
information					

Implications For Practice

Table 108 implies developmental students are more likely to have statistical significance in the institutional practices that include practices that are mandatory prior to enrolling in their first semester of college. Imposing developmental students to take placement tests and courses based on their placement tests scores ultimately leads to their success. The student success courses teach developmental students the fundamental skills necessary for success while enrolled in college.

In addition, the institutional practice of assigning a person for needed information is significant for developmental students.

Developmental students in this study have proven to be influenced by socialization. Having one person to contact for needed information about the 2-year institution or other offerings at the college may increase retention of students. One contact person may decrease the delay in information, inaccuracies in information, and may build a strong amount of trust for administrators/instructors.

Findings

The institutional practice or academic support initiatives that demonstrated the most significance for developmental students were before registration they were required to take a placement test, they took a placement test, the college required them to enroll in classes indicated by their placement test scores during their first semester/quarter, and during

their first semester they were required to enroll into a specific course: college success (table 109, table 110). Having an assigned person for needed information was significant for developmental students at three of the five colleges within Lone Star College System.

Table 109.

Overall Cross-Campus Significance in Institutional Practices/Academic Support Initiatives for Developmental Students

Item Description	Significance
Before registration	Yes
required placement test	
Took a placement test	Yes
(COMPLASS, ASSET	
ACCUPLACER, SAT, ACT,	
etc.)	
I was exempt from taking	Yes
a placement test at this	
college.	
This college required me	Yes
to enroll in classes	
indicated by my	
placement test scores.	

This table reflects the institutional practices that are most significant for developmental students in this study.

Table 110.

Overall Cross-Campus Significance in Institutional Practices/Academic Support Initiatives for Developmental Students: Four Out of Five Campuses

Item Description	College with	College with no
	significance	significance
LSC Cyfair		
All instructors	LSC Kingwood	LSC Montgomery
had activities to	LSC North Harris	
introduce students	LSC Tomball	
to one another		

Developmental students at four of the five colleges within Lone Star College System were more likely to report that all instructors had

activities to introduce students to one another.

Table 111.

Institutional Practices/Academic Support Initiatives Significance

Overall Cross-Campus Significance in Institutional Practices/Academic Support Initiatives for Developmental Students: Three Out of Five Campuses

Item Description	College with	College with no
Assigned person for needed information	LSC Cyfair	LSC Montgomery
Advisor helped identify courses needed	LSC Kingwood	LSC North Harris
	LSC Tomball	

Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair, Kingwood, and Tomball were more likely to report having an assigned person for needed information. Developmental students at Lone Star College Cyfair, Kingwood, and Tomball were more likely to report an advisor helped identify courses needed.

Table 112.

Overall Cross-Campus Non Significance in Institutional Practices/Academic Initiatives for Developmental students (Scaled)

Met with an advisor at convenient times
An advisor helped me to select a course of study, program, or major.
Staff discussed commitments outside of school.
One other student learned my name.
Received prompt written, oral feedback from an instructor on my performance.
Online orientation prior to class.
On campus orientation.
Enrolled first semester in a learning community.
Academic advising/planning
Face to face tutoring
Online tutoring

The table above reflects no significance in institutional practices or

academic support initiatives for students at this 2-year institution. This table may be useful for administrators interested in altering administrative practices that are not significantly beneficial when used at large suburban 2-year institutions. This table in no way suggests these practices are not significant or eliminated, but for these students at this system these practices were not significant. Many of these practices are traditionally offered at 2-year institutions and can be altered to meet the needs of developmental students based on each college's need and or available resources.

This concludes the analysis from the 2009 SENSE survey for research questions #1 and #2. Chapter five provides further review of the findings.

Chapter Five: Conclusions and Recommendations

Introduction

The purpose of this study was to explore the differences in engagement levels between first time in college developmental students and non-developmental students and to determine what institutional practices or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in 2-year institutions utilizing the 2009 Survey of Entering Student Engagement (SENSE).

The preceding chapters introduced the purpose of the study, the literature review, the methodology, and the findings from the statistical analyses performed in 2009 using the SENSE survey. This chapter contains conclusions and recommendations for educational leaders and instructors from the statistical analysis reported in chapter four.

There are a few limitations placed on this study. First, the data employed in this study to answer research questions one and two were limited to results from the 2009 SENSE survey for Lone Star College System and the five colleges that encompass that system. Consequently, the encounters of the participants in this survey may not signify the experiences of all first time in college developmental or non-developmental students locally, nationally, or internationally. The study also captures the experiences of these community college students in the first few weeks of their first semester in college. Also, the SENSE survey examined the experiences of students enrolled in 2-year institutions and not 4-year institutions or for profit institutions.

Study Summary

To delve into the variation in engagement levels between first time in college developmental and non-developmental students the researcher used the 2009 SENSE survey to compare and contrast the two groups using a quantitative methodology. This study focused on analyzing engagement levels of developmental and non-developmental students using the six SENSE benchmarks: Early Connections, High Expectations and Aspirations, Clear Academic Plan and Pathway, Effective Track to College Readiness, Engaged Learning, and Academic and Social Support Network. Thorough assessment between the two groups was performed.

Research question #1: Are there significant differences in the engagement levels among first year developmental education students versus first year non-developmental college students within 2-year institutions?

This question was answered by analyzing data for the following six SENSE benchmarks within the five colleges at Lone Star College System: Early Connections, High Expectations and Aspirations, Clear Academic Plan and Pathway, Effective Track to College Readiness, Engaged Learning, and Academic and Social Support Network. Major findings for question one are below.

Research question #2: What institutional practices or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in two-year institutions?

This research question was answered by analyzing all questions in the 2009 SENSE Survey that indicated an institutional practice or practices that support academics. The following questions were examined to determine which institutional practice or academic support initiatives support developmental students' engagement in 2-year institutions.

Table 113.

Research Variables

Variable #	Item Description/ Variable Name
------------	---------------------------------

ONLORIEN	111a	I took part in an online orientation program prior to the beginning of classes.
----------	------	---

ONLORIEN	111a	I took part in an online orientation program prior to the beginning of classes.
----------	------	---

ONCORIEN	111b	I attended an on-campus orientation program prior to the beginning of classes.
----------	------	--

CSORIEN	11c	I enrolled in an orientation course as part of my
	course schedule during my first semester/quarter at	
	this college.	

REQPTEST	12a	Before I could register for classes I was required
	to take a placement test to assess my reading,	
	writing, math skills	

|TKPTEST |12b |I took a placement test (COMPASS, ASSES, ACCUPLACER,|
| |SAT, ACT, etc) |

|EXPTEST |12c |I was exempt from taking a placement test at this |
| |college. |

REQCLASS	14	This college required me to enroll in classes
	indicated by my placement test scores during my	
	FIRST SEMESTER/ QUARTER.	

ENRLSSDC	17e	In which of the following types of courses were you
	enrolled during your FIRST SEMESTER/QUARTER at this	
	college? A course	
	specifically designed to teach skills and strategies	
	to help students succeed in college (e.g. a college	
	success or student course)	

ENRLOLC	17f	In which of the following types of courses were you
	enrolled during your FIRST SEMESTER/QUARTER at this	
	college?	
	An organized "learning community" (two or more	
	courses that a group of students take together)	

|WELCOME |18a |The very first time I came to this college I felt |
| |welcome. |

|WNTSCCD | 18b|The instructors at this college want me to succeed. |

|AACONTIM |18d |I was able to meet with an academic advisor at times|
| |convenient for me. |

|AASELMAJ |18e |An advisor helped me to select a course of study, |
| |program, or major. |

|ACADGOAL |18f |An advisor helped me to set academic goals and to |
| |create a plan for achieving them. |

|CRSADV |18g |An advisor helped me identify the courses I needed |
| |to take during my first semester/quarter. |

OSCOMM	18h	A college staff member talked with me about my
		commitments outside of schoolwork, children,
		dependents, etc.) to help me figure out the number
		of courses to take.

|ACTINTRO |18k |All instructors had activities to introduce students|
| | |to one another. |

|RESOURCE |18L |All instructors clearly explained academic and |
| | |student support services available at this college. |

|CSTAFNAM |18P |At least one college staff member (other than an |
| | |instructor) learned my name. |

|FACNAM |18r |At least one instructor learned my name. |

SUPINSTR	19e	Participate in supplemental instruction (extra class
		sessions with an instructor tutor, or experienced
		student)

|FACASSN |19m |Discuss an assignment or grade with an instructor |

|FEEDBACK |19o |Receive prompt written or oral feedback from |
| | |instructors on your performance. |

|ACADPLN |20a | |

|CAREERC |20b |Career Counseling |

|JOBPLACE |20c |Job placement assistance |

|FFTUTOR |20d |Face-to-face tutoring |

|OLTUTOR |20e |Online tutoring |

ASNERS	23	Was a specific person assigned to you so you could
		see him/her each time you needed information or
		assistance.

| | |

Traditional/Non-Traditional Age versus Gender in Developmental Students

“Community colleges enroll over half of all beginning public postsecondary students including disproportionate numbers of adult, first generation, low income, and other underrepresented subpopulations” (Schuetz & Barr, 2008, p. 17). With this knowledge, the researcher explored age and gender. Further analysis of the six SENSE Benchmarks within developmental students at Lone Star College Systems indicated that there may be additional reasons that sustain engagement levels within this population (see table 105). There is variation in traditional (younger) students

versus non-traditional (older) students. There is also disparity in gender when comparing female developmental students to male developmental students.

The following tables of data analyzed indicate that non-traditional (older) students that are female are more likely to report engagement in the six benchmarks than traditional (younger) female or male students. Older male students were more likely to report slight engagement in the benchmark areas of Early Connections and Academic and Social Network. Within traditional (younger) students, developmental female students were slightly more engaged than developmental male students. Traditional (younger) male students indicated engagement in the benchmarks Early Connections, Effective Track for College Readiness, and Clear Academic Plan and Pathway.

Table 114.

Developmental/Non-Developmental for Traditional Age/Non-Traditional Age and Gender Students

Benchmark	Younger	Female	Description
	Older	Male	
Tomball	Tomball	Overall, developmental students	at LSC Tomball are more engaged than their non-developmental peers.
Early Connections	2.8	2.6	Among developmental students, it appears that younger students and men are slightly more engaged, though statistical significance has not been determined.
High Expectations and Aspirations	NS	NS	Not significant at this college
Clear Academic Plan and Pathway	3.0	1.3	Among developmental students, it appears that older students and females are slightly more

Pathway			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined.
Effective	-	-	Among developmental students, it
Track for	.2	2.6	appears that younger students and
College			female are slightly more engaged,
Readiness			though statistical significance
			has not been determined.
Engaged	-	-	Among developmental students, it
Learning	-1.7	1.3	appears that younger students and
			female are slightly more engaged,
			though statistical significance
			has not been determined.
Academic	NS	NS	Not significant at this college
and			
Social			
Network			

At Lone Star College Tomball traditional developmental students that are female are more likely to significantly report engagement in the five out of the six SENSE benchmarks.

Table 115.

Developmental/Non-Developmental for Traditional Age/Non-Traditional Age and Gender Students

Benchmark	Younger	Female-	Description
	-Older	Male	
	Cyfair	Cyfair	Overall, developmental students
			at LSC Cyfair are as engaged as
			their non-developmental peers.
Early	NS	NS	Not significant at this college.
Connection			
s			
High	NS	NS	Not significant at this college.
Expectatio			
ns and			
Aspiration			

|s | | | |

|Clear |NS |NS |Not significant at this college.|

|Academic | | | |

|Plan and | | | |

|Pathway | | | |

|Effective |+ |- |Among developmental students, it|

|Track for |2.0 |.07 |appears that younger students |

|College | | |and male are slightly more |

|Readiness | | |engaged, though statistical |

| | | |significance has not been |

| | | |determined. |

|Engaged |- |+ |Among developmental students, it|

|Learning |8.1 |1.4 |appears that older students and |

| | | |female are slightly more |

| | | |engaged, though statistical |

| | | |significance has not been |

| | | |determined. |

|Academic |- |- |Among developmental students, it|

|and Social|4.5 |0.4 |appears that older students and |

|Network | | |male are slightly more engaged, |

| | | |though statistical significance |

| | | |has not been determined. |

At Lone Star College Cyfair non-traditional male and female developmental students are more likely to significantly report engagement in three out of the six SENSE benchmarks.

Table 116.

Developmental/Non-Developmental for Traditional Age/Non-Traditional Age and Gender Students

|Benchmark |Younger-|Female-M|Description |

| |Older |ale | |

| |Kingwood|Kingwood|Overall, developmental students |

| | | |at LSC Kingwood are as engaged |

| | | |as their non-developmental |

| | | |peers. |

|Early |- |- |Among developmental students, it|

Connection	9.3	4.1	appears that older students and
s			males are slightly more engaged,
			though statistical significance
			has not been determined
High	NS	NS	Not significant at this college.
Expectatio			
ns and			
Aspiration			
s			
Clear	NS	NS	Not significant at this college.
Academic			
Plan and			
Pathway			
Effective	+	-	Among developmental students, it
Track for	1.6	3.2	appears that younger students
College			and females are slightly more
Readiness			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined
Engaged	-	+	Among developmental students, it
Learning	8.9	1.5	appears that older students and
			female are slightly more
			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined
Academic	NS	NS	Not significant at this college.
and Social			
Network			

At Lone Star College Kingwood non-traditional male and female students are more likely to report significance in three out of the six SENSE benchmarks.

Table 117.

Developmental/Non-Developmental for Traditional Age/Non-Traditional Age and Gender Students

|Benchmark |Younger-OI|Female-Mal|Description |

	der	e	
	Montgomery	Montgomery	Overall, developmental students
			at LSC Montgomery are as
			engaged as their
			non-developmental peers.
Early	NS	NS	Not significant at this
Connection			college.
s			
High	NS	NS	Not significant at this
Expectatio			college.
ns and			
Aspiration			
s			
Clear	+	+	Among developmental students,
Academic	4.6	1.3	it appears that younger
Plan and			students and females are
Pathway			slightly more engaged, though
			statistical significance has
			not been determined
Effective	+	+	Among developmental students,
Track for	5.8	.3	it appears that younger
College			students and females are
Readiness			slightly more engaged, though
			statistical significance has
			not been determined
Engaged	-	+	Among developmental students,
Learning	3.9	6.7	it appears that older students
			and females are slightly more
			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined
Academic	NS	NS	Not significant at this
and Social			college.
Network			
At Lone Star College Montgomery traditional female developmental students

are more likely to report significance in three out of the six SENSE benchmarks.

Table 118.

Developmental/Non-Developmental for Traditional Age/Non-Traditional Age and Gender Students

Benchmark	Younger	Female	Description
	Older	Male	
North	North	Overall	developmental students
Harris	Harris	at LSC North Harris	are as
			engaged as their
			non-developmental peers.
Early	NS	NS	Not significant at this college.
Connection			
High	-	+	Among developmental students, it
Expectatio	10.2	70	appears that older students and
ns and			females are slightly more
Aspiration			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined
Clear	+	-	Among developmental students, it
Academic	2.1	5.9	appears that younger students
Plan and			and males are slightly more
Pathway			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined
Effective	+	+	Among developmental students, it
Track for	3.8	2.4	appears that older students and
College			females are slightly more
Readiness			engaged, though statistical
			significance has not been
			determined
Engaged	-	+	Among developmental students, it
Learning	7.0	2.3	appears that older students and
			females are slightly more

||| |engaged, though statistical |

||| |significance has not been |

||| |determined |

|Academic |NS |NS |Not significant at this college.|

|and Social| |||

|Network| |||

At Lone Star College North Harris non-traditional female students are more likely to report significance in four out of the six SENSE benchmarks.

The tables for traditional versus non-traditional developmental students who are male versus female reflect significantly for females. The suggested recommendations are discussed in the recommendations section.

Recommendations

Increased socialization. Astin's (1999) Student Development Theory supports college persistence and describes the emotional and physical drive that students apply towards their education. The learner's learning is enhanced by the rigor dedicated to his or her academic career. The student's academic development is enhanced by academic support programs and interaction. Astin's theory supports the idea that students with high levels of involvement in studying, extracurricular activities, and constant interaction with faculty are prone to persist farther educationally than students who do not participate in the same activities.

According to the results from this survey, the researcher strongly suggests that this system of colleges support institutional practices that focus on socialization between students and staff for developmental and non-developmental students. Enforcing communication between students inside or outside the classroom appears to be significant to students as they engage themselves to the campus and courses. Under the assumption that engagement between students leads to increased involvement in class assignments, campus activities, and general information, socialization may be key to engaging the student. Suggested socialization within the classroom may include icebreaker activities at the start of the semester, in class group discussions throughout the semester, or assigned group activities outside of class. Outside of class assignments will encourage students to make initial contact with other students within their class, obtain contact information of those students, and increase socialization about course work

outside of class.

Vincent Tinto's (1987) Interactionist theory of student persistence and retention suggests the community college student is similar to a melting pot of diversity. The theory supports the idea that each student arrives to college with an array of academic, cultural, and social backgrounds. The theory explains the reasons why some students succeed scholastically where other students do not. The cultural differences between students can also be a strong factor that alters student persistence. Tinto further documented that academic and social integration for the student with the institution occurs through educational and social communities on the campus.

Male and female initiatives. The researcher suggests implementation of male and female support groups, clubs, or programs that support the male and female college student. The data analyzed on traditional and non-traditional students reflects a growing number of male students that significantly reported engagement in several of the SENSE benchmarks (see tables 114, 115, 116, 118). Traditional males reported significance in Early Connections, Effective Track for College Readiness, and Clear and Academic Pathway. Though women currently outnumber men within 2-year institutions it is vital to support the males that are attending college.

Initiatives such as African American or Hispanic based can provide the mentorship, guidance, and academic support needed to retain these students through their academic careers. Adding support for Veterans specifically in counseling, advising, and financial aid may target the non-traditional older male population that is growing within 2-year institutions.

Non-traditional females reported the most significance in the SENSE benchmarks. This may reflect the interest in older women returning to college to seek education post-children, a desire to change careers, or the effects of the current economic recession. Either or, this population may need non-traditional services within their community college. The researcher recommends low cost daycare, individual and group counseling services, as well as support groups or clubs for older female students. Support groups for this population will assist them with transition back into the classroom, support of their families while they pursue their education, as well as provide them with training on the newest

technological tools used academically within the classroom without anxiety. Increase use of electronic tools. Developmental students may need additional encouragement to utilize electronic tools in and out of the classroom. Some developmental students are proficient and use electronic tools often while others have not ever used electronic tools due to lack of access within their home or previous institution. Assigning assignments that must be typed or presented visually may increase the number of developmental students that use computers, etc. to complete assignments. On occasion, instructors may want to utilize computer labs on their campus to engage students electronically. Instructors can assist students technologically by including websites or programs in their lectures that can be searched during class on a computer. Allowing class time provides practice and comfort in seeking assistance if needed. For example, schedule a lab for your class and allow a librarian to visit the class and review useful websites to do research, write papers, or answer any questions they may have. At University Park, a satellite campus of Lone Star College Tomball, the sociology instructors utilize movies via the library. They create assignments with questions that come from the assigned movie. Each student must view the movie out of class, answer the questions thoughtfully, and turn the assignment in.

As campuses are becoming bookless and utilizing books online, this may be an ideal opportunity to engage students electronically while exposing them to countless electronic resources. Allowing hands on activities during and out of class may encourage developmental students to utilize electronic tools while enrolled in courses at the 2-year institution.

Tinto's Integration Model (1987) suggests that institutions of higher learning that incorporate the academic environment with the extracurricular interests of its students have a better chance of retaining those students.

This model says that students involved in both entities increase their chances of staying in college, which in return increases the colleges overall retention rates. Tinto developed a model that incorporates the significance of engagement activities and academics. The model links the formal and informal aspects of college that are essential in success of college students.

In addition, there are many social networking sites that can be tied

into a course. Twitter or Facebook are growing resources that can be used academically. For example, Twitter can be used in a sociology course to engage students on world topics that occur daily. Providing extra credit to students who use this system to communicate with the instructor and others can be engaging. Facebook can be used for students to organize their presentations outside of class. For convenience purposes students can discuss topics, ideas, and responsibilities for assignments assigned by the instructor.

Utilize class time. A recommendation to solve the high number of students who turn in assignments late is to clearly review assignments during class time. Instructors can further assist students by allowing them to ask questions regarding the assignment rather than be unclear about the requirements of the assignment when they attempt it outside of class time. This allows ample opportunity to complete the assignment while impressing on the student the importance of the assignment. Discussing the assignment during class time may also encourage students to socialize with one another and discuss the assignment further.

Student success courses. The researcher recommends implementation of student success courses for students who place in developmental courses. The results from this survey indicate developmental students lack fundamental skills needed to obtain academic achievement for a variety of reasons. A student success course will provide the opportunity for developmental students to learn the fundamentals needed to be successful at the college. Student success courses should include a component on goal setting, time management, and a review of various study techniques.

Goal setting will teach students how to prepare for the future by setting realistic goals and an effective plan to achieve them. This can be reviewed with an academic advisor for school or real life examples can be used to help students make better use of their time. Being that community college students are non-traditional students with ample responsibilities out of the classroom, goal setting will allow them to see the importance of planning and executing effectively.

A student success course that facilitates identifying strengths and weaknesses will assist students who are unclear in the most effective study habits that benefit them. For example, a student success course that

teaches how to read assigned material, highlight key points, and study those key points may be needed for students who are not clear on this technique.

Discuss grades. The researcher recommends discussing grades with developmental and non-developmental students by the next class meeting. Full time and part time faculty that provide examinations to students should grade them, return them, and provide an opportunity to discuss those grades. Instead of waiting for a student to schedule office time with you, you schedule office time with them. As enrollments increase, so do the need for part time faculty to teach more courses. All too often adjunct faculty return exams without providing students the opportunity to discuss their scores. Departmental leaders may want to look into opportunities to provide locations for part time faculty to meet with students privately to discuss their grades. If space is an issue at the college, perhaps utilizing social network tools such as Skype (free webcam conferencing) may allow flexible times for the instructor and the student to discuss grades. This recommendation covers several areas: socialization, use of electronic tools, engagement, and teaching and learning.

Mentor programs. Previous research has shown that intervention may lead to prevention for future students. A majority of first-time freshmen are considerably older and have not been in a classroom in a long time; they don't have the skills they need to succeed at college-level work without intervention (Roueche & Roueche, 1999). "Community colleges have a particularly important role. They educate the most deficient students and prepare them for employment and personal advancement" (McCabe, 2000, p. 13). This validates the necessity for intercession in developmental education for all ages and skill levels of college students.

Assign a person for needed information. This researcher recommends assigning a specific person to each student. This area was statistically significant for both developmental and non-developmental students (see chapter four). Most campuses utilize advisors or counselors to provide valuable information to students. But with growing enrollments these individuals are overwhelmed. "As is typical in a recession, many community colleges are experiencing a surge in enrollment, at precisely the same time that they must-like many enterprises, both public and private-contend with

choking constraints on resources” (McClenney, 2009, p. 1). With this in mind, 2-year institutions should look into creative ways to utilize all the manpower that is available. The researcher recommends utilizing all members of the department that work towards student success. At the discretion of the departmental administrator, employees trained to provide accurate student information can be assigned a specific person for needed information. An example of employees to utilize can be admission advisors, recruiters, or financial aid staff. This will free up advisors to assist students with pertinent college related issues while providing the one on one attention a student may be needing. This suggested practice is commonly used at for profit institutions with much success. There may be resistance with this practice. A different way to think of this practice is that the employees all work towards student success in their individual departments, employing this recommendation may make student success the job of everyone at the college.

Virtual advisor. Continuing with the recommendation of assigning a person for needed information, the researcher suggests a virtual advisor. A virtual advisor may be a cost effective way to provide students with the linkage they need to answer immediate questions they may have. This resource links students electronically and socially and may ultimately increase the persistence of students. The Creative Community College: Leading Change Through Innovation (2008) noted some certainties for colleges:

- Technology will enable and significantly improve faculty/student engagement. Soon, teachers and learning objects will virtually appear in three dimensions wherever and whenever students need. Education will continue to be increasingly mobile. (Roueche et al., p. 253)

A virtual advisor is an innovative and cost effective way to provide information to students without the cost of an onsite advisor. For colleges having difficulties providing office space to accommodate advisors and students that are waiting to see the advisors, this may be one of many space saving solutions.

Recommendations For Future Research

Mandatory student success course. A recommendation for future

research is to employ mandatory comprehensive student success courses for developmental students. Analysis of the engagement levels of developmental students who are enrolled in two or more developmental courses and are enrolled in student success courses versus developmental students who placed in two or more developmental courses but do not have to complete a student success course may reveal the necessity of mandatory student success courses within 2-year institutions. A comparison of their levels of engagement and performance may provide institutions with data to utilize this practice in the future.

Non-traditional students: Motivation. An additional recommendation for future research is to study non-traditional female and male students. This study revealed that non-traditional female students were more likely to significantly report engagement than traditional students within the six SENSE benchmarks (see table 115). To capitalize on their levels of engagement, additional research is needed to discover specifically where their engagement levels are the highest and uncover the source of their motivation. Non-traditional students tend to display qualities conducive to retention such as to contribute more to class and ask questions.

Research should further delve in these areas to uncover the source of their motivation. A study of this nature can increase the knowledge of retention and persistence of non-traditional female and male students.

Advisor to student ratios. This study revealed that developmental students are more likely to report engagement when assigned one person for information. The rise in enrollment within 2-year institutions may directly affect the quality of academic advising that is offered to developmental and non-developmental students. The researcher recommends low advisor to student ratios to increase the quality of service being offered to the student. To keep this ratio low, administrators should consider hiring and training virtual advisors to meet with students at their convenience or by way of social networking tools of communication.

Summary

The SENSE survey has accumulated statistical facts to support the student success needs of entering students into the college while providing administrators, faculty, and staff with numerical feedback on how to improve their experiences. Two-year institutions that side with the voice

of the student may be eager to use this survey to realign their administrative or academic support initiatives based on the results. In sum, administrative leadership within 2-year institutions should use this survey during the first college semester of their developmental and non-developmental students' educational careers. The SENSE survey provides answers to the many questions from administrators and faculty about the student population in which they serve. Having an open door policy for a student to come to speak with you in your office is no longer the way to obtain the true experiences from students. Strong surveys and thorough data analysis is the approach to solve the riddle of student engagement. Key input is provided from both developmental and non-developmental students based on various variables that determine their engagement at the college. The researcher strongly urges administrators and faculty to consider utilizing the SENSE survey.

Overall, engaging developmental and non-developmental students will take a team effort. The success of a student is not the responsibility of the student success division solely. It is the responsibility of every employee at the college. We can never underestimate who may motivate or encourage a student based on their title alone. Student success for developmental and non-developmental students is contingent on individuals that think and work outside of the box, color outside of the lines, and use data tools to benefit this generation of college students.

APPENDIX A

SENSE SURVEY

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APPENDIX B

SENSE CODEBOOK

|Item #|Variable |Item Description/Variable Label|Response Value |

| |Name | | |

|Please note the following for the SENSE data set: Invalid responses |
|are coded as missing “.” |

| |SURVEYNO |Survey Number | |

|1 |SRVAGAIN |Have you taken this survey in |1= Yes |

| | |another class THIS |2= No |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER? | |

|2 |ENRLMENT |Thinking about THIS |1= Less than |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER, how would you|Full-time |

| | |describe your enrollment at |2= Full-time |

| | |this college? | |

|3 |ENTER |Did you begin college at this |1= Started here |

| | |college or elsewhere? |2= Started |

| | |elsewhere |

|4 |The following statements are about whether a student earned |

| |college credit for one or more questions while in high school.|

| |This question asks students to select all options that apply. |

| |To permit multiple responses, the question is represented in |

| |the codebook by four separate items the student either checks |

| |or does not check. |

|4a |NOHS |While in high school, did you |0= No Response |

| | |learn college credit for one or |1= Response |

| | |more courses? No | |

|4b |THISC |While in high school, did you |0= No Response |

| | |learn college credit for one or |1= Response |

| | |more courses? Yes, at this | |

| | |college | |

|4c |DIFFC |While in high school, did you |0= No Response |

| | |learn college credit for one or |1= Response |

| | |more courses? Yes, at a | |

| | |different college | |

|4d |MYHS |While in high school, did you |0= No Response |

| | |learn college credit for one or |1= Response |

| | |more courses? Yes, at my high | |

| | |school | |

|5 |OTHERENR |In addition to taking courses |1= Yes |

| | |at this college, were/are you |2= No |

| | |also enrolled at a 4-year | |

| | |college or university during | |

| | |YOUR FIRST SEMESTER/QUARTER? | |

|6 |TERMSENR |How many semesters/quarters |1= This is my |

| | |have you been enrolled at this |first |

| | |college? |semester/quarter |

| | |2= This is my |

| | |second |

| | |semester/quarter |

| | |3= This is my |

| | |third |

| | |semester/quarter |

| | |4= This is my |

| | |fourth |

| | |semester/quarter |

| | |5= I have been |

| | |enrolled more than|

| | |four |

| | |semesters/quarters|

|7 |COURSENO |How many courses did you enroll|1= 1 course |

| | |in for YOUR FIRST |2= 2 courses |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER at this |3= 3 courses |

| | |college? |4= 4 courses or |

| | |more |

|8 |ADDROP |Did you add or drop any classes|1= Yes, without |

| | |within the FIRST THREE WEEKS OF|discussing my |

| | |YOUR FIRST SEMESTER/QUARTER at |decision with a |

| | |this college? |college staff |

| | |member or |

| | |instructor |

| | |2= Yes, after |

| | |discussing my |

| | |decision with a |

		college staff	
		member or	
		instructor	
		3= No, I did not	
		add or drop any	
		courses	
9	DROPN0	Of the courses you enrolled in	1= None
		during YOUR FIRST	2= 1 course
		SEMESTER/QUARTER at this	3= 2 courses
		college, how many did you drop	4= 3 courses
		after the first day of class	5= 4 courses or
		and before the end of the term?	more
10	REGCLASS	When did you register for your	1= More than one
		courses for YOUR FIRST	week before
		SEMESTER/QUARTER at this	classes began
		college?	2= During the week
		before classes	
		began	
		3= During the	
		first week of	
		classes	
		4= After the first	
		week of classes	
11	The following statements are about this college's orientation		
	program. This question asks students to select all options		
	that apply. To permit multiple responses, the question is		
	represented in the codebook by five separate items the student		
	either checks or does not check.		
11a	ONLORIEN	I took part in an online	0= No Response
	orientation program prior to	1= Response	
	the beginning of classes		
11b	ONCORIEN	I attended an on-campus	0= No Response
	orientation program prior to	1= Response	
	the beginning of classes		
11c	CSORIEN	I enrolled in an orientation	0= No Response

		course as part of my course	1= Response
		schedule during my first	
		semester/quarter at this	
		college	
11d	NWORIEN	I was not aware of a college	0= No Response
		orientation	1= Response
11e	UNAORIEN	I was unable to participate in	0= No Response
		the orientation due to	1= Response
		scheduling or other issues	
12a	REQPTEST	Before I could register for	1= Yes
		classes I was required to take	2= No
		a placement test (COMPASS,	
		ASSET, ACCUPLACER, SAT, ACT,	
		etc.) to assess my skills in	
		reading, writing, and/or math	
12b	TKPTEST	I took a placement test	1= Yes
		(COMPASS, ASSET, ACCUPLACER,	2= No
		SAT, ACT, etc.)	
12c	EXPTEST	I was exempt from taking a	1= Yes
		placement test at this college	2= No
13	The following statements are about whether a student's		
		placement test scores indicated he or she needed to take a	
		Developmental course. This question asks students to select	
		all options that apply. To permit multiple responses, the	
		question is represented in the codebook by five separate items	
		the student either checks or does not check.	
13a	NOTEST	My placement test scores	0= No Response
		indicated that I needed to take	1= Response
		a Developmental course (also	
		referred to as Basic Skills,	
		College Prep, etc.) in the	
		following areas: Didn't take a	
		placement test	
13b	NEEDREAD	My placement test scores	0= No Response
		indicated that I needed to take	1= Response

|| |a Developmental course (also ||

|| |referred to as Basic Skills, ||

|| |College Prep, etc.) in the ||

|| |following areas: Developmental| |

|| |reading ||

|13c |NEEDWRIT |My placement test scores |0= No Response |

|| |indicated that I needed to take|1= Response |

|| |a Developmental course (also ||

|| |referred to as Basic Skills, ||

|| |College Prep, etc.) in the ||

|| |following areas: Developmental| |

|| |writing ||

|13d |NEEDMATH |My placement test scores |0= No Response |

|| |indicated that I needed to take|1= Response |

|| |a Developmental course (also ||

|| |referred to as Basic Skills, ||

|| |College Prep, etc.) in the ||

|| |following areas: Developmental| |

|| |math ||

|13e |NEEDNONE |My placement test scores |0= No Response |

|| |indicated that I needed to take|1= Response |

|| |a Developmental course (also ||

|| |referred to as Basic Skills, ||

|| |College Prep, etc.) in the ||

|| |following areas: Didn't place ||

|| |into any Developmental courses ||

|14 |REQCLASS |This college required me to |1= Yes |

|| |enroll in classes indicated by |2= No |

|| |my placement test scores during| |

|| |my FIRST SEMESTER/QUARTER ||

|15a |APPLIED |I applied for financial |1= Yes |

|| |assistance (scholarships, |2= No |

|| |grants, or loans, etc.) ||

|15b |OFFERED |I was notified I was eligible |1= Yes |

|| |to receive financial assistance|2= No |

|(scholarships, grants, or |
|loans, etc.) |
|15c |RECEIVED |I received financial assistance|1= Yes |
|funds (scholarships, grants, or|2= No |
|loans, etc.) before classes |
|began |
|16 |TIMEAPPL |When did you first apply for |1= 3 or more |
|financial assistance |months before |
|classes began |
||2= 1 or 2 months |
|before classes |
||began |
||3= Less than 1 |
|month before |
|classes began |
	4= After classes
	began
	5= I did not apply
for financial	
assistance	
17a	EDCPR
of courses were you enrolled	2= Not Enrolled
during your FIRST	
SEMESTER/QUARTER at this	
college? Developmental Reading	
(also referred to as Basic	
Skills, College Prep, etc.)	
17b	EDCPW
of courses were you enrolled	2= Not Enrolled
during your FIRST	
SEMESTER/QUARTER at this	
college? Developmental	
Writing (also referred to as	
Basic Skills, College Prep,	
etc.)	

|17c |EDCPM |In which of the following types|1= Enrolled |

| | |of courses were you enrolled |2= Not Enrolled |

| | |during your FIRST | |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER at this | |

| | |college? Developmental Math | |

| | |(also referred to as Basic | |

| | |Skills, College Prep, etc.) | |

|17d |ENRLENG |In which of the following types|1= Enrolled |

| | |of courses were you enrolled |2= Not Enrolled |

| | |during your FIRST | |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER at this | |

| | |college? An English course | |

| | |taught specifically for | |

| | |students whose first language | |

| | |is not English (ESL, ESOL) | |

|17e |ENRLSSDC |In which of the following types|1= Enrolled |

| | |of courses were you enrolled |2= Not Enrolled |

| | |during your FIRST | |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER at this | |

| | |college? A course | |

| | |specifically designed to teach | |

| | |skills and strategies to help | |

| | |students succeed in college | |

| | |(e.g., a college success or | |

| | |student course) | |

|17f |ENRLOLC |In which of the following types|1= Enrolled |

| | |of courses were you enrolled |2= Not Enrolled |

| | |during your FIRST | |

| | |SEMESTER/QUARTER at this | |

| | |college? An organized | |

| | |"learning community" (two or | |

| | |more courses that a group of | |

| | |students take together) | |

|18a |WELCOME |The very first time I came to |1= Strongly |

| | |this college I felt welcome |Disagree |

||| 2= Disagree |

||| 3= No opinion |

||| 4= Agree |

||| 5= Strongly Agree |

|18b |WNTSCCD |The instructors at this college|1= Strongly |

|| |want me to succeed |Disagree |

||| 2= Disagree |

||| 3= No opinion |

||| 4= Agree |

||| 5= Strongly Agree |

|18c |CONVTIME |All the courses I needed to |1= Strongly |

|| |take during my first |Disagree |

|| |semester/quarter were available|2= Disagree |

|| |at times convenient for me |3= No opinion |

||| 4= Agree |

||| 5= Strongly Agree |

|18d |AACONTIM |I was able to meet with an |1= Strongly |

|| |academic advisor at times |Disagree |

|| |convenient for me |2= Disagree |

||| 3= No opinion |

||| 4= Agree |

||| 5= Strongly Agree |

|18e |AASELMAJ |An advisor helped me to select |1= Strongly |

|| |a course of study, program, or |Disagree |

|| |major |2= Disagree |

||| 3= No opinion |

||| 4= Agree |

||| 5= Strongly Agree |

|18f |ACADGOAL |An advisor helped me to set |1= Strongly |

|| |academic goals and to create a |Disagree |

|| |plan for achieving them |2= Disagree |

||| 3= No opinion |

||| 4= Agree |

||| 5= Strongly Agree |

|18g |CRSADV |An advisor helped me identify |1= Strongly |

		the courses I needed to take	Disagree
		during my first	2= Disagree
		semester/quarter	3= No opinion
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
18h	OSCOMM	A college staff member talked	1= Strongly
		with me about my commitments	Disagree
		outside of school (work,	2= Disagree
		children, dependents, etc.) to	3= No opinion
		help me figure out the number	4= Agree
		of courses to take	5= Strongly Agree
18i	FAINFO	The college provided me with	1= Strongly
		adequate information about	Disagree
		financial assistance	2= Disagree
		3= No opinion	
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
18j	QUALFA	A college staff member helped	1= Strongly
		me determine whether I	Disagree
		qualified for financial	2= Disagree
		assistance	3= No opinion
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
18k	ACTINTRO	All instructors had activities	1= Strongly
		to introduce students to one	Disagree
		another	2= Disagree
		3= No opinion	
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
18l	RESOURCE	All instructors clearly	1= Strongly
		explained academic and student	Disagree
		support services available at	2= Disagree
		this college	3= No opinion
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	

|18m |GRADEPOL |All instructors clearly |1= Strongly |

| | |explained course grading |Disagree |

| | |policies |2= Disagree |

| | | |3= No opinion |

| | | |4= Agree |

| | | |5= Strongly Agree |

|18n |SYLLABI |Instructors clearly explained |1= Strongly |

| | |course syllabi (syllabuses) |Disagree |

| | | |2= Disagree |

| | | |3= No opinion |

| | | |4= Agree |

| | | |5= Strongly Agree |

|18o |FACMEET |I knew how to get in touch with|1= Strongly |

| | |my instructors outside of class|Disagree |

| | | |2= Disagree |

| | | |3= No opinion |

| | | |4= Agree |

| | | |5= Strongly Agree |

|18p |CSTAFNAM |At least one college staff |1= Strongly |

| | |member (other than an |Disagree |

| | |instructor) learned my name |2= Disagree |

| | | |3= No opinion |

| | | |4= Agree |

| | | |5= Strongly Agree |

|18q |OSTUDNAM |At least one other student whom|1= Strongly |

| | |I did not previously know |Disagree |

| | |learned my name |2= Disagree |

| | | |3= No opinion |

| | | |4= Agree |

| | | |5= Strongly Agree |

|18r |FACNAM |At least one instructor learned|1= Strongly |

| | |my name |Disagree |

| | | |2= Disagree |

| | | |3= No opinion |

| | | |4= Agree |

		5= Strongly Agree	
18s	STUNAM	I learned the name of at least	1= Strongly
	one other student in most of my	Disagree	
	classes	2= Disagree	
		3= No opinion	
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
18t	ITTAKES	I have the motivation to do	1= Strongly
	what it takes to succeed in	Disagree	
	college	2= Disagree	
		3= No opinion	
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
18u	ACPRPRD	I am prepared academically to	1= Strongly
	succeed in college	Disagree	
		2= Disagree	
		3= No opinion	
		4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
19a	ASKQUES	Ask questions in class or	1= Never
	contribute to class discussions	2= Once	
		3= Two or three	
		times	
		4= Four or more	
		times	
19b	PREPDRFT	Prepare at least two drafts of	1= Never
	a paper or assignment before	2= Once	
	turning it in	3= Two or three	
		times	
		4= Four or more	
		times	
19c	LATETURN	Turn in an assignment late	1= Never
		2= Once	
		3= Two or three	
		times	

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | |times |

|19d |NOTTURN |Not turn in an assignment |1= Never |

| | | 2= Once |

| | | 3= Two or three |

| | | |times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | |times |

|19e |SUPINSTR |Participate in supplemental |1= Never |

| | |instruction (extra class |2= Once |

| | |sessions with an instructor |3= Two or three |

| | |tutor, or experienced student) |times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | |times |

|19f |NOTCOMPL |Come to class without |1= Never |

| | |completing readings or |2= Once |

| | |assignments |3= Two or three |

| | | |times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | |times |

|19g |PINCLASS |Work with other students on a |1= Never |

| | |project or assignment during |2= Once |

| | |class |3= Two or three |

| | | |times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | |times |

|19h |PREOUTC |Work with classmates outside of|1= Never |

| | |class on class projects or |2= Once |

| | |assignments |3= Two or three |

| | | |times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | |times |

|19i |GRPSTUDY |Participate in a required study|1= Never |

| | |group outside of class |2= Once |

| | | 3= Two or three |

			times
			4= Four or more
			times
19j	NRGSTUDY	Participate in a	1= Never
		student-initiated (not	2= Once
		required) study group outside	3= Two or three
		of class	times
			4= Four or more
			times
19k	USEINTMG	Use an electronic tool (e-mail,	1= Never
		text messaging, Facebook,	2= Once
		MySpace, class Web site, etc.)	3= Two or three
		to communicate with another	times
		student about coursework	4= Four or more
			times
19l	MAILFAC	Use an electronic tool (e-mail,	1= Never
		text messaging, Facebook,	2= Once
		MySpace, class Web site, etc.)	3= Two or three
		to communicate with an	times
		instructor about coursework	4= Four or more
			times
19m	FACASSN	Discuss an assignment or grade	1= Never
		with an instructor	2= Once
			3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more
			times
19n	CLASSREL	Ask for help from an instructor	1= Never
		regarding questions or problems	2= Once
		related to a class	3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more
			times
19o	FEEDBACK	Receive prompt written or oral	1= Never
		feedback from instructors on	2= Once

		your performance	3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more
			times
19p	RCVGRDS	Receive grades or points on	1= Never
		assignments, quizzes, tests, or	2= Once
		papers	3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more
			times
19q	FACIDOC	Discuss ideas from readings or	1= Never
		classes with instructors	2= Once
		outside of class	3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more
			times
19r	OCIDEAS	Discuss ideas from your	1= Never
		readings or classes with others	2= Once
		outside of class (students,	3= Two or three
		family, co-workers, etc.)	times
			4= Four or more
			times
19s	SKIPCL	Skip class	1= Never
			2= Once
			3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more
			times
20a1	ACADPLNG	Academic advising/planning	1= Yes
			2= No
20a2	ACADPUSE	Frequency: Academic	1= Never
		advising/planning	2= Once
			3= Two or three
			times
			4= Four or more

|| |times |

|20a3 |ACADPSAT |Satisfaction: Academic |0= Not applicable |

|| |advising/planning |1= Not at all |

|| |2= Somewhat |

|| |3= Very |

|20b1 |CAREERC |Career Counseling |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|20b2 |CARCUSE |Frequency: Career Counseling |1= Never |

|| |2= Once |

|| |3= Two or three |

|| |times |

|| |4= Four or more |

|| |times |

|20b3 |CARCSAT |Satisfaction: Career Counseling|0= Not applicable |

|| |1= Not at all |

|| |2= Somewhat |

|| |3= Very |

|20c1 |JOBPLACE |Job placement assistance |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|20c2 |JOBPLUSE |Frequency: Job placement |1= Never |

|| |assistance |2= Once |

|| |3= Two or three |

|| |times |

|| |4= Four or more |

|| |times |

|20c3 |JOBPLSAT |Satisfaction: Job placement |0= Not applicable |

|| |assistance |1= Not at all |

|| |2= Somewhat |

|| |3= Very |

|20d1 |FFTUTOR |Face-to-face tutoring |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|20d2 |FFTUSE |Frequency: Face-to-face |1= Never |

|| |tutoring |2= Once |

|| |3= Two or three |

|| |times |

||| 4= Four or more |

||| |times |

|20d3 |FFTSAT |Satisfaction: Face-to-face |0= Not applicable |

|| |tutoring |1= Not at all |

||| 2= Somewhat |

||| 3= Very |

|20e1 |OLTUTOR |Online tutoring |1= Yes |

||| 2= No |

|20e2 |OLTUSE |Frequency: Online tutoring |1= Never |

||| 2= Once |

||| 3= Two or three |

||| |times |

||| 4= Four or more |

||| |times |

|20e3 |OLTSAT |Satisfaction: Online tutoring |0= Not applicable |

||| 1= Not at all |

||| 2= Somewhat |

||| 3= Very |

|20f1 |SKILLABS |Writing, math, or other skill |1= Yes |

|| |lab |2= No |

|20f2 |SKLABUSE |Frequency: Writing, math, or |1= Never |

|| |other skill lab |2= Once |

||| 3= Two or three |

||| |times |

||| 4= Four or more |

||| |times |

|20f3 |SKLBSAT |Satisfaction: Writing, math, or |0= Not applicable |

|| |other skill lab |1= Not at all |

||| 2= Somewhat |

||| 3= Very |

|20g1 |FAADVS |Financial assistance advising |1= Yes |

||| 2= No |

|20g2 |FAUSE |Frequency: Financial assistance |1= Never |

|| |advising |2= Once |

||| 3= Two or three |

|| |times |

|| |4= Four or more |

|| |times |

|20g3 |FAADVSAT |Satisfaction: Financial |0= Not applicable |

|| |assistance advising |1= Not at all |

|| |2= Somewhat |

|| |3= Very |

|20h1 |COMPLAB |Computer lab |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|20h2 |COMLBUSE |Frequency: Computer lab |1= Never |

|| |2= Once |

|| |3= Two or three |

|| |times |

|| |4= Four or more |

|| |times |

|20h3 |COMLBSAT |Satisfaction: Computer lab |0= Not applicable |

|| |1= Not at all |

|| |2= Somewhat |

|| |3= Very |

|20i1 |STUORGS |Student organizations |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|20i2 |STORGUSE |Frequency: Student |1= Never |

|| |organizations |2= Once |

|| |3= Two or three |

|| |times |

|| |4= Four or more |

|| |times |

|20i3 |STORGSAT |Satisfaction: Student |0= Not applicable |

|| |organizations |1= Not at all |

|| |2= Somewhat |

|| |3= Very |

|20j1 |TRANSFCR |Transfer credit assistance |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|20j2 |TRNFCRAS |Frequency: Transfer credit |1= Never |

|| |assistance |2= Once |

| | | 3= Two or three |

| | | times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | times |

|20j3 |TRCRASAT |Satisfaction: Transfer credit |0= Not applicable |

| | assistance |1= Not at all |

| | | 2= Somewhat |

| | | 3= Very |

|20k1 |DISABSVS |Services to students with |1= Yes |

| | disabilities |2= No |

|20k2 |DISVSUSE |Frequency: Services to students|1= Never |

| | with disabilities |2= Once |

| | | 3= Two or three |

| | | times |

| | | 4= Four or more |

| | | times |

|20k3 |DISVSAT |Satisfaction: Services for |0= Not applicable |

| | people with disabilities |1= Not at all |

| | | 2= Somewhat |

| | | 3= Very |

|21a |LNDSTUDY |With a class, or through |1= Strongly |

| | another experience at this |Disagree |

| | college: I learned to improve |2= Disagree |

| | my study skills (listening, |3= Neutral |

| | note taking, highlighting |4= Agree |

| | readings, working with others, |5= Strongly Agree |

| | etc.) | |

|21b |LNDACAWK |With a class, or through |1= Strongly |

| | another experience at this |Disagree |

| | college: I learned to |2= Disagree |

| | understand my academic |3= Neutral |

| | strengths and weaknesses |4= Agree |

| | | 5= Strongly Agree |

|21c |LNDKLLS |With a class, or through |1= Strongly |

| | another experience at this |Disagree |

	college: I learned skills and	2= Disagree	
	strategies to improve my	3= Neutral	
	test-taking ability	4= Agree	
		5= Strongly Agree	
22	PSOURACA	Thinking about your experiences	1= Instructors
	FROM THE TIME OF YOUR DECISION	2= College staff	
	TO ATTEND THIS COLLEGE THROUGH	(not instructors)	
	THE END OF THE FIRST THREE	3= Friends, family	
	WEEKS OF YOUR FIRST	or other students	
	SEMESTER/QUARTER, what has been	4= Computerized	
	your MAIN source of academic	degree advisor	
	advising (help with academic	system	
	goal-setting, planning, course	5= College Web	
	recommendations, graduation	site	
	requirements, etc.)?	6= Other college	
		materials	
23	ASNPERs	Was a specific person assigned	1= Yes
	to you so you could see him/her	2= No	
	each time you needed		
	information or assistance		
24a	PREPCLAS	During the first three weeks of	1= None
	your first SEMESTER/QUARTER at	2= 1-5 hours	
	this college, about how many	3= 6-10 hours	
	hours did you spend in a	4= 11-20 hours	
	typical 7-day week doing the	5= 21-30 hours	
	following?	6= More than 30	
	Preparing for class (in a	hours	
	typical 7-day week)		
24b	WORKPAY	During the first three weeks of	1= None
	your first SEMESTER/QUARTER at	2= 1-5 hours	
	this college, about how many	3= 6-10 hours	
	hours did you spend in a	4= 11-20 hours	
	typical 7-day week doing the	5= 21-30 hours	
	following?	6= More than 30	
	Working for pay (in a typical	hours	

|| |7-day week) | |

|25 |AGAINCL |When do you plan to take |1= I will |

|| |classes at this college again? |accomplish my |

|| |goal(s) this |

|| |semester/quarter |

|| |and will not be |

|| |returning |

|| |2= I have no |

|| |current plans to |

|| |return |

|| |3= Within the next|

|| |12 months |

|| |4= Uncertain |

|26a |MATHALLF |While in high school, did you |0= Not Applicable |

|| |take math every school year? |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|26b |MATHSNYR |While in high school, did you |0= Not Applicable |

|| |take math during your senior |1= Yes |

|| |year? |2= No |

|27 |RECOCOLL |Would you recommend this |1= Yes |

|| |college to a friend or family |2= No |

|| |member? | |

|28 |HSGRADE |In what range was your overall |1= A |

|| |high school grade average? |2= A- to B+ |

|| |3= B |

|| |4= B- to C+ |

|| |5= C |

|| |6= C- or lower |

|29 |SEX |Your sex |1= Male |

|| |2= Female |

|30 |AGENEW |Mark your age group |1= Under 18 |

|| |2= 18 to 19 |

|| |3= 20 to 21 |

|| |4= 22 to 24 |

|| |5= 25 to 29 |

|| |6= 30 to 39 |

|| |7= 40 to 49 |

|| |8= 50 to 64 |

|| |9= 65+ |

|31 |MARRSTAT |Are you married? |1= Yes |

|| |2= No |

|32 |CHILDREN |Do you have children who live |1= Yes |

|| |with you and depend on you for |2= No |

|| |their care? ||

|33 |ENGNAT |Is English your native (first) |1= Yes |

|| |language? |2= No |

|34 |INTERNAT |Are you an international |1= Yes |

|| |student or nonresident alien? |2= No |

|35 |DIVERSIT |What is your racial |1= American Indian|

|| |identification? |or Native American|

|| |2= Asian, Asian |

|| |American or |

|| |Pacific Islander |

|| |3= Native Hawaiian|

|| |4= Black or |

|| |African American, |

|| |Non-Hispanic |

|| |5= White, |

|| |Non-Hispanic |

|| |6= Hispanic, |

|| |Latino, Spanish |

|| |7= Other |

|36 |DEGREE |What is the highest academic |1= None |

|| |certificate or degree you have |2= GED |

|| |learned? |3= High school |

|| |diploma |

|| |4= |

|| |Vocational/technic|

|| |al certificate |

|| |5= Associate |

|| |degree |

|| |6= Bachelor's |

|| |degree |

|| |7= |

|| |Master's/Doctoral/|

|| |Professional |

|37a |CERTPRGM |Please indicate whether your |1= Yes |

|| |goal(s) for attending this |2= No |

|| |college include the following: | |

|| |To complete a certificate | |

|37b |ASSOCDEG |Please indicate whether your |1= Yes |

|| |goal(s) for attending this |2= No |

|| |college include the following: | |

|| |To obtain an Associate degree | |

|37c |TR4YR |Please indicate whether your |1= Yes |

|| |goal(s) for attending this |2= No |

|| |college include the following: | |

|| |To transfer to a 4-year college| |

|| |or university | |

|38 |This question asks students to select all options that apply. |

|| |To permit multiple responses, the question is represented in |

|| |the codebook by seven separate items the student either checks|

|| |or does not check. |

|38a |MOTHED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

|| |at least some college? Mother|1= Response |

|38b |FATHED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

|| |at least some college? Father|1= Response |

|38c |SIBLINED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

|| |at least some college? |1= Response |

|| |Brother/Sister | |

|38d |CHILDED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

|| |at least some college? Child |1= Response |

|38e |SPOUCED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

|| |at least some college? |1= Response |

|| |Spouse/Partner | |

|38f |LGUARDED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

| | |at least some college? Legal |1= Response |

| | |Guardian | |

|38g |NONED |Who in your family has attended|0= No Response |

| | |at least some college? None |1= Response |

| | |of the above | |

The items below contain course level data from the Course Schedule File:

|Variable Name |Item Description/Variable |Response Value |

| |Label | |

|in_analysis |Included in analysis |0=False |

| | |1=True |

|In |Survey number in range for |0=False |

| |packet |1=True |

|sdate |Course start date |

|edate |Course end date |

|camploc |Campus location |

|secno |Section number |

|courseno |Course number |

|courname |Course full name |

|bldg |Building |

|room |Room |

|meetdays |Class meeting days |

|instrnam |Instructor name |

|depart |Department |

|maxenrol |Maximum enrollment |

|stime |Class start time |

|etime |Class end time |

The items below refer to derived SENSE variables:

|Variable Name |Item Description/Variable |Response Value |

| |Label | |

|return |Entering/Returning students |0=Entering |

| | |1=Returning |

|studage |Traditional/Nontraditional |1=Traditional Age |

| |age students |Student (24 and |

| | |younger) |

	2=Nontraditional Age	
	Student (25 and	
	older)	
developm	Enrolled in one or more	1=Developmental
	developmental education	2=Non-Developmental
	classes	
firstgen	First-Generation/Not	1=First-Generation
	First-Generation Students	(neither parent
	attended college)	
	2=Not	
	First-Generation (at	
	least one parent	
	attended college)	
whitemin	White/Non-Asian minority	1=White
	students	2=Non-Asian Minority

The items below contain course level data from the class information sheet

Variable Name	Item	Response Value
	Description/Variable	
	Label	
SRVADMN	Survey administered by	1=Faculty
	2=Survey Administrator	
NUMSTU	Number of students in attendance	
ADMNTIME	Total administration time: in minutes	
ADMNDATE	Administration date	

The items below are calculated weights and benchmarks:

Variable Name	Item Description/Variable Label
iweight	Institutional weight based on part-time/full-time
	enrollment
earlycon	Early connections benchmark score (rescaled from 0
	to 1)
hiexpect	High expectations and aspirations benchmark score
	(rescaled from 0 to 1)
acadplan	Clear academic plan and pathway benchmark score
	(rescaled from 0 to 1)
collread	Effective track to college readiness benchmark score

| |(rescaled from 0 to 1) |

|engaglrn |Engaged learning benchmark score (rescaled from 0 to
| |1) |

|acsocsup |Academic and social support network benchmark score |
| |(rescaled from 0 to 1) |

The items below are standardized benchmarks:

|Variable Name |Item Description/Variable Label |

|earlycon_std |Standardized early connections benchmark score (mean|
| |of 50) |

|hiexpect_std |Standardized high expectations and aspirations |
| |benchmark score (mean of 50) |

|acadplan_std |Standardized clear academic plan and pathway |
| |benchmark score (mean of 50) |

|collread_std |Standardized effective track to college readiness |
| |benchmark score (mean of 50) |

|engaglrn_std |Standardized engaged learning benchmark score (mean |
| |of 50) |

|acsocsup_std |Standardized academic and social support network |
| |benchmark score (mean of 50) |

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Her previous employment includes nursing home administration, mental health counseling and administration as well as academic compliance. Marie served as a sociology faculty member, where she was nominated faculty of the year, prior to her doctoral studies at The University of Texas at Austin in May

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